

Business models and processes with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of areas for the introduction of IT solutions WP3 Y1Q4

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Executive Summary

This document describes in details all the findings related to:

- Task 2.4: Business model implementation scenarios and relative support system definition;
- Task 3.1: Design of the business models for the delivery of assistance and independent living services;
- Task 3.2: Design of ToBe organisational and process model including variants for each local needs.

The document aims to define 4 Country-specific Business Model (BM) Canvases containing a subset of the elements included within the General BM of the D2.2, which identified the variables to be considered in order to describe the BM of a digital solution used for assisting elderly people with Mild Cognitive Impairments (MCI) and Mild Dementia. This first objective is achieved through 2 tools:

- **The Business Model Environment:** which mainly adopts as inputs the D1.1 in order to deeply scan the DECI environment;
- **The Coherence Matrix:** which exploits all the information gained from D1.2, D1.3, D2.1 and the “Alignment with technological partners”, mixing various key variables regarding DECI project to discern between: (i) coherent and incoherent pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need; (ii) relevant and not relevant pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need; (iii) Country-specific and common among Country pairs Functionality-Action.

To deepen the Value Proposition and reduce the complexity to be tackled in the design of the overall DECI BM, packages of service model common to all the 4 countries are highlighted crossing the most relevant cluster of needs with the relative cluster of functionalities. For example, the functionalities regarding the monitoring of patient’s status have an impact mostly on the needs related to the diagnosis and assessment, as the ones concerning the communication between care providers. Furthermore, it is important to underline that some clusters of functionalities are able to meet more clusters of needs. These clusters are those on which focusing first in the definition of the pilots. At the same time, there are some clusters of needs that are covered by less functionalities than others: these are the needs that are more difficult to meet and that it’s important to monitor.

The general value proposition is enriched with further packages of country-specific service models, also describing how they affects:

- **The upstream building blocks:** Key partners, Key activities and Key resources;
- **The downstream building blocks:** Customer Relationships, Customer Segments and Channels;
- **Cost and revenues:** Cost Structure and Revenue Streams.

Italian clinicians underline the importance of other needs in addition to those common to all the countries—particularly the patient physical needs, the caregiver needs and the ones regarding patient environment. This has an impact on the other building blocks: for example, the caregiver has a central role and must be engaged and informed about the evolution of symptoms and of the disease, and a personal assistance based on human interaction should be preferred also to meet the patient psychological needs. At the same time, considering the Italian environment, not only Revenue Streams should be a B2P and B2C mix, but also, considering the central role of the caregivers, their training costs must be considered as relevant to meet their needs.

Also Swedish clinicians underline the importance of other needs in addition to those common to all the countries—particularly the patient physical needs that can be met provisioning automatic reminder to patients for the performing of scheduled activities. This has an impact on the other building blocks. For example, provide alerts based on patient’s activities meet all the 5 clusters of needs: also considering the sparse population, this mean that is important to provide automatic remote feedbacks to the patients. This is possible not only mapping the patient’s activities, but also through an engagement of the patient and keeping the relationship with him or, if present, his caregiver (considering the low tendency to informal care). In this sense, the caregiver has not a central role and is better to focus on the engagement and empowerment of the patients, keeping him informed about the evolution of symptoms and of the disease. Finally, Revenue Streams should change depending on the specific country council, because the number of private primary care providers varies widely between the county councils (in some urban county councils up to 60% of the primary care providers may be private, whereas in other county councils only a few private providers can be found).

Spanish clinicians underline the importance of other needs in addition to those common to all the countries: particularly the caregiver needs and the ones regarding physical activities of the patients. This has an impact on the other building blocks. For example, provide alerts based on patient’s activities meet all the 5 clusters of patient needs: this mean that is crucial not only mapping the patient’s activities, but also through an engagement of the patient, keeping this relationship with him and his caregiver. Furthermore, to make available remote-based training programs tailored on individual patient’s characteristics, it is important to personalize the service, making it properly inserted within his daily activities.

Israeli clinicians have not highlighted other needs in addition to those common to all the countries, and the unique specificity is related to the diagnosis and assessment, that the clinicians considers particularly relevant for the monitoring of patient’s activities. Considering the Israeli environment, to meet the patient psychological needs, a possible key partnership could be the one with the “Supportive neighborhoods” program, that provide a “basket” that include especially social

activities, as well as the safety and security of their homes. Furthermore, in addition to the Health Maintenance Organisations (HMOs), is crucial to involve the Day care centers, where special programs for the cognitively impaired, including elderly people with Alzheimer’s disease and other types of dementia, has been established. Finally, Revenue Streams should be based on a B2B model. However, cannot be excluded a B2C model for some services that would be sold directly to the patient, for example the ones for monitoring the patient’s status or for the cognitive stimulation.

The DECI Business Models are validated with members of the Scientific Advisory Board, in order to underline the feasibility of the designed business models and the alignments with the DECI scenarios designed within WP1.

This document is aimed also at modelling and engineering the care processes for patients with Cognitive Impairment in the pilot countries involved in the project via the pervasive use of digital technologies, taking inputs from the care process analysis performed within the WP1 and the evidence emerged from the technological benchmark analysis (WP2). The analysis highlighted four common phases to every care process for people with cognitive impairment:

- Noticing symptoms and first detection,
- Assessment and diagnosis,
- Treatment and care service definition,
- Service delivery and follow-up.

What emerges from the AS-IS processes analysis is that all the local sites have the same process at a high-level analysis. The main challenge was to combine the actors in the care system, because in each local site there are the same care actors organized in a different way. This is due not also to the characterization of each local care system, but also to the role of each clinical partner in the care network involved in the project. Indeed, the pilot sites are different from each other: HUG is focused only on the health-care service, MAC offers both health-care and socio-care services and, finally, VGR and FDG offer a socio-health care service integrated with external Community.

Starting from these evidences, the TO-BE processes desired by each pilot site has been described. The main differences from the AS-IS processes concern the fourth macro-phase “Service delivery and follow up”. Only VGR will introduce a periodical screening in the first macro-phase “Noticing symptoms and first detection” and only HUG will improve the activity of the “Definition of health care/social care services” in the macro-phase “Treatment and care service definition”. This focus on the last part of the flow is also caused by the type of technological solutions, that are mainly directed to the home assistance.

With the aim of monitoring the performances related to the delivery processes, and to analyse the benefits associated with the development of DECI solution, a dedicated

analysis has been performed starting from preliminary elements from WP6, where the full set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be described, monitored and implemented. Particularly, through the adoption of the **Cluster Impact Matrix** – a tool mixing the main categories of KPIs with the 4 process phases considered and the Key Functionalities emerged from the previous analysis – it was possible to highlight:

- Clusters of Functionalities that are characterized by a relevant potential impact on the various pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs;
- Pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs that are not covered by any Cluster of Functionality;
- Country-Specific Clusters of Functionalities characterized by a relevant potential impact on some pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs.

To summarize, the deliverable produces four main outputs:

1. It provides a scalable, solid and general framework, which can be exploited also in context different from the ones in which DECI pilots will be accomplished;
2. It identifies and assess the feasibility of key service packages to be delivered in DECI, which are useful for the following phases associated to pilot design;
3. It provides a care processes model and describes as-is and to-be care processes in the 4 pilot settings;
4. It offers insights about the potential impact of the various key service packages identified, in order to estimate the area of benefits that DECI project could impact.

It is easily understandable that all the knowledge generated and described in this document is the key starting point for the future tasks within DECI project (first of all WP3, WP5 and WP6) and potentially for other future projects that can treasure it in order to continue the journey undertaken to support the treatment of MCI and Mild Dementia.

1 Introduction

As already reported in D1.5, analysis performed during the first phases of the DECI project, within WP1 and WP2, confirmed the need of a bilateral approach to design the DECI Business Models and the related scenarios. From one side, indeed, it is necessary to define the DECI Business Models starting from a consolidated literature analysis, from the other side the related DECI scenarios can be designed only thanks to the contribution of stakeholders directly involved in the care process for people with MCI and mild Dementia. Given a restricted time to perform the focal activity of DECI Business Models design, the Consortium decided to follow a parallel double-tier perspective:

1. **A top-down design process of the DECI Business Model**, fed by theoretical and empirical analysis performed on all topics within WP1 and WP2;
2. **A bottom-up design process of pilot scenarios**, deeply participative for stakeholders within and external to DECI partners' organizations (Local Brainstorming Sessions – LBSs), also fed by benchmark analysis of similar projects and field-study of processes, organizations, clinical needs and information systems at each local site (outputs of WP1 and WP2).

The two perspectives – bottom-up and top-down – have been run in parallel, but are heavily intertwined, thanks to a strong link between local-based and theoretical modelling activities. These two design processes, indeed, should generate aligned results in order to demonstrate that the business models created from top-down perspective correctly suite the real local requirements emerged from the bottom-up perspective.

All discussions, firstly, provided inputs to Task 1.3 and T2.4 in terms of DECI scenarios (D1.5). Then, the two approaches fed the present D3.1 and, in particular, the following tasks:

- Task 3.1: Business Models (BMs) for delivery of assistance and independent living services;
- Task 3.2: home care process models in each pilot site;
- Task 2.4: business feasibility check of the BMs.

Finally, those discussions will provide input to the Task 3.3 for defining the requirements (D3.2) and T3.4 for designing different implementation settings (D3.3-D3.4).

The following figure depicts the rationale of the two perspectives.

Figure 1 – Top-down and bottom-up perspectives

This deliverable reports the main results of the top-down approach, executed within three different tasks and articulated as following:

- Chapter 2: description of the Business Models designed within Task 3.1, with a description of the applied methodological approach, the DECI Models Canvases and DECI Service Models and, finally, the results of the feasibility study of the designed Business Models, performed within Task 2.4 with the support of the Scientific Advisory Board;
- Chapter 3: description of TO-BE process models designed within T3.2, with a description of the applied methodological approach, a general home care process, the AS-IS process models and the TO-BE process models in each pilot site;
- Chapter 4: preliminary assessment of the Business Models performed within T3.1, underlining the impacts of the Business Models in each macro-phase of the home care general model.

Those results, with findings of previous tasks, will be the input for the T3.3 aimed at defining the requirements and the definition of the ICT infrastructure and application and for the T3.4 aimed at designing the different implementation settings.

2 A comprehensive Business Model for DECI: definition of the Digital Environment and of the relative service model

This Chapter describes the results of the performed analysis that are divided into 3 paragraphs. Chapter 2.2 describes the results regarding the Business Model Canvases in all the four pilot contexts. Chapter 2.3 describes the results regarding DECI Service Model both from the point of view of the General Service Model and of the 4 Country-specific Service Models. Chapter 2.4. outlines the performed feasibility check of the business models, which follows the taken routes of the top-down developed DECI business model factors and assess the feasibility by means of a Strategic Advisory Board and expert opinion consultation.

2.1 Objective and methodology

This chapter describes the goals of Task 3.1 and the methodology adopted to pursue them. The process is based on 2 subsequent steps that allow first to obtain the BM_{Canvases} and, then, the DECI Service Model. Figure 1 shows these two steps, together with the previous tasks of the projects that have been exploited in order to accomplish each step.

Figure 2 - Methodological model

BM_{Canvases} are composed by 4 Country-specific business model canvases containing a subset of the elements included within the Business Model of the Deliverable 2.2, called BM_{General}. Furthermore, BM_{Canvases} goes into detail about the subset of these elements, which are meticulously listed. Conversely, BM_{General} is characterized by a list of all the possible elements/variables within the 9 building blocks of the BM but without any difference among Countries or links between Functionalities and Needs of the various Customer Segments.

DECI Service Model contains 4 Service Models mainly focused on Value Propositions in all the 4 Countries in which pilot projects will be developed and, particularly, on the common value propositions among the aforementioned 4 Countries.

The first step is made through 2 tools: (i) **Business Model Environment** (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010);(ii) **Coherence Matrix**. These tools are used, on the one hand, to reduce the multitude of elements proposed in BM_{General} (see D2.2). On the other hands, the tools allow prioritizing the required activities for the implementation of pilot projects—distinguishing among relevant and irrelevant elements.

Business Model Environment is referred to the homonymous framework developed by Osterwalder & Pigneur (2010). It is useful to understand how Country-specific contexts will affect the final shape of the business model – enabling or avoiding some of the elements raised through the analysis of the literature (D.2.2).

Coherence Matrix is a tool developed by the research group and allows to discern between: (a) coherent and incoherent pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need; (b) relevant and not relevant pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need; (c) Country-specific and common among Country pairs Functionality-Action.

The second step allows to switch from BM_{Canvases} to DECI Service Model that provides a synthesis of the overriding elements of the Value Proposition that are common among Countries (General Service Model). Furthermore, DECI Service Model includes also the description of the other elements that are Country-specific (Further specific Service Model).

This step takes into account the context-specific as-is processes characterizing the 4 pilot sites described within the D1.1 and D3.2. Therefore, DECI Service Model constitutes the input for the D3.2 because justifies the choice made regarding the future state of the processes.

2.1.1 First Step: From BM_{GENERAL} to Country-specific BM_{CANVASES}

This paragraph describes how to move from the BM_{General} to BM_{Canvases}. Chapter 2.1.1.1 describes the methodology related to the Business Model Environment, while Chapter 2.1.1.2 describes the principles and the underlying concepts of the Coherence Matrix.

2.1.1.1 Business Model Environment

The Business Model Environment (BME) adopts as inputs the D1.1 and other documents and reports (Anell, Glenngard, & Merkur, 2012; Ferre et al., 2014; Garcia-Armesto, Abadia-Taira, Duran, Hernandez-Quevedo, & Bernal-Delgado, 2010; Lupianez, Maghiros, & Abadie, 2013; Rosen & Merkur, 2009; World Health Organization, 2015). These materials have been exploited to have a detailed knowledge of the context in which the pilots will be accomplished.

Indeed, a deep environmental scanning is crucial to adapt the BM more effectively to shifting external forces, allowing to take into account drivers and constraints – or more generally, specificities – that really affect the context. Furthermore, a better understanding of the context allows to evaluate not only the current external forces, but also in which direction the BM could evolve, preparing it for the future.

Finally, the BME organizes and describes the key contextual variables useful to synthetically characterize each Country involved in DECI project, according to the following 4 macro-areas:

- Key trends;
- Macro-economic forces;
- Industry forces;
- Market forces.

The original model has been interpreted and adapted to the DECI project, associating to each of the 4 macro-areas pertinent variables useful to describe the external forces – intended as the specificities of each national health system – in order to identify drivers and constraints in the design phase of the BM. The tool allows scanning the environment of the project and adapting the BM more effectively to shifting external forces.

The list of the 18 key variables used in the model has been validated with the DECI partners, as well as the related contents regarding the context of each country. With respect to the macro-areas (and their related variables) to the 4 countries involved in the project, the BME takes the form of a 4x18 matrix as shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1 – The Business Model Environment structure

	Key trends			Macro-economic forces			Industry forces			Market forces		
	Variable 1	Variable 2	Variable m	Variable 1	Variable 2	Variable p	Variable 1	Variable 2	Variable r	Variable 1	Variable 2	Variable q
Country ₁												
Country ₂												
Country ₃												
Country ₄												

1. Key trends:

- The National socio-healthcare system overview, which allows to get the general setting of the health system. (source: D1.1).
- The general government expenditure on health, as a percentage of total expenditure on health (World Health Organization, 2015).
- The private expenditure on health, as a percentage of total expenditure on health (World Health Organization, 2015).
- The “Out-of-pocket” expenditure, as a percentage of private expenditure on health (World Health Organization, 2015).
- The *per-capita* total expenditure on health, converted to international dollars using purchasing power parity (PPP int. \$) (World Health Organization, 2015).

2. Macro-economic forces:

- The payment mechanisms, for example policies regarding payment for health services and reimbursement (Anell et al., 2012; Ferre et al., 2014; Garcia-Armesto et al., 2010; Rosen & Merkur, 2009).

- The policies regarding the sources of revenue and financial flow, for example General Government, private insurance and out-of-pocket (Anell et al., 2012; Ferre et al., 2014; Garcia-Armesto et al., 2010; Rosen & Merkur, 2009).

3. Industry forces:

- The balance between Public and Private healthcare, for example: has the health system a universal nature? (Anell et al., 2012; Ferre et al., 2014; Garcia-Armesto et al., 2010; Rosen & Merkur, 2009).
- Centralization VS Decentralization: how the responsibility for health care services is divided between the different levels? And how is it organized? Are the local authorities autonomous in managing and defining their care services? (Anell et al., 2012; Ferre et al., 2014; Garcia-Armesto et al., 2010; Rosen & Merkur, 2009).
- Which are the main actors involved in the national health system. (Anell et al., 2012; Ferre et al., 2014; Garcia-Armesto et al., 2010; Rosen & Merkur, 2009).
- Number of Health and social care integration Hospitals per 100.000 population (World Health Organization, 2015).
- Number of psychiatric beds per million population (World Health Organization, 2015).

4. Market forces:

- The percentage of population aged > 60 years compared to the overall population (World Health Organization, 2015).
- The life expectancy at age 60 (World Health Organization, 2015).
- The estimated prevalence of dementia per 1.000 population (OECD, 2015; Prince et al., 2013).
- The percentage of population living in urban areas (World Health Organization, 2015).
- The population Information Technologies (IT) readiness, measured as the percentage of population that access to the internet and use it at home every day (Lupianez et al., 2013).
- The tendency to informal care, measured as the percentage of population that is taking care of person with long-term illness or disability (Lupianez et al., 2013).

In the Appendix, all the 18 key variables are described for each of the 4 countries involved in DECI.

2.1.1.2 Coherence Matrix

Coherence Matrix (CM) is a tool that exploits all the information gained from the previous Deliverables produced within the DECI project. Therefore, it adopts as inputs the D1.2, D1.3, D2.1 and the “Alignment with technological partners”, and mixes various key variables regarding DECI project:

- Technologies (D2.1);

- Functionalities (D2.1, D2.2, “Alignment with tech. partners”);
- Patient’s needs (D1.2, D1.3);
- Needs of the Overall system (D1.3);
- Actions to address the needs (D1.3);
- Patients’ clusters (D1.2);
- Country-specific needs (D1.2, D1.3).

CM links all these dimensions and allows discerning between:

- Coherent and not coherent pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need (i.e. need of the patient or of the overall system) (Chapter 0);
- Relevant and not relevant pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need (Chapter 0);
- Country-specific and common among Countries pairs Functionality-Action (Chapter 2.1.2.1).

All these elements contribute to the identification of the common value proposition, therefore, to the definition of the General Service Model, and also of the Country-specific value propositions. The latter, together with the General Service Model, define the overall DECI Service Model.

The next paragraphs are structured and organized as follows: first are described the dimensions of the CM, and then are showed the underlying logics that links all the dimensions of the CM.

Dimensions of the Coherence Matrix

The Coherence Matrix is characterized by the following 5 dimensions: (i) Countries; (ii) Customer segment; (iii) Functionalities; (iv) Actions to address the Needs of the patient and of the overall system; (v) Relevance of the specific Need. As an example, **Table 2** shows the structure of the Coherence Matrix.

Table 2 – Coherence Matrix dimensions

	Relevance of the Action ₁ in the Country _p	Relevance of the Action ₂ in the Country _p	...	Relevance of the Action _m in the Country _p
Customer Segment ₁				
Customer Segment ₂				
...				
Customer Segment _q				

	Action ₁	Action ₂	...	Action _m
Functionality ₁				
Functionality ₂				
...				
Functionality _n				

Countries

The Countries considered in the analysis are the following: (a) Israel; (b) Italy; (c) Spain; (d) Sweden. In each of these context, a pilot project will be developed and it will be characterized by different value propositions due to the peculiarities of the specific backgrounds.

Customer Segments

Following the D1.3, this analysis considers the same customer segments, therefore it distinguishes between Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and Mild Dementia (MD) patients.

Functionalities

The vast amount of functionalities, emerged within the D2.1 (from the literature analysis and from the description of the solutions offered by the partner of the DECI project), the D2.2 and the “Alignment with technological partners”, constitute the first axis of the CM, and are listed below (alphabetical order):

1. Activity monitoring through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station): stand / sit / walk / steps + intensity of activity;
2. Analysis of structured patients’ activity patterns and sharing of information with primary and secondary care actors;
3. Automatic provision and submitting of questionnaires (of various nature, including patient’s health status and to support change detection) to care-involved subjects;

4. Automatic provision of feedbacks and alerts on patients' progresses or deterioration;
5. Automatic provision of feedbacks and alerts to formal and informal caregivers based on structured analysis of patient-specific characteristics (thanks to de definition of patient-specific threshold and reference parameters);
6. Automatic provision of patients-tailored training programs (gives instruction on physical activities in home environment according to a personalized training scheme);
7. Automatic provision of remote feedback on patients' activities, building on long-time data analysis on patients' status;
8. Automatic provision of remote real-time feedback on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities;
9. Automatic provision of remote real-time patient-tailored motivational messages based on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities;
10. Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's blood pressure;
11. Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's heart rate;
12. Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's O₂ saturation;
13. Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's weight (scale-based detection);
14. Availability of personalized and adaptable remote-based training programs automatically tailored on individual patient's characteristics;
15. Cognitive games/exercises to stimulate patients to preserve cognitive/executive functions;
16. Coherence check between clinical guidelines / protocols and data gathered as part of care activities;
17. Data sharing and integration between outdoor-functioning monitoring devices and Hospitals' Information Systems (HIS);
18. Data sharing and integration between outdoor-functioning monitoring devices and rehabilitation and treatment tools;
19. Data storage from and sharing to external Electronic Medical Record (EMR) or other care management tools;
20. Displaying of care sheets and clinical data;
21. Drug management;
22. Early detection/diagnosing solutions;
23. Emergency calls or advise (activation of third-party external service/rescue team) for elderly monitoring at home (indoor);
24. Enablement in 1-to-1 remote interaction between patients and care provider;
25. Enablement of multidisciplinary teamwork across care providers, doctors and informal caregivers (or some of these);
26. Evaluation and monitoring of cognitive skills and monitoring of decay curves and other trends;

27. Evaluation of user position “user not at home” (disconnection from base station) for elderly monitoring at home (indoor);
28. Fall detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor);
29. Gathering on non-structured information on patient’s health status from informal caregivers or social caretakers;
30. GPS localization (outdoor) of the patient - under development as an additional ‘device’ that could be inserted within a person’s item (e.g. clip, show sensor, ...);
31. GPS-based patient monitoring and structured health-based data gathering for outdoor step counting or activity monitoring (including detection of falls);
32. Home environmental temperature and humidity control to support home care (indoor);
33. Immobility detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor)
34. Informal communication (messaging) among various actors (e.g.: family members and doctors);
35. Locate items;
36. Management of a structured fall events record;
37. Periodic registration of subjective observations on behavioral disorders and side effects of medications by patients and informal caregivers;
38. Provision of automatic real-time feedback to patients’ performing pre-scheduled physical activities;
39. Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity;
40. Real-time response to patients’ distress calls (via call center);
41. Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is formally required to provide a yes/no answer and a video proof of the performed activity);
42. Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is formally required to provide a yes/no answer);
43. Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is monitored real-time by sensors when performing the activity);
44. Sharing / viewing of clinical guidelines and protocols among formal and informal caregivers (or some of them);
45. Sharing of a treatment plan among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these);
46. Sharing of information on patient’s monitoring activities among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these);
47. Simulate presence and support to dial relatives;
48. Step counting through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station);
49. Storage of information on patient’s monitoring activities;
50. Tele-consultation (tele-presence) functionalities allowing patients and professionals to communicate to each other visually;

51. Training of patients (and other people not already affected by Cognitive Impairment) to preserve their physical capabilities and executive functions;
52. Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities;
53. Wayfinding support;
54. Wearing check sensor elderly monitoring at home (indoor).

Actions to Address the Needs of the Patient and of the Overall System

Following the D1.3, which exploits the analysis of D1.1, D1.2, CCWs and LBS, the other axis of the CM contains all the required actions to address the various needs (**Table 3** and Table 4).

Table 3 – Patient needs and actions to address the needs

Need category	Need	Action to address the need
Patient environmental needs	The person might not have an adequate and appropriate home	Assuring suitable living space
	The person might have problems keeping their home tidy and organized	Assuring maintenance of living space
	Buy food	Shopping assistant
	Eat in a safe way	Malnutrition avoidance
	Patients not able to keep track of their expenses	Money budgeting
	Caring for someone else	Caring for someone else
	Wandering expose people to dangers	tracking / prevent wandering
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information about the disease, symptoms and evolution Information on current condition and treatment The patient can contact a health professional for questioning
	People might need support for designing a physical activity plan	Physical activity plan and exercise
	Drugs (chronic disease management)	Education on side-effects on medication treatment by clinical pharmacologist or clinical team coordinated by case manager
	Have a prescription by general practitioner	Medication plan
	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions	Medication Reminders
	Eyesight/ hearing/ Communication	
	People can have high risk of fall	Fall detection
	People need to be able to move	Immobility detection
	Keeping neat and tidy	education, follow-up
	Continance	

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Access to non-pharmacological treatment	
		Alternative treatments	
		Brief psychotherapies	
		Psychopharmacological treatment	
		Remote monitoring of psychological status	
	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Cognitive stimulation	
		Online Cognitive Training	
		Alcohol abuse prevention	Alcohol abuse prevention
		Inadvertent self-harm	
		Deliberate self-harm	
Psychotic symptoms	Monitoring hallucinations or delusions		
Patient Social needs	Patient refuses help and sociality outside home / lives alone in an isolated hose / does not have partners	social interaction	
	Intimate relationship		
	The person might not have relatives / friends / etc. With whom realising social activities	Recommendation of social activities	
Patient general needs	People with cognitive problems might have problems with other people that might take advantage of their condition (i.e. using their money)	Abuse/Neglect prevention	
	People might not be aware of available social services	information of the social benefits available in the area	
	People are not able to contact social services or social workers	Patients can contact the social worker	
	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	
Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Discuss financial and long-term care plans	

Table 4 – Overall system needs and actions to address the needs

Need category	Need	Action to address the need
Detection	Patient detection	Reactive detection
		Proactive search I (Database parameters)
		Proactive search II (75 th birthday)
Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical	Clinical diagnosis
		Overall medical condition
		Medical instability
	Psychological	Behavior and mood
		Anosognosia
	Physical	Assess the Risk of malnutrition
	Functional	ADL
		risk for falls
		Frailty
	Socio economic	Assess Socio economic state
	Caregiver burden	Assess Caregiver burden
Clinical team needs	Coordinated care	Coordination of care
	Information sharing	Clinical team information sharing
	Improve diagnosis method	Improve diagnosis method
	Standard of care	Advising on deciding course of action
		Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies
	Standard of care	Standardized care pathway
	Accessibility	Facilitating access to medical services in rural/ isolated areas
Longitudinal treatment	comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy+ follow-up	

Need category	Need	Action to address the need
Social care team needs	Information sharing	Health team information sharing (including social care)
		To improve social awareness about the disease
	Accessibility	To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources
		To facilitate access to social services in rural/ isolated areas
Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	To facilitate and to speed up access to social services (Day Centres, Night Centres, etc.)
		Online Cognitive Training
	Overall condition	Monitoring of cognitive condition
		monitoring overall condition
	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions / ensure adherence	measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
		Social care
Caregivers needs	Physical and psychological monitoring of the caregiver	Interventions with the caregiver
		Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease
	Medical information for NFC	Information about the secondary effects of medication
	Communication healthcare prof. - NFC	The caregiver can ask questions to the health professional
	Social care information for NFC	Information about available social services in the area
Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)		

Relevance of the Specific Need

The relevance of the actions to address the various needs are analyzed in D1.3. Furthermore, it is specific for the Country and for the two cluster of patients (i.e. Mild Cognitive Impairment and Mild Dementia). A scale of 1 to 5 rates the perceived importance of an item. A score of "5" refers to an action to address a need which is most important, while a score of "0" reflects that the item is not pertinent to MCI/Dementia or was considered out of the scope of the DECI project (

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Detection	Patient detection	Reactive detection	4			4	0	0	5	4
		Proactive search I (Database parameters)	4			4	0	0	5	3
		Proactive search II (75 th birthday)	4			0	0	0	4	3
Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical	Clinical diagnosis	5		5	5	0	0	5	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Overall medical condition	5		5	5	5	5	4	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Medical instability	0		3	4	0	0	0	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Psychological	Behavior and mood	5		5		5	5	5	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Anosognosia	0		2	2	1	1	0	0
Diagnosis and assessment	Physical	Assess the Risk of malnutrition	5		5	5	5	5	3	5
Diagnosis and assessment	Functional	ADL	5		5	5	5	5	3	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Diagnosis and assessment		risk for falls	5		5	5	5	5	3	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Frailty	5		5	5	5	5	4	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Socio economic	Assess Socio economic state	5		5	5			5	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Caregiver burden	Assess Caregiver burden	5		5	5	5	5	2	4
Patient environmental needs	The person might not have an adequate and appropriate home	Assuring suitable living space	1		1	2	0	0	4	4
Patient environmental needs	The person might have problems keeping their home tidy and organized	Assuring maintenance of living space	3				3	5	2	3
Patient environmental needs	Buy food	Shopping assistant	2		3		3	4	2	4
Patient environmental needs	Eat in a safe way	Malnutrition avoidance	2		4		3	5	2	3

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient environmental needs	Patients not able to keep track of their expenses	Money budgeting	3		2	1	3	5	3	4
Patient environmental needs	Caring for someone else	Caring for someone else	1		0	0	1	0	4	4
Patient environmental needs	Wandering expose people to dangers	tracking / prevent wandering	0		1	3	0	4	0	0
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information about the disease, symptoms and evolution	4		5	5	1	0	4	4
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information on current condition and treatment	4		5	5	2	2	4	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	The patient can contact a health professional for questioning	4		3	3	0	0	5	5
Patient physical needs	People might need support for designing a physical activity plan	Physical activity plan and exercise	4		5	5	2	1	4	4
Patient physical needs	Drugs (chronic disease management)	Education on side-effects on medication treatment by clinical pharmacologist or clinical team coordinated by case manager	4		4	4	0	0	4	4
Patient physical needs	Have a prescription by general practitioner	Medication plan	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Patient physical needs	Remember timing and drugs according to	Medication Reminders	4		4	4	5	5	4	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
	prescriptions									
Patient physical needs	Eyesight/hearing/Communication		0				3	2	2	2
Patient physical needs	People can have high risk of fall	Fall detection	3		3	4	3	5	3	4
Patient physical needs	People need to be able to move	Immobility detection	3		3	3	3	5	3	4
Patient physical needs	Keeping neat and tidy	education, follow-up	2		2	2	3	5	2	2
Patient physical needs	Continence		0		1	1	1	4	0	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety, Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Access to non-pharmacological treatment	4		4	5	5	5	4	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Alternative treatments	4		4	4	3	3	4	4
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Brief psychotherapies	4		4	4	0	0	4	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Psychopharmacological treatment	0		0	0	0	0	3	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Remote monitoring of psychological status	4		5	5	2	2	3	3

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Cognitive stimulation	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Patient psychological needs	Alcohol abuse prevention	Alcohol abuse prevention	3		3	3	3	0	3	3
Patient psychological needs	inadvertent self-harm		1		1	1	0	1	0	0
Patient psychological needs	deliberate self-harm		0				0	1	0	0
Patient psychological needs	Psychotic symptoms	Monitoring hallucinations or delusions	0		3	4	3	4	4	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient Social needs	Patient refuses help and sociality outside home / lives alone in an isolated hose / does not have partners	social interaction	0		3	3	3	3	3	3
Patient Social needs	Intimate relationship		0		0	0	0	0	1	1
Patient Social needs	The person might not have relatives / friends / etc. With whom realising social activities	Recommendation of social activities	1		2	2	1	2	3	4
Patient Social needs	People with cognitive problems might have problems with other people that might take advantage of their condition (i.e. using their money)	Abuse/Neglect prevention	1		1	2	0	2	2	2

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient general needs	People might not be aware of available social services	information of the social benefits available in the area	4		4	4	3	4	4	4
Patient general needs	People are not able to contact social services or social workers	Patients can contact the social worker	4		4	4	2	0	5	5
Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	2	0	4	4
Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Discuss financial and long-term care plans	4		4	4	1	0	4	4
Clinical team needs	Coordinate d care	Coordination of care	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Information sharing	Clinical team information sharing	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Improve diagnosis method	Improve diagnosis method	5		5	5	*	*	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Advising on deciding course of action	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Standardized care pathway	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Accessibility	Facilitating access to medical services in rural/isolated areas	3		2	3	0	0	5	5
Clinical team needs	Longitudinal treatment	comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy+ follow-up	5		5	5	3	3	5	5
Social care team needs	Information sharing	Health team information sharing (including social care)	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Social care team needs	Information sharing	To improve social awareness about the disease	4		5	5	3	3	5	5
Social care team needs	Information sharing	To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources	4		5	5	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate access to social services in rural/ isolated areas	3		3	3	0	0	4	4
Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate and to speed up access to social services (Day Centres, Night Centres, etc.)	3		3	3	5	5	3	4
Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5		3	3	5	5
Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Monitoring of cognitive condition	5		5		3	3	5	5
Follow up	overall condition	monitoring overall condition	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Follow up	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions / ensure adherence	measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment	5		5	5	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Follow up	social care	Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Caregivers needs	Physical and psychological monitoring of the caregiver	Interventions with the caregiver	4		4	4	5	5	5	5
Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease	4		5	5	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the secondary effects of medication	4		4	4	3	3	4	4
Caregivers needs	Communication healthcare prof. - NFC	The caregiver can ask questions to the health professional	4		3	3	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about available social services in the area	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	3	3		

Table 68
 – Appendix).

Links among the dimensions of the Coherence Matrix

As written before, the CM links all the dimensions and allows to discern between:

- Coherent and not coherent pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need (i.e. need of the patient or of the overall system);
- Relevant and not relevant pairs Functionality-Action to address the Need.

Links Between Functionalities and Actions to Address the Needs

The relationships among Functionalities and actions to address the needs are analyzed following the structure of Table 5. The variables $x_{j,i}$, which fill the cells of the $m \times n$ table, are categorical and lead to the identification of functionalities allowing to accomplish the various actions required to address the various needs.

$$x_{j,i} = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if the Functionality}_j \text{ is a key one to accomplish the Action}_i \\ 1 & \text{if the Functionality}_j \text{ allows to accomplish the Action}_i \\ 0 & \text{if the Functionality}_j \text{ does not allow to accomplish the Action}_i \end{cases}$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, m$
 $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$

Table 5 – Relationship among Functionalities and Actions to address the needs

	Action₁	Action₂	...	Action_m
Functionality₁	$x_{1,1}$	$x_{1,2}$...	$x_{1,m}$
Functionality₂	$x_{2,1}$	$x_{2,2}$...	$x_{2,m}$
...
Functionality_n	$x_{n,1}$	$x_{n,2}$...	$x_{n,m}$

Links among Relevance of the specific action to address the need, Countries and Customer segment

The other three dimensions (i.e. Relevance of the specific need, Countries and Customer segment) are taken into account through the clustering – between relevant and not relevant actions to address the need – of the information of Table 66 in the Table 6. The distinction between relevant and not relevant actions is reached through the definition of a threshold beyond which the specific action is considered relevant.

The variables $y_{k,i,p}$ and $z_{i,p}$ are Boolean. The latter allow prioritizing the actions that should be accomplished.

$$y_{k.i.p} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the Action}_i \text{ is relevant to address the need} \\ & \text{of the Customer segment}_k \text{ in the Country}_p \\ 0 & \text{if the Action}_i \text{ is not relevant to address the need} \\ & \text{of the Customer segment}_k \text{ in the Country}_p \end{cases}$$

$$z_{i.p} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the Action}_i \text{ is relevant to address the need} \\ & \text{of at least one Customer segment}_k \text{ in the Country}_p \\ 0 & \text{if the Action}_i \text{ is not relevant to address the need} \\ & \text{of the Customer segment}_k \text{ in the Country}_p \end{cases}$$

$$i = 1, 2, \dots, m$$

$$k = 1, 2, \dots, q$$

$$p = \begin{cases} \text{Israel} \\ \text{Italy} \\ \text{Spain} \\ \text{Sweden} \end{cases}$$

Table 6 – Relationship among Customer segments and Relevance of the Actions to address the needs

	Relevance of the Action ₁ in the Country _p	Relevance of the Action ₂ in the Country _p	...	Relevance of the Action _m in the Country _p
Customer Segment₁	$y_{1.1.p}$	$y_{1.2.p}$...	$y_{1.m.p}$
Customer Segment₂	$y_{2.1.p}$	$y_{2.2.p}$...	$y_{2.m.p}$
...
Customer Segment_q	$y_{q.1.p}$	$y_{q.2.p}$...	$y_{q.m.p}$
Union of Customer segments	$z_{1.p}$	$z_{2.p}$...	$z_{m.p}$

The variables $z_{i,p}$ allow to discern between relevant and not relevant actions to address the needs in a specific Country.

Key pairs Functionality-Action

The intersection among the results of Table 5 and Table 6 is reached through the Boolean variables $X_{j,i,p}$. The latter link the variables $x_{j,i}$ and $z_{i,p}$ and lead to the the CM (Table 7) where:

$$X_{j.i.p} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x_{j,i} = 2 \text{ AND if } z_{i,p} = 1 & i = 1,2, \dots, m; j = 1,2, \dots, n \\ 0 & \text{if } x_{j,i} = 0 \text{ OR } x_{j,i} = 1 & i = 1,2, \dots, m; j = 1,2, \dots, n \end{cases}$$

$$p = \begin{cases} \text{Israel} \\ \text{Italy} \\ \text{Spain} \\ \text{Sweden} \end{cases}$$

Table 7 – Coherence Matrix

	Action₁	Action₂	...	Action_m
Functionality₁	X _{1.1.p}	X _{1.2.p}	...	X _{1.m.p}
Functionality₂	X _{2.1.p}	X _{2.2.p}	...	X _{2.m.p}
...
Functionality_n	X _{n.1.p}	X _{n.2.p}	...	X _{n.m.p}

The variable $X_{j.i.p}$ takes the value “1” if the Functionality j is a key one to accomplish the Action i AND if the Action i is relevant at least in one of the 4 Countries in which Pilot projects will be developed. It allows identifying all the key pairs Functionality-Action to address the n+Needs. Therefore, it helps decision makers in understanding how to prioritize the activities required to implement the pilot projects in the 4 selected Countries.

2.1.2 Second Step: From BM_{CANVASES} to DECI Service Model

This paragraph describes how to move from the BM_{Canvases} to DECI Service Model.

Chapter 2.1.2.1 presents the methodology adopted to select the common value propositions among all 4 Countries (General Service Model) and to take into account also the peculiar aspects of the contexts (Country-specific Service Models), furthermore, it describes the criteria considered to cluster the Functionalities of the General Service Model and of the Country-specific Service Models.

Chapter 2.1.2.2 presents the methodology related to the feasibility check of the Business Models done with members of Scientific Advisory Board.

2.1.2.1 General Service Model and Country-specific Service Models

The Second Step aims to reduce the complexity of the vast amount of elements of the BM_{Canvases} focusing on the key building blocks of Value Proposition and Customer Segments. Regarding the key pairs Functionality-Action it distinguishes between Country-specific and common among all the 4 Countries pairs. Furthermore, it analyzes the results regarding the aforementioned building blocks in order to identify

functionalities that can be grouped in the same service package through a clustering process.

Country-specific VS common among Countries key pairs Functionality-Action

From the starting point of the results of the Table 7, it is possible to add a further condition in the definition of the aforementioned variable $X_{j,i,p}$. Therefore, it is converted from a Boolean variable to a categorical one through the following conditions:

$$X_{j,i,p} = \begin{cases} 2 & \text{if } x_{j,i} = 2 \text{ AND if } z_{i,p} = 1 & i = 1,2, \dots, m; j = 1,2, \dots, n \\ 1 & \text{if } x_{j,i} = 2 \text{ AND if } z_{i,p} = 1 & i = 1,2, \dots, m; j = 1,2, \dots, n \\ 0 & \text{if } x_{j,i} = 0 \text{ OR } x_{j,i} = 1 & i = 1,2, \dots, m; j = 1,2, \dots, n \end{cases}$$

$$p = \begin{cases} \text{Israel} \\ \text{Italy} \\ \text{Spain} \\ \text{Sweden} \end{cases}$$

The variable $X_{j,i,p}$ takes the value “2” if the Functionality j is a key one to accomplish the Action i AND if the Action i is relevant in all the 4 Countries in which Pilot projects will be developed. It takes the value “1” if the Functionality j is a key one to accomplish the Action i AND if the Action i is relevant at least in one of the 4 Countries in which Pilot projects will be developed.

The first condition allows to identify the pairs Functionality-Action that are relevant in all the Countries. Therefore, it helps focusing on the key elements to build the Value Proposition of the General Service Model, while the second condition contributes to the building of the 4 Specific Service Models.

DECI Service Model vs. General Service Model

All the Service Models are characterized by a common set of pairs Functionality-Action (General Service Model) and by further pairs Functionality-Action that are Country-specific (Figure 2).

Figure 3 – Schematic Representation of relationship between $BM_{General}$, General Service Model and Country-specific Service Models

DECI Service model is the union of all the 4 Country-Specific Service Models and the General Service Model constitutes its core (Figure 4).

Figure 4 – Schematic Representation of relationship between General Service Model and DECI Service Model

Cluster Definition

The identification of the functionalities that can be grouped in the same service package has been performed through a clustering process, taking into account the following criteria.

All the Functionalities, related to the pairs Functionality-Action that are relevant in all the 4 Countries (i.e. $X_{j,i,p} = 2$) and then also to those Country-specific pairs, were clustered considering two levels to categorize elements. The first level of clustering refers to the main target of the solution (i.e. patient, care provider, care pathway/treatment plan). This level of analysis was further detailed regarding the patient distinguishing between patient's activities and patient's status. The second level of clustering considers the technological similarities among the Functionalities. As an example, it is possible to consider the following list that will be detailed in Chapter 2.3.1, Chapter 2.3.2, Chapter 2.3.3, Chapter 2.3.4 and Chapter 2.3.5:

- **Patient's status:**
 - Alert;
 - Communication-Cognitive stimulation;
 - Monitoring;
 - Storage and sharing information.
- **Patient's activities:**
 - Alert;
 - Monitoring;
- **Care providers:**
 - Communication;
 - Teamwork;
- **Care pathway/treatment plan:**
 - Monitoring;
 - Sharing information.

2.1.2.2 Feasibility study for the business model inside each organizational context

Usually one in fifty business ideas is actually viable for a commercialisation phase (Bickerdyke I., Lattimore R., and Madge A., 2000). A feasibility study can be an effective way to safeguard against wastage and steer of further development (Wickham P. A., 2006). Within Task 2.4, a feasibility study is performed to deepen the results of previous tasks within WP1, WP2 and WP3. It builds upon the four developed BM implementation scenarios from the pilot sites and the general DECI BM characteristics. The first approach, bottom-up is done via the previous held activities with stakeholders at the pilot locations in the Co-Creation Workshops (CCW) and the Local Brainstorming Sessions (LBS). The second approach, the top-down developed key characteristic for e general DECI BM is already described in the introduction of this document.

This feasibility study aims supporting the decision-making in the management of BM by, on the one hand, eliciting experiences-based qualitative expert-opinion, and, on the other hand, by generating recommendations and limitations.

Furthermore, in line with the task in the Document of Work (“deepening the result of previous task with interviews with healthcare lead authorities stakeholders”), it is good to mention that in all SAB meetings representatives from healthcare lead authorities have been involved.

Per pilot location, a factsheet is presented with the key-elements of the business model. These factsheets are an accumulation of information gathered in the project via the Co-Creation Workshops, Local Brainstorming Sessions (LBS) and deliverables D1.3, D1.5 and D3.1 itself. The factsheets contain information on the process of the designing the BM and local scenarios. The BM elements were structured via the format of the BM Canvas method (Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. 2010). A general introduction and reference to a video explaining BMC was attached as well.

The feasibility check was composed of a questionnaire of 14 statements, to be answered on a 5-point Likert scale and three open questions. The questionnaire was based upon a mixture of BM feasibility and evaluation questions posed by Wirtz (2016) and Thomas (2005). Via the scorecard (see Figure 5), Strategic Advisory Board members and other opinion leaders were invited to provide the consortium with feedback on the feasibility of the BM. The members indicated which of the models (e.g. pilot scenarios) they assessed and checked on feasibility. The statements were prioritized afterwards by the project group, in order to create a ranking with the most critical statements (i.e. the weakest statement first – which has the potential most impact on the failure of the BM until the least impact on failure, strongest statement) along with key success and potential risk factors elicited in the open questions.

		[Strongly disagree]			[Strongly agree]	
		1	2	3	4	5
1	The DECI service model clearly addresses the common value proposition via the patient layer and the overall system layer.					
2	The business models allows to take relevant local/regional health and social system context elements into account (e.g. environment)					
3	The business model delivers the value to the end-users and involved stakeholders.					
4	The business model is NOT disruptive for clinicians and clinical stakeholders (normal patient flow).					
5	The business model is in line with the current trends and developments in care for MCI patients.					
6	The business model is in line with the current trends and developments in care for mild dementia patients.					
7	The business model allows customization to different (end-)users-groups needs and wishes.					
8	The business models takes all the relevant (regional/national) cost and revenue systems into account.					
9	The resources and activities are enabling the business model' value delivery.					
10	There is enough flexibility in the business model to cope with change drivers (technology, markets, (de-)regulation).					
11	The business model offers a real possibility for ubiquitous commercialization in future.					
12	The business model allows growth and scale-up easily.					
13	The displayed pilot scenario design facts are realistic (as described in D1.5).					
14	The business models converge with the pilot scenario design.					
15	What are potential risk factors that should be taken into account by the business model?					
16	What are potential success factors that drive the success of the business model?					
17	Remarks or comments					

Figure 5 - Example of the used scorecard and questions

2.2 Business Model Canvases (BMCs)

In this paragraph the general Business Model described in D2.2 (and specifically in Chapter 4.2 “Business Model Synthesis”) is turned into a comprehensive DECI BM that takes into account just the DECI elements.

Indeed, starting from the general BM - that had the aim to identify the key variables to be considered in order to describe the BM of a digital solution used for assisting elderly people with Mild to Moderate Cognitive Impairments - this has been exploited into the project, allowing not only to specify many features of the BM with elements consistent with DECI, but also to remove others that are not coherent or applicable.

Specifically, thanks to the evidences emerged from the Business Model Environment (which organizes and describes the key contextual variables useful to synthetically

characterize each Country involved in DECI) and the Coherence Matrix (which is mainly focused on functionalities, and it's a tool supporting the detection of the functionalities that are not coherent with the needs of the clusters of users that should be addressed), 4 BM Canvases (BMCs) specific for the different Pilot scenarios of implementation are provided together with further insights on the mechanisms adopted to deliver digital services, actors involved, coordination mechanisms, technologies in use, partnership and resources.

In line with T.2.2, the analysis exploits the 9 building blocks described by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010) and is characterized by the adoption of two lenses¹: the first one considers the viewpoint of the end-user of the solution, while the second one takes into accounts all the actors that are in charge of realizing, managing and delivering the service or part of it.

¹ To deepen the Business Model Canvas framework and know more about the 9 building blocks, their definition and categorization, and all the relative literature's findings and results from the Co-Creation Workshop, see Deliverable 2.2 "*Business model of the digital solutions used for assisting elderly people with cognitive impairments*".

2.2.1 BMC for Italy

In this Chapter are tabled the 9 building blocks that describes the comprehensive BM for Italy.

Customer Segments

Table 8 - BM Italy, Customer Segments

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare specialists/providers -> i.e. the care service providers, the Local Health Authorities and the Municipalities • Healthcare structures/facilities -> e.g. 2,1 Hospitals per 100.000 population; 44,5 Psychiatric beds per million population 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 27% of the population is over-60: one of the highest in EU • Patients with dementia (MD) and MCI -> one of the highest estimated prevalence of dementia per 1000 population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2015: 21,8 ○ 2035: 31,4 Relevant needs / Action to address the need: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Overall medical condition ○ Behavior and mood ○ Assess the Risk of malnutrition ○ ADL ○ Risk for falls ○ Cognitive stimulation ○ Online Cognitive Training ○ Coordination of care ○ Clinical team information sharing ○ Improve diagnosis method

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Advising on deciding course of action ○ Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies ○ Standardized care pathway ○ Monitoring overall condition ○ Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment ○ Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support ○ Frailty ○ Assess Caregiver burden ○ Assuring maintenance of living space ○ Malnutrition avoidance ○ Money budgeting ○ Medication plan ○ Medication Reminders ○ Fall detection ○ Immobility detection ○ Education and follow-up ○ Health team information sharing (including social care) ○ To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources ○ To facilitate and to speed up access to social services (Day Centres, Night Centres, etc.) ○ Interventions with the caregiver ○ Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease ○ The caregiver can ask questions to the health professional
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Information about available social services in the area • Caregiver -> extremely high tendency to Informal Care: 68% of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability. The caregiver has a central role and is highly involved.
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Value Proposition

Table 9 - BM Italy, Value Proposition

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's blood pressure for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Monitoring overall medical condition and frailty ○ Indirect measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment ○ Monitoring risk for falls • Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's O₂ saturation for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Monitoring overall medical condition and frailty ○ Indirect measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment ○ Monitoring risk for falls • Automatic provision and submitting of questionnaires (of various nature, including patient's health status and to support change detection) to care-involved subjects for 	

- Monitoring overall condition
- Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease
- Behavior and mood
- ADL
- Assess Caregiver burden
- Gathering on non-structured information on patient's health status from informal caregivers or social caretakers for
 - Behavior and mood
 - ADL
 - Monitoring overall medical condition and frailty
- Evaluation and monitoring of cognitive skills and monitoring of decay curves and other trends for
 - Behavior and mood
 - Advising on deciding course of action
- Automatic provision of feedbacks and alerts on patients' progresses or deterioration for:
 - Improve diagnosis method
 - Monitoring overall condition
 - Monitoring Frailty
- Cognitive games/exercises to stimulate patients to preserve cognitive/executive functions for
 - Cognitive stimulation
 - Online cognitive training
- Tele-consultation (tele-presence) functionalities allowing patients and professionals to communicate to each other visually for
 - Online cognitive training
- Automatic provision of remote real-time feedback on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for
 - ADL
 - Coordination of care
 - Monitoring overall condition

- Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Automatic provision of remote real-time patient-tailored motivational messages based on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for
 - Cognitive stimulation
 - Online Cognitive Training
 - Behavior and mood
- Automatic provision of remote feedback on patients' activities, building on long-time data analysis on patients' status for
 - Risk for falls
 - Improve diagnosis method
 - Advising on deciding course of action
 - Monitoring overall condition
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Activity monitoring through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station): stand / sit / walk / steps + intensity of activity for
 - Risk for falls
- GPS-based patient monitoring and structured health-based data gathering for outdoor step counting or activity monitoring (including detection of falls) for
 - Risk for falls
- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is monitored real-time by sensors when performing the activity) for
 - Assess the Risk of malnutrition
 - ADL
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
 - Monitoring overall condition
- Sharing of information on patient's monitoring activities among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these) for
 - Clinical team information sharing

- Storage of information on patient's monitoring activities for
 - Overall medical condition
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Displaying of care sheets and clinical data for
 - Overall medical condition
- Data storage from and sharing to external Electronic Medical Record (EMR) or other care management tools for
 - Overall medical condition
 - Coordination of care
 - Monitoring overall condition
- Management of a structured fall events record for
 - Risk for falls
- Immobility detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor) for
 - Immobility detection
- Fall detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor) for
 - Fall detection
- Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities for
 - Frailty
 - Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease
 - Improve diagnosis method
 - Monitoring overall condition
- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is formally required to provide a yes/no answer) for
 - Monitoring overall condition
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
 - Assuring maintenance of living space
 - Education, follow-up

- Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity for
 - Assuring maintenance of living space
 - Malnutrition avoidance
 - Medication Reminders
- Availability of personalized and adaptable remote-based training programs automatically tailored on individual patient's characteristics for
 - Education, follow-up
- Drug management for
 - Medication plan

Channels

Table 10- BM Italy, Channels

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet -> high population IT readiness: 89% has internet access and use it at home every day • Pharmacies -> central role of the pharmacies, also considering the low percentage of population living in urban areas (69%) • Providers of digital solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver-> extremely high tendency to Informal Care: the 68% of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability. The caregiver has a central role and is highly involved • General practitioner (MMG) -> central role of the GPs, also considering the low percentage of population living in urban areas (69%) • Health care specialists • Healthcare structures/facilities -> i.e. the care service providers, the Local Health Authorities and the Municipalities. Indeed, Italy's

	<p>health-care system is a regionally organized National Health Service: the Regional Plans establish the integration between health and social care services in line with the Regional Health Plan goals, while the Local Plans define, design and implement interventions that compose the overall offer of socio-health care services provided by public or private subjects</p>
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Customer Relationships

Table 11- BM Italy, Customer Relationship

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance² (Service provider-Healthcare organization/specialist) • Co-creation³: feedback, ideas, suggestions and experiences from patient/caregiver/community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance (Caregiver-Patient) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support to the relationships: • Patient-Technology • Patient-Healthcare

² This relationship is based on human interaction. The customer can communicate with a real customer representative to get help during the sales process or after the purchase is complete. This may happen onsite at the point of sale, through call centers, by e-mail, or through other means.

³ More companies are going beyond the traditional customer-vendor relationship to co-create value with customers. Amazon.com invites customers to write reviews and thus create value for other book lovers. Some companies engage customers to assist with the design of new and innovative products. Others, such as YouTube.com, solicit customers to create content for public consumption.

Revenue Streams

Table 12- BM Italy, Revenue Streams

Overall System	Patient
<p>Marketplace</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business to Public sector (B2P) -> the National Socio-Healthcare System has a universal and solidarity nature, and the healthcare system is funded from general taxation. The main source of finance for the Italian SSN is a mix of taxes applied at both regional and national level • Business to Business (B2B): e.g. insurance funds <p>Relationship provider of digital solution – healthcare organization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare organization purchases the entire system (one-time capital investment) • Healthcare organization pays a license fee for each patient connected to the system 	<p>Business to Consumer (B2C): the service is sold directly to the patient or his caregiver. This includes those that directly fund their care and those that exploit personal budget related to local authorities (high Out-of-pocket expenditure - as a percentage of private expenditure on health: 82,8%)</p>

Key Resources

Table 13- BM Italy, Key Resources

Overall System	Patient

<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialist of digital technologies <p>Intellectual</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents, licenses and copyrights <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors • Apps • Smartphones/Tablets 	<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver/ Social workers of the Municipality • Healthcare professionals – i.e. nurses <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors • Apps • Smartphones/Tablets • Pill dispenser
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Key Activities

Table 14- BM Italy, Key Activities

Overall System	Patient
<p>Governmental activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional awareness campaigns -> e.g. not only at a Regional level (that establish the integration between health and social care services in line with the Regional Health Plan goals), but 	<p>Creation and sustainment of relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create the connection between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Engagement of the patient

<p>mostly local campaigns to the ASL (that has the role of manager, and in some cases even of regulator, of health care and social care services), to the Municipalities and to the Case Service Providers</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial incentives to healthcare organizations that offer quality of MCI and dementia care • Financial incentives to healthcare specialist for the diagnosis of MCI and dementia -> for an early detection, GPs should be involved • Financial incentives to healthcare specialists and healthcare organizations for the adoption of digital solutions to treat MCI and dementia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance of the relationship between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Maintenance of the relationship with the patient <p>Activities related to technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of the equipment and the sensors • Mapping of patient's activities • Selection of the most appropriate technology/sensor • Installation of the technologies in the patients' home • Calibration of the sensors • Personalization of the service to the specific characteristics of the patient, properly inserted within his daily activities
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Key Partners

Table 15- BM Italy, Key Partners

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Healthcare Council • Researchers centers/Universities -> e.g. Politecnico di Milano • Local regional community -> i.e. ASL; Municipality; Care Service Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary associations

Cost Structure

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

Table 16- BM Italy, Cost Structure

Overall System
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training costs of caregivers • Personnel costs • Purchasing costs (software and hardware) • Installation costs • Maintenance costs

2.2.2 BMC for Sweden

In this Chapter are tabled the 9 building blocks that describes the comprehensive BM for Sweden.

Customer Segments

Table 17 - BM Sweden, Customer Segments

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare specialists/providers -> i.e. Municipalities: their responsibilities include issues relating to the immediate environment of the citizens, for example social welfare services. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 26% of the population is over-60: one of the highest in EU • Patients with dementia (MD) and MCI -> one of the highest estimated prevalence of dementia per 1000 population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2015: 18,5 ○ 2035: 24,9

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare structures/facilities -> e.g. 0,8 Hospitals per 100.000 population; 45 Psychiatric beds per million population 	<p>Relevant needs / Action to address the need:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Overall medical condition ○ Behavior and mood ○ Assess the Risk of malnutrition ○ ADL ○ Risk for falls ○ Cognitive stimulation ○ Online Cognitive Training ○ Coordination of care ○ Clinical team information sharing ○ Improve diagnosis method ○ Advising on deciding course of action ○ Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies ○ Standardized care pathway ○ Monitoring overall condition ○ Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment ○ Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support ○ Reactive detection ○ Proactive search I (Database parameters) ○ Clinical diagnosis ○ Assess Socio economic state ○ The patient can contact a health professional for questioning
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Medication Reminders ○ Access to non-pharmacological treatment ○ Patients can contact the social worker ○ Facilitating access to medical services in rural/ isolated areas ○ Comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy+ follow-up ○ To improve social awareness about the disease ○ To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources ○ Online Cognitive Training ○ Monitoring of cognitive condition ○ Interventions with the caregiver ○ Caregiver-> low tendency to Informal Care: just 14% of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability • Caregiver -> low tendency to Informal Care: just 14% of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability
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Value Proposition

Table 18 - BM Sweden, Value Proposition

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's blood pressure for 	

- assess the risk of malnutrition
- Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's O₂ saturation for
 - assess the risk of malnutrition
 - improve diagnosis method
- Automatic provision and submitting of questionnaires (of various nature, including patient's health status and to support change detection) to care-involved subjects for
 - Behavior and mood
 - ADL
- Gathering on non-structured information on patient's health status from informal caregivers or social caretakers for
 - Behavior and mood
 - ADL
- Evaluation and monitoring of cognitive skills and monitoring of decay curves and other trends for
 - Behavior and mood
- Automatic provision of feedbacks and alerts on patients' progresses or deterioration for:
 - Improve diagnosis method
- Cognitive games/exercises to stimulate patients to preserve cognitive/executive functions for
 - Cognitive stimulation
 - Online cognitive training
- Tele-consultation (tele-presence) functionalities allowing patients and professionals to communicate to each other visually for
 - Online cognitive training
- Automatic provision of remote real-time feedback on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for
 - ADL
 - Coordination of care
- Automatic provision of remote real-time patient-tailored motivational messages based on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for

- Cognitive stimulation
- Online Cognitive Training
- Automatic provision of remote feedback on patients' activities, building on long-time data analysis on patients' status for
 - Risk for falls
 - Improve diagnosis method
 - Advising on deciding course of action
 - Monitoring overall condition
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Activity monitoring through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station): stand / sit / walk / steps + intensity of activity for
 - Risk for falls
- GPS-based patient monitoring and structured health-based data gathering for outdoor step counting or activity monitoring (including detection of falls) for
 - risk for falls
- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is monitored real-time by sensors when performing the activity) for
 - Assess the Risk of malnutrition
 - ADL
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Sharing of information on patient's monitoring activities among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these) for
 - Clinical team information sharing
- Storage of information on patient's monitoring activities for
 - Overall medical condition
- Displaying of care sheets and clinical data for
 - Overall medical condition

- Data storage from and sharing to external Electronic Medical Record (EMR) or other care management tools for
 - Overall medical condition
 - Coordination of care
 - Monitoring overall condition
- Management of a structured fall events record for
 - Risk for falls
- Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities for
 - Clinical diagnosis
- Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity for
 - Medication reminders

Channels

Table 19- BM Sweden, Channels

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet -> high population IT readiness: 93% has internet access and use it at home every day • Pharmacies • Providers of digital solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver-> low tendency to Informal Care: just 14% of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability • General practitioner -> GPs have a geographically broad responsibility and are connected to Health centers. • Health care specialists • Healthcare structures/facilities -> i.e. The Government and the Parliament have the overall political responsibility for healthcare, while 20 counties/regions and 290 municipalities

	bear the operational responsibility for citizens' care. The Health and Medical Services Act is designed to give county councils and municipalities considerable freedom with regard to the organization of their health services
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Customer Relationships

Table 20- BM Sweden, Customer Relationship

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance (Service provider-Healthcare organization/specialist) • Co-creation: feedback, ideas, suggestions and experiences from patient/caregiver/community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance (Caregiver-Patient) • Support to the relationships: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient-Technology • Patient-Healthcare

Revenue Streams

Table 21- BM Sweden, Revenue Streams

Overall System	Patient
Marketplace <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business to Public sector (B2P) -> According to the Health and Medical Services Act, the Swedish system provides coverage for all residents of Sweden, regardless of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business to Consumer (B2C): the service is sold directly to the patient or his caregiver. This includes those that directly fund their care and those that exploit personal budget related to local authorities (high Out-of-pocket expenditure - as a percentage of private expenditure on health: 88,1%)

nationality. The regions and municipalities have a mandate to tax the population through employee and employer salary-based taxes. Both the county councils and the municipalities levy proportional income taxes on the population to cover the services that they provide. It is up to each county council to decide on the mechanisms for paying providers and therefore methods vary across the country. In hospital care, a mix of payment mechanisms is used across the country. Often, fixed prospective per-case payments (based on DRGs), complemented with price or volume ceilings and quality components are used. The use of DRGs and other classification systems for payment varies among regions and county councils.

- **Business to Business (B2B): e.g. insurance funds** -> There are few private hospitals, and the number of private primary care providers varies widely between the county councils. In some urban county councils, up to 60% of the primary care providers may be private, whereas in other county councils only a few private providers can be found. The same variation in the public/private mix of providers can be found across the municipalities.

Relationship provider of digital solution – healthcare organization

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare organization purchases the entire system (one-time capital investment) • Healthcare organization pays a license fee for each patient connected to the system 	
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Key Resources

Table 22- BM Sweden, Key Resources

Overall System	Patient
<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialist of digital technologies <p>Intellectual</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents, licenses and copyrights <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software • Sensors • Apps • Smartphones/Tablets 	<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver/ Social workers of the provinces and municipalities • Healthcare professionals – i.e. nurses <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software • Sensors • Apps • Smartphones/Tablets • Pill dispenser

Key Activities

Table 23- BM Sweden, Key Activities

Overall System	Patient
<p>Governmental activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional awareness campaigns -> e.g. at a Municipal level: the responsibility for means testing, and the financing and organization of long-term care services for older people and providing support to people with disabilities lies with the municipalities • Financial incentives to healthcare organizations that offer quality of MCI and dementia care -> At the local government level, several county councils initiated reform projects focusing on the development of community services, that is, locally organized and provided services that should respond to the needs for common preventive and curative services for the population. The idea of community services developed in different directions across county councils: in some county councils, the reforms focused on a new role for smaller hospitals. In other county councils, the reforms focused more on the need to develop primary care in order to improve the care for older people and for patients with chronic diseases. 	<p>Creation and sustainment of relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create the connection between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Engagement of the patient • Maintenance of the relationship between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Maintenance of the relationship with the patient <p>Activities related to technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of the equipment and the sensors • Mapping of patient's activities • Selection of the most appropriate technology/sensor • Installation of the technologies in the patients' home • Calibration of the sensors • Personalization of the service to the specific characteristics of the patient, properly inserted within his daily activities

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial incentives to healthcare specialist for the diagnosis of MCI and dementia -> for an early detection, GPs should be involved • Financial incentives to healthcare specialists and healthcare organizations for the adoption of digital solutions to treat MCI and dementia 	
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Key Partners

Table 24- BM Sweden, Key Partners

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments -> There are eight government agencies directly involved in the area of health, medical care and public health: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The National Board of Health and Welfare is a large government agency, engaged in a wide range of activities in the areas of social services, health care services, environmental health, communicable disease prevention and epidemiology ○ The HSAN is a government agency that decides on disciplinary measures in the event of complaints or possible malpractice ○ The primary objective of the SBU is to promote the use of cost-effective health care technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary associations

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The MPA is the Swedish national authority responsible for the regulation and surveillance of the development, manufacture and sale of drugs and other medicinal products ○ The TLV works has the primary task of deciding if a medicine or medicinal product should be subsidized and included in the pharmaceutical benefits scheme ○ The Swedish Agency for Health and Care Services Analysis analyze and evaluate implemented measures and the availability of information within the sphere of health and care service policy from the perspective of citizens and patients ○ National Institute for Public Health promote health and prevent diseases by providing the government, government agencies, municipalities and county councils with knowledge based on scientific evidence ○ Swedish Social Insurance Agency is the authority that administers the various types of insurance and benefits that make up social insurance in Sweden • Regional Healthcare Council • Researchers centers/Universities • Local regional community -> the Local Authorities (county councils and municipalities) 	
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Cost Structure

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

Table 25- BM Sweden, Cost Structure

Overall System
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training costs of caregivers • Personnel costs • Purchasing costs (software and hardware) • Installation costs • Maintenance costs

2.2.3 BMC for Spain

In this Chapter are tabled the 9 building blocks that describes the comprehensive BM for Sweden.

Customer Segments

Table 26 - BM Spain, Customer Segments

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare specialists/providers -> i.e. the Local Authorities (provinces and municipalities) that collaborate in health services provision and direct management of residual public health and community services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 23% of the population is over-60: one of the highest in EU • Patients with dementia (MD) and MCI -> one of the highest estimated prevalence of dementia per 1000 population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2015: 18,5 ○ 2035: 28,0

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare structures/facilities -> e.g. 1,6 Hospitals per 100.000 population; 38,7 Psychiatric beds per million population 	<p>Relevant needs / Action to address the need:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Overall medical condition ○ Behavior and mood ○ Assess the Risk of malnutrition ○ ADL ○ Risk for falls ○ Cognitive stimulation ○ Online Cognitive Training ○ Coordination of care ○ Clinical team information sharing ○ Improve diagnosis method ○ Advising on deciding course of action ○ Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies ○ Standardized care pathway ○ Monitoring overall condition ○ Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment ○ Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support ○ Clinical diagnosis ○ Frailty ○ Assess Socio economic state ○ Assess Caregiver burden ○ Information about the disease, symptoms and evolution
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Information on current condition and treatment ○ Physical activity plan and exercise ○ Access to non-pharmacological treatment ○ Remote monitoring of psychological status ○ comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy+ follow-up ○ To improve social awareness about the disease ○ To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources ○ Online Cognitive Training ○ Monitoring of cognitive condition ○ Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease • Caregiver-> quite high tendency to Informal Care: 38% of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability
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Value Proposition

Table 27 - BM Spain, Value Proposition

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic remote-based measurement of patient’s blood pressure for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ assess the risk of malnutrition • Automatic remote-based measurement of patient’s O₂ saturation for 	

- assess the risk of malnutrition
 - improve diagnosis method
- Automatic provision and submitting of questionnaires (of various nature, including patient's health status and to support change detection) to care-involved subjects for
 - Behavior and mood
 - ADL
- Gathering on non-structured information on patient's health status from informal caregivers or social caretakers for
 - Behavior and mood
 - ADL
- Evaluation and monitoring of cognitive skills and monitoring of decay curves and other trends for
 - Behavior and mood
- Automatic provision of feedbacks and alerts on patients' progresses or deterioration for:
 - Improve diagnosis method
- Cognitive games/exercises to stimulate patients to preserve cognitive/executive functions for
 - Cognitive stimulation
 - Online cognitive training
- Tele-consultation (tele-presence) functionalities allowing patients and professionals to communicate to each other visually for
 - Online cognitive training
- Automatic provision of remote real-time feedback on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for
 - ADL
 - Coordination of care
- Automatic provision of remote real-time patient-tailored motivational messages based on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for
 - Cognitive stimulation
 - Online Cognitive Training

- Automatic provision of remote feedback on patients' activities, building on long-time data analysis on patients' status for
 - Risk for falls
 - Improve diagnosis method
 - Advising on deciding course of action
 - Monitoring overall condition
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Activity monitoring through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station): stand / sit / walk / steps + intensity of activity for
 - Risk for falls
- GPS-based patient monitoring and structured health-based data gathering for outdoor step counting or activity monitoring (including detection of falls) for
 - risk for falls
- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is monitored real-time by sensors when performing the activity) for
 - Assess the Risk of malnutrition
 - ADL
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Sharing of information on patient's monitoring activities among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these) for
 - Clinical team information sharing
- Storage of information on patient's monitoring activities for
 - Overall medical condition
- Displaying of care sheets and clinical data for
 - Overall medical condition
- Data storage from and sharing to external Electronic Medical Record (EMR) or other care management tools for
 - Overall medical condition

- Coordination of care
- Monitoring overall condition
- Management of a structured fall events record for
 - Risk for falls
- Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities for
 - Clinical diagnosis
 - Frailty
 - Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease
- Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity for
 - Physical activity plan and exercise
- Availability of personalized and adaptable remote-based training programs automatically tailored on individual patient's characteristics for
 - Physical activity plan and exercise

Channels

Table 28- BM Spain, Channels

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet -> high population IT readiness: 92% has internet access and use it at home every day • Pharmacies -> central role of the pharmacies, also considering the low percentage of population living in urban areas (79%) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver-> quite high tendency to Informal Care: the 38 % of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability. • General practitioner -> central role of the GPs, also considering the low percentage of population living in urban areas (79%).

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers of digital solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health care specialists • Healthcare structures/facilities -> i.e. the Local Health Authorities (provinces and Municipalities) that collaborate in health services provision and direct management of residual public health and community services. Indeed, the National Ministry of Health is the Government body responsible for the planning the national health policy, providing each one of the 17 Autonomous Communities (AC) with general resources according to their population, area and special conditions. ACs can freely allocate those funds among their Ministries. This freedom brings out heterogeneity in health expenditure per capita and access to different baskets of services, as each AC can give more or less importance and support to health issues
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Customer Relationships

Table 29- BM Spain, Customer Relationship

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance (Service provider-Healthcare organization/specialist) • Co-creation: feedback, ideas, suggestions and experiences from patient/caregiver/community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance (Caregiver-Patient) <p>Support to the relationships:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient-Technology • Patient-Healthcare

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

Revenue Streams

Table 30- BM Spain, Revenue Streams

Overall System	Patient
<p>Marketplace</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business to Public sector (B2P) -> The Spanish National Health System (SNHS) provides Spanish citizens with universal coverage. The system is fully funded from taxes and predominantly within the public sector: healthcare provision is free of charge at the point of delivery. Hospitals are normally funded through a global budget, set against individual spending headings: the trend has evolved to a DRG-like system. Private Voluntary Insurance (PVI) plays a minor function in the Spanish healthcare system, and it is mostly used for specific specialties such as Dental Surgery, to speed up waiting lists or for complementary care. The Spanish can freely purchase health care services from private health insurers that contract private health providers (e.g. Quirón, Ruber, etc.) or independent specialists. <p>Relationship provider of digital solution – healthcare organization</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business to Consumer (B2C): the service is sold directly to the patient or his caregiver. This includes those that directly fund their care and those that exploit personal budget related to local authorities (high Out-of-pocket expenditure - as a percentage of private expenditure on health: 77,1%)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare organization purchases the entire system (one-time capital investment) • Healthcare organization pays a license fee for each patient connected to the system 	
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Key Resources

Table 31- BM Spain, Key Resources

Overall System	Patient
<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialist of digital technologies <p>Intellectual</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents, licenses and copyrights <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors • Apps • Smartphones/Tablets 	<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver/ Social workers of the provinces and municipalities • Healthcare professionals – i.e. nurses <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors • Apps • Smartphones/Tablets • Pill dispenser

Key Activities

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

Table 32- BM Spain, Key Activities

Overall System	Patient
<p>Governmental activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional awareness campaigns -> e.g. at a Autonomous Communities level, because of have not only the role of legislation, but also of management and provision health services. • Financial incentives to healthcare organizations that offer quality of MCI and dementia care • Financial incentives to healthcare specialist for the diagnosis of MCI and dementia -> for an early detection, GPs should be involved • Financial incentives to healthcare specialists and healthcare organizations for the adoption of digital solutions to treat MCI and dementia 	<p>Creation and sustainment of relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create the connection between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Engagement of the patient • Maintenance of the relationship between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Maintenance of the relationship with the patient <p>Activities related to technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of the equipment and the sensors • Mapping of patient's activities • Selection of the most appropriate technology/sensor • Installation of the technologies in the patients' home • Calibration of the sensors • Personalization of the service to the specific characteristics of the patient, properly inserted within his daily activities

Key Partners

Table 33- BM Spain, Key Partners

Overall System	Patient

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional Healthcare Council • Researchers centers/Universities • Local regional community -> the Local Authorities (provinces and municipalities) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary associations
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Cost Structure

Table 34- BM Spain, Cost Structure

Overall System
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training costs of caregivers • Personnel costs • Purchasing costs (software and hardware) • Installation costs • Maintenance costs

2.2.4 BMC for Israel

In this Chapter are tabled the 9 building blocks that describes the comprehensive BM for Sweden.

Customer Segments

Table 35 - BM Israel, Customer Segments

Overall System	Patient
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare specialists/providers -> i.e. four competing, non-profit-making health funds called “Health Maintenance Organisations” (HMOs): Clalit, Maccabi Healthcare Services, Kupat Holim Meuhedet and Leumit • Healthcare structures/facilities -> e.g. 0,6 Hospitals per 100.000 population; 43,8 Psychiatric beds per million population 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15% of the population is over-60 • Patients with dementia (MD) and MCI -> quite high prevalence of dementia per 1000 population: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ 2015: 10,4 ◦ 2035: 25,1 <p>Relevant needs / Action to address the need: Clinical diagnosis</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Overall medical condition ◦ Behavior and mood ◦ Assess the Risk of malnutrition ◦ ADL ◦ Risk for falls ◦ Cognitive stimulation ◦ Online Cognitive Training ◦ Coordination of care ◦ Clinical team information sharing ◦ Improve diagnosis method ◦ Advising on deciding course of action ◦ Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies ◦ Standardized care pathway ◦ Monitoring overall condition ◦ Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support ○ Frailty ○ Assess Socio economic state ○ Assess Caregiver burden ○ comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy + follow-up ○ Online Cognitive Training ○ Monitoring of cognitive condition <p>Or</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver
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Value Proposition

Table 36 - BM Israel, Value Proposition

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic remote-based measurement of patient’s blood pressure for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ assess the risk of malnutrition • Automatic remote-based measurement of patient’s O₂ saturation for <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ assess the risk of malnutrition ○ improve diagnosis method 	

- Automatic provision and submitting of questionnaires (of various nature, including patient's health status and to support change detection) to care-involved subjects for
 - Behavior and mood
 - ADL
- Gathering on non-structured information on patient's health status from informal caregivers or social caretakers for
 - Behavior and mood
 - ADL
- Evaluation and monitoring of cognitive skills and monitoring of decay curves and other trends for
 - Behavior and mood
- Automatic provision of feedbacks and alerts on patients' progresses or deterioration for:
 - Improve diagnosis method
- Cognitive games/exercises to stimulate patients to preserve cognitive/executive functions for
 - Cognitive stimulation
 - Online cognitive training
- Tele-consultation (tele-presence) functionalities allowing patients and professionals to communicate to each other visually for
 - Online cognitive training
- Automatic provision of remote real-time feedback on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for
 - ADL
 - Coordination of care
- Automatic provision of remote real-time patient-tailored motivational messages based on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities for
 - Cognitive stimulation
 - Online Cognitive Training
- Automatic provision of remote feedback on patients' activities, building on long-time data analysis on patients' status for
 - Risk for falls

- Improve diagnosis method
- Advising on deciding course of action
- Monitoring overall condition
- Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Activity monitoring through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station): stand / sit / walk / steps + intensity of activity for
 - Risk for falls
- GPS-based patient monitoring and structured health-based data gathering for outdoor step counting or activity monitoring (including detection of falls) for
 - risk for falls
- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is monitored real-time by sensors when performing the activity) for
 - Assess the Risk of malnutrition
 - ADL
 - Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment
- Sharing of information on patient's monitoring activities among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these) for
 - Clinical team information sharing
- Storage of information on patient's monitoring activities for
 - Overall medical condition
- Displaying of care sheets and clinical data for
 - Overall medical condition
- Data storage from and sharing to external Electronic Medical Record (EMR) or other care management tools for
 - Overall medical condition
 - Coordination of care
 - Monitoring overall condition

- Management of a structured fall events record for
 - Risk for falls
- Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities for
 - Clinical diagnosis
 - Frailty

Channels

Table 37- BM Israel, Channels

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internet • Pharmacies • Providers of digital solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver • General practitioner • Health care specialists • Healthcare structures/facilities -> i.e. four competing, non-profit-making health funds called "Health Maintenance OrganisationsOrganizations" (HMOs): Clalit, Maccabi Healthcare Services, Kupat Holim Meuhedet and Leumit. The HMOs are health insurance funds recognized by the Israeli National Health Insurance Law, and are obligated to a uniform basic basket of health services. They are allowed to offer supplemental health and care services beyond the basket, for an additional premium

Customer Relationships

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

Table 38- BM Israel, Customer Relationship

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance (Service provider-Healthcare organization/specialist) • Co-creation: feedback, ideas, suggestions and experiences from patient/caregiver/community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal assistance (Caregiver-Patient) Support to the relationships: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient-Technology • Patient-Healthcare

Revenue Streams

Table 39- BM Israel, Revenue Streams

Overall System	Patient
Marketplace <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is free choice among four competing, non-profit-making health plans that receive NHI funds from the Government according to a capitation formula. • Business to Business (B2B): e.g. insurance funds -> The system is financed primarily from public sources via payroll and general tax revenues. However, 75% of the population purchases complementary health insurance from one of the four health insurance funds that covers services outside the basic package. Approximately 80% of hospital revenue comes from sales of services to health plans; the reimbursement of public hospitals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business to Consumer (B2C): the service is sold directly to the patient or his caregiver. This includes those that directly fund their care and those that exploit personal budget related to local authorities (Out-of-pocket expenditure - as a percentage of private expenditure on health: 64,5%)

<p>in Israel takes place in the form of fee-for-service payments, per diem fees and case payments</p> <p>Relationship provider of digital solution – healthcare organization</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Healthcare organization purchases the entire system (one-time capital investment) • Healthcare organization pays a license fee for each patient connected to the system 	
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Key Resources

Table 40- BM Israel, Key Resources

Overall System	Patient
<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Specialist of digital technologies <p>Intellectual</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patents, licenses and copyrights <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors 	<p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caregiver/ Social workers • Healthcare professionals <p>Physical</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Warehouse • Distribution network • Communication network • Hardware and software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors • Apps

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apps • Smartphones/Tablets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smartphones/Tablets • Pill dispenser
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Key Activities

Table 41- BM Israel, Key Activities

Overall System	Patient
<p>Governmental activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National/regional awareness campaigns -> The Ministry of Health has overall responsibility for the health of the population and the effective functioning of the health care system. It plans and determines health priorities, drafts health care laws to be discussed with the Knesset, provides adequate resources for NHI system, monitor and promote population health, etc. • Financial incentives to healthcare organizations that offer quality of MCI and dementia care -> The vast majority of elderly people live or are cared for at home, with only 4.5% residing in any kind of institutional setting (with less than 3% in a nursing home). This is due to the extensive care provided by families and the development of formal services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Day care centers: in addition to some 900 social clubs that provide a framework for activities and facilitate interpersonal contact and socialization for the elderly population that are in good health, a network of (at least 	<p>Creation and sustainment of relationships</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create the connection between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Engagement of the patient • Maintenance of the relationship between healthcare specialist and caregiver/social worker • Maintenance of the relationship with the patient <p>Activities related to technology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production of the equipment and the sensors • Mapping of patient's activities • Selection of the most appropriate technology/sensor • Installation of the technologies in the patients' home • Calibration of the sensors <p>Personalization of the service to the specific characteristics of the patient, properly inserted within his daily activities</p>

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

180) day care centers for the disabled elderly has been developed. Most centers are stand-alone organizations although some are affiliated with other institutions (sheltered housing, old-age homes and so on). Another significant development within the day care center network has been the establishment of special programs for the cognitively impaired, including elderly people with Alzheimer's disease and other types of dementia

- Institutional long-term care: Patients are categorized according to (one of) five levels of dependency with the institutions, and regulated by two ministries: the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Social Affairs. Those families that are able to purchase care from a licensed long-term institution (whether profit-making or non-profit-making) are expected to do so. However, given the high cost of such care, more than two-thirds of families turn to the Ministry of Health for a subsidy
- Supportive neighborhoods: One of the most important and innovative developments in community care in recent years has been the supportive neighborhood program, designed to emphasize the neighborhood as a force that provides the elderly with a sense of security and access to services. Elderly people who live in supportive neighborhoods in cities, towns or rural areas enjoy a "basket" of services that includes: a neighborhood

<p>facilitator who ensures their personal safety, as well as the safety and security of their homes, and also provides home repairs; an emergency call button; a physician/ambulance on call 24 hours a day; social activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial incentives to healthcare specialist for the diagnosis of MCI and dementia -> for an early detection, GPs should be involved • Financial incentives to healthcare specialists and healthcare organizations for the adoption of digital solutions to treat MCI and dementia 	
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Key Partners

Table 42- BM Israel, Key Partners

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Governments -> The Knesset ultimately determines laws and budgets • Regional Healthcare Council -> there are Public Health Divisions that operate through regional and local offices: their aim is to ensure the implementation of those policies and strategies developed at national level • Researchers centers/Universities • Local regional community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voluntary associations -> Health plans are voluntary, non-profit-making organizations, obliged to ensure that their members have access to a benefits package, as specified in the NHI Law. In return, the health plans receive an annual capitation fee per member from the Government

- | | |
|--|--|
| • Private organizations -> HMOs | |
|--|--|

Cost Structure

Table 43- BM Israel, Cost Structure

Overall System
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training costs of caregivers • Personnel costs • Purchasing costs (software and hardware) • Installation costs • Maintenance costs

2.3 DECI Service Model

The Value Proposition is the core block of the BMC framework, in which is described the reason why a customer should choose a products or a service.

To deepen the Value Proposition and reduce the complexity to be tackled in the design of the overall DECI business model, packages of service model common to all the 4 countries are highlighted in Chapter 2.3.1, crossing the most relevant cluster of needs with the relative cluster of functionalities. Then, this general value proposition is enriched with further packages of country-specific service model.

2.3.1 General Service Model

In order to design a general service model able to encase a value proposition common to all the 4 countries involved in DECI, the needs marked as extremely relevant (Maccabi index score = 5/5) has been highlighted and clustered following T1.3 activities, as follows:

N1. Diagnosis and assessment:

- Overall medical condition;
- Behavior and mood;
- Assess the Risk of malnutrition;
- Activities of Daily Living (ADL);
- Risk for falls.

N2. Patient psychological needs:

- Cognitive stimulation;
- Online Cognitive Training.

N3. Clinical team needs:

- Coordination of care;
- Clinical team information sharing;
- Improve diagnosis method;
- Advising on deciding course of action;
- Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies;
- Standardized care pathway.

N4. Follow-up:

- Monitoring overall condition;
- Measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment;
- Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support.

Starting from these clusters, it is possible to develop some clusters for the technological functionalities common to all countries and that allow meeting these needs. Regarding the patient layer, the following 5 clusters have been identified:

TFP1. Patient's status (Monitoring):

- Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's blood pressure;
- Automatic remote-based measurement of patient's O₂ saturation;
- Automatic provision and submitting of questionnaires (of various nature, including patient's health status and to support change detection) to care-involved subjects;
- Gathering on non-structured information on patient's health status from informal caregivers or social caretakers;
- Evaluation and monitoring of cognitive skills and monitoring of decay curves and other trends.

TFP2. Patient's status (Alert): automatic provision of feedbacks and alerts on patients' progresses or deterioration

TFP3. Patient's status (Communication-Cognitive stimulation):

- Cognitive games/exercises to stimulate patients to preserve cognitive/executive functions;
- Tele-consultation (tele-presence) functionalities allowing patients and professionals to communicate to each other visually.

TFP4. Patient's Activities (Alert):

- Automatic provision of remote real-time feedback on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities;
- Automatic provision of remote real-time patient-tailored motivational messages based on patients' activities, including non-pre-scheduled activities.
- Automatic provision of remote feedback on patients' activities, building on long-time data analysis on patients' status.

TFP5. Patient's Activities (Monitoring):

- Activity monitoring through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station): stand / sit / walk / steps + intensity of activity;
- GPS-based patient monitoring and structured health-based data gathering for outdoor step counting or activity monitoring (including detection of falls);
- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is monitored real-time by sensors when performing the activity).

TFP6. Patient's status (Storage and sharing information):

- Activity monitoring through accelerometer for elderly monitoring (also outdoor, with batch data download once reconnected to base station): stand / sit / walk / steps + intensity of activity;
- GPS-based patient monitoring and structured health-based data gathering for outdoor step counting or activity monitoring (including detection of falls);

- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is monitored real-time by sensors when performing the activity).

Regarding the overall system layer, the following 4 clusters have been identified:

TFS1. Care providers (Communication): informal communication (messaging) among various actors (e.g.: family members and doctors);

TFS2. Care providers (Teamwork): enablement of multidisciplinary teamwork across care providers, doctors and informal caregivers (or some of these);

TFS3. Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring): coherence check between clinical guidelines / protocols and data gathered as part of care activities;

TFS4. Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information): sharing of a treatment plan among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these).

Combining the clusters of common relevant needs with the clusters of common relevant functionalities, it is possible to point out the match between the two as number of notable crossings, in order to highlight packages of service model common to all 4 countries (Figure 6).

Patient layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up
Patient's status (Monitoring)	7	1		
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation)			3	
Patient's status (Alert)		1		
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)	4	2		2
Patient's activities (Alert)	2	3	2	2
Patient's activities (Monitoring)	4			1

Overall system layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up
Care providers (Communication)	1			
Care providers (teamwork)		2		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)		1		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)		2		

- High match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between needs & functionalities

Figure 6 - General service model

As shown in **Figure 6**, the various clusters of functionalities can have a different impact on the clusters of common relevant needs: the green cells reveals a high match between the two, highlighting the main cluster of need on which a cluster of functionality impacts. The blank cells mean that there are no notable crossings between needs and functionalities: for example, is useless try to cover the psychological needs of the patient with technologies that are born to storage and share information related to the status of the patients.

On the other side, the functionalities regarding the monitoring of patient's status have an impact mostly on the needs related to the diagnosis and assessment, as the ones concerning the communication between care providers. Furthermore, is important to underline as some clusters of functionalities are able to meet more clusters of needs, and are the ones on which to focus first in the definition of the pilots.

At the same time, there are some clusters of needs that are covered by less functionalities than others: these are the needs that are more difficult to meet and that, even more so, it's important to monitor.

At least, crossing the most relevant cluster of needs with the relative cluster of functionalities, it is possible to define a value proposition common to all the 4 countries, tabled in Table 44.

Table 44 – Common value proposition

Overall System	Patient
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Care providers (Communication) for Diagnosis and assessment • Care providers (teamwork) for Clinical team needs • Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring) for Clinical team needs • Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information) for Clinical team needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient's status (Monitoring) mostly for Diagnosis and assessment • Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation) mostly for Patient psychological needs • Patient's status (Alert) for Clinical team needs • Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) mostly for Diagnosis and assessment • Patient's activities (Alert) mostly for Clinical team needs • Patient's activities (Monitoring) mostly for Diagnosis and assessment

Each of the nine building block of the framework can inspire the design of the Business Model. However, as a starting point, it is useful focusing on the blocks that can have a greater impact on the others. From this viewpoint, Osterwalder et al. (2014) suggest focusing on “Customer Segment” and “Value Proposition” blocks. According to the authors, these two blocks have to fit well one another, and have a significant impact on all the other blocks of the BM canvas.

As described in **Figure 7** the 4 country-specific service model presented in the next paragraphs will deepen these two key blocks, and will describes how they affects the upstream building blocks (Key partners, Key activities and Key resources), the downstream building blocks (Customer Relationships, Customer Segments and Channels), and cost and revenues (Cost Structure and Revenue Streams).

Figure 7 – From the general service model to the country specific service model

2.3.2 Italy Service Model

In Chapter 2.3.1 a value proposition common to all the 4 countries involved in DECI has been analyzed. However, this general service model must be enriched with further specificities related to the Italian Customer Segments (and consequently Value Proposition).

Specifically, the Italian customer profile is enriched with further needs (and required actions to address the various needs) identified as extremely relevant by the Italian clinicians: the union between these needs and the ones common to all the DECI countries, shapes the complete Italian Customer Segments building block. Starting from this, also the common Value Proposition described in the previous Chapter is completed, with features specific for Italy.

Fitting the Italian specific needs with the functionalities that can meet these needs, further specific service model elements for Italy are available:

- Immobility detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor) for patient physical needs {*Immobility detection*}
- Fall detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor) for patient physical needs {*Fall detection*}
- Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities for diagnosis and assessment {*Frailty*} & for caregivers needs {*Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease*}
- Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is formally required to provide a yes/no answer) for patient environmental needs {*Assuring maintenance of living space*} & for patient physical needs {*Education, follow-up*}

- Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity for patient environmental needs {*Assuring maintenance of living space & Malnutrition avoidance*} & for patient physical needs {*Medication Reminders*}
- Availability of personalized and adaptable remote-based training programs automatically tailored on individual patient's characteristics for patient physical needs {*Education, follow-up*}
- Drug management for patient physical needs {*Medication plan*}

The functionalities clusters are enriched, for the Italian case, as follow:

- Patient's status (Monitoring)
 - Immobility detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor)
 - Fall detection for elderly monitoring at home (indoor)
- Patient's activities (Monitoring)
 - Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities
 - Registering of pre-scheduled activities performed by the patient (patient is formally required to provide a yes/no answer)
- Patient's Activities (Alert)
 - Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity
 - Availability of personalized and adaptable remote-based training programs automatically tailored on individual patient's characteristics
- Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring): Drug management

These packages goes to complete the general service model, shaping the Italian specific one.

Patient layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up	Caregivers needs	Patient environmental needs	Patient physical needs
Patient's status (Monitoring)	7	1	2				
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation)			3				
Patient's status (Alert)		1					
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)	4	2		2			
Patient's activities (Alert)	2	3	2	2		1	2
Patient's activities (Monitoring)	5			1	1	1	1

Overall system layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up	Patient physical needs
Care providers (Communication)	1				
Care providers (teamwork)		2			
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)		1			1
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)		2			

- High match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between needs & functionalities

Country specificities

Patient layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up	Caregivers needs	Patient environmental needs	Patient physical needs
Patient's status (Monitoring)	7	1	2				
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation)			3				
Patient's status (Alert)		1					
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)	4	2		2			
Patient's activities (Alert)	2	3	2	2		1	2
Patient's activities (Monitoring)	5			1	1	1	1

Overall system layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up	Patient physical needs
Care providers (Communication)	1				
Care providers (teamwork)		2			
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)		1			1
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)		2			

- High match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between needs & functionalities

Country specificities

Figure 8 - Italian value proposition

As shown in Figure 8, Italian clinicians underline the importance of other needs in addition to those common to all the countries: particularly the patient physical needs, the caregivers needs and the ones regarding patient environment. Furthermore, the Italian clinicians considers the diagnosis & assessment and the patient psychological needs more important than what the clinicians of the other countries do, in particular to monitor the patient's status and activities.

At the same time, the functionalities that can cover a greater number of needs are the ones that can monitor and make alert on patient's activities.

Table 45 presents the main impacts on the other building blocks.

Table 45 – How the Italian Service Model affect the BMC building blocks

Upstream building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Italian clinicians consider crucial the diagnosis and assessment: about that, for an early detection GPs should be involved because of their central role in the system • To meet the clinical team needs, it is important to provide the technological functionalities to the Local Health Authorities (that has the role of manager, and in some cases even of regulator, of health care and social care services), to the Municipalities and to the Case Service Providers • The monitoring of the patient’s status and activities meet all the 7 clusters of needs: this mean that the selection of the most appropriate technologies, the production and installation of this equipment and sensors are crucial key activities that can satisfy a large part of the most relevant needs expressed • To provide automatic reminders to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity is important to personalize the service to the specific characteristics of the patient, properly inserted within his daily activities • From an overall system viewpoint, is crucial to enable multidisciplinary teamwork across Local Health Authorities, Municipalities, Case service Providers, informal caregivers and voluntary associations
Downstream building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further clusters of needs have been identified as relevant from the Italian clinicians: the patient physical needs, the caregivers needs and the ones regarding the patient environmental • The caregiver has a central role, is highly involved, and must be engaged and informed about the evolution of symptoms and of the disease • A personal assistance based on human interaction should be preferred also to meet the patient psychological needs
Cost and revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue Streams should be a B2P and B2C mix: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ B2P: some functionalities, for example the ones for the storage and sharing to external EMR or other care management tools, should be funded from general taxation ○ B2C: some services should be sold directly to the patient or his caregiver, for example the ones for monitoring the patient’s status or for the cognitive stimulation • Considering the central role of the caregivers, their training costs must be considered also to meet their needs

2.3.3 Sweden Service Model

In Chapter 2.3.1 a value proposition common to all the 4 countries involved in DECI has been analyzed. However, this general service model must be enriched with further specificities related to the Swedish Customer Segments (and consequently Value Proposition).

Specifically, the Swedish customer profile is enriched with further needs (and required actions to address the various needs) identified as extremely relevant by the Swedish clinicians: the union between these needs and the ones common to all the DECI countries, shapes the complete Sweden Customer Segments building block. Starting from this, also the common Value Proposition described in the previous Chapter is completed, with features specific for Sweden.

Fitting the Swedish specific needs with the functionalities that can meet these needs, further specific service model elements for Sweden are available:

- Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities for diagnosis and assessment {*Clinical diagnosis*}.
- Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity for patient physical needs {*Medication Reminders*}.

The functionalities clusters are enriched, for the Swedish case, as follow:

- Patient's activities (Monitoring): trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities;
- Patient's Activities (Alert): provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity.

These packages goes to complete the general service model, shaping the Swedish specific one.

Patient layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up	Patient physical needs
Patient's status (Monitoring)	7	1			
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation)			3		
Patient's status (Alert)		1			
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)	4	2		2	
Patient's activities (Alert)	2	3	2	2	1
Patient's activities (Monitoring)	5			1	

Overall system layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up
Care providers (Communication)	1			
Care providers (teamwork)		2		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)		1		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)		2		

- High match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between needs & functionalities

Country specificities

Figure 9 - Swedish value proposition

As shown in **Figure 9**, Swedish clinicians underline the importance of other needs in addition to those common to all the countries, particularly the patient physical needs that can be met provisioning automatic reminder to patients for the performing of scheduled activities.

Furthermore, the Swedish clinicians considers the diagnosis & assessment more important than what the clinicians of the other countries do, in particular to monitor the patient's activities.

At the same time, is important to stress that the functionalities that can cover a greater number of needs - all those considered as relevant by the Swedish clinicians - are the ones that can make alert on patient's activities. **Table 46** presents the main impacts on the other building blocks.

Table 46 - How the Swedish Service Model affect the BMC building blocks

<p style="text-align: center;">Upstream building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Swedish clinicians consider crucial the diagnosis and assessment: about that, for an early detection GPs (that have a geographically broad responsibility) and Health Centers (the two are connected) should be involved • To meet the clinical team needs, it is important to provide the technological functionalities to the municipalities, that have the responsibility to organize the long-term care services for older people and provide them support • Provide alerts based on patient’s activities meet all the 5 clusters of needs: also considering the sparse population, this mean that is important to provide automatic remote feedbacks to the patients. This is possible not only mapping the patient’s activities, but also through an engagement of the patient and keeping the relationship with him or, if present, his caregiver (considering the low tendency to informal care) • To provide automatic reminders to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity is important to personalize the service to the specific characteristics of the patient, properly inserted within his daily activities • From an overall system viewpoint, is crucial to enable multidisciplinary teamwork across the Local Authorities (county councils and municipalities), and facilitate the sharing of treatment plan among caregivers, doctors and family members (or some of these). This could be made easier at the local government level, where several county councils initiated reform projects focusing on the development of community services (locally organized and provided services that should respond to the needs for common preventive and curative services for the population) for example to improve the care for older people and for patients with chronic diseases
<p style="text-align: center;">Downstream building blocks</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A new cluster of needs has been identified as relevant from the Swedish clinicians: the patient physical needs • The caregiver hasn’t a central role (low tendency to informal care: just 14% of the population is already taking care of person with long-term illness or disability) and is better to focus on the engagement and empowerment of the patients, keeping him informed about the evolution of symptoms and of the disease

Cost and revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue Streams should change depending on the specific country council, because the number of private primary care providers varies widely between the county councils (in some urban county councils up to 60% of the primary care providers may be private, whereas in other county councils only a few private providers can be found) • The same variation in the public/private mix of providers can be found across the municipalities. This can also affect how some services, for example the ones for monitoring the patient’s status or for the cognitive stimulation, are provided: directly to the patient or his caregiver (B2C), or sold as a bundle from the private primary care providers (B2B)
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2.3.4 Spain Service Model

In Chapter 2.3.1 a value proposition common to all the 4 countries involved in DECI has been analyzed. However, this general service model must be enriched with further specificities related to the Spanish Customer Segments (and consequently Value Proposition).

Specifically, the Spanish customer profile is enriched with further needs (and required actions to address the various needs) identified as extremely relevant by the Spanish clinicians: the union between these needs and the ones common to all the DECI countries, shapes the complete Spanish Customer Segments building block. Starting from this, also the common Value Proposition described in the previous Chapter is completed, with features specific for Spain.

Fitting the Spanish specific needs with the functionalities that can meet these needs, further specific service model elements for Spain are available:

- Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients’ monitoring activities for Diagnosis and assessment {*Clinical diagnosis & Frailty*} & Caregivers needs {*Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease*};
- Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity for Patient physical needs {*Physical activity plan and exercise*};
- Availability of personalized and adaptable remote-based training programs automatically tailored on individual patient’s characteristics for Patient physical needs {*Physical activity plan and exercise*}.

The functionalities clusters are enriched, for the Spanish case, as follow:

- Patient's activities (Monitoring): trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients’ monitoring activities;
- Patient’s Activities (Alert):
 - Provision of automatic reminder to patients for the performing of a scheduled activity;
 - Availability of personalized and adaptable remote-based training programs automatically tailored on individual patient’s characteristics.

These packages goes to complete the general service model, shaping the Spanish specific one.

Patient layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up	Caregivers needs	Patient physical needs
Patient's status (Monitoring)	7	1				
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation)			3			
Patient's status (Alert)		1				
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)	4	2		2		
Patient's activities (Alert)	2	3	2	2		2
Patient's activities (Monitoring)	6			1	1	

Overall system layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up
Care providers (Communication)	1			
Care providers (teamwork)		2		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)		1		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)		2		

- High match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between needs & functionalities

Country specificities

Figure 10 - Spanish value proposition

As shown in Figure 10, Spanish clinicians underline the importance of other needs in addition to those common to all the countries: particularly the caregivers needs and the ones regarding physical activities of the patient. Furthermore, the Spanish clinicians considers the diagnosis & assessment more important than what the clinicians of the other countries do, in particular to monitor the patient’s activities.

At the same time, the functionalities that can cover a greater number of needs are the ones that can monitor and make alert on patient’s activities.

Table 47 presents the main impacts on the other building blocks.

Table 47 - How the Spanish Service Model affect the BMC building blocks

Upstream building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Spanish clinicians consider crucial the diagnosis and assessment: about that, for an early detection GPs should be involved because of their central role in the system • To meet the clinical team needs, it is important to engage the Autonomous Communities, because of have not only the role of legislation, but also of management and provision health services • Provide alerts based on patient’s activities meet all the 5 clusters of patient needs: this mean that is crucial not only mapping the patient’s activities, but also through an engagement of the patient, keeping this relationship with him and his caregiver • To make available remote-based training programs tailored on individual patient’s characteristics, is important to personalize the service, properly inserted within his daily activities
Downstream building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further clusters of needs have been identified as relevant from the Spanish clinicians: the caregivers needs and the patient physical needs • The caregiver has a central role, is highly involved, and must be engaged and informed about the evolution of symptoms and of the disease
Cost and revenues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revenue Streams should be a B2P and B2C mix: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ B2P: some functionalities, for example the ones for the storage and sharing to external EMR or other care management tools, should be funded from general taxation ○ B2C: some services should be sold directly to the patient or his caregiver, for example the ones for monitoring the patient’s status or for the cognitive stimulation • Considering the central role of the caregivers, their training costs must be considered also to meet their needs

2.3.5 Israel Service Model

In Chapter 2.3.1 a value proposition common to all the 4 countries involved in DECI has been analyzed. However, this general service model must be enriched with further specificities related to the Israeli Customer Segments (and consequently Value Proposition).

Specifically, the Israeli customer profile is enriched with further needs (and required actions to address the various needs) identified as extremely relevant by the Israeli clinicians: the union between these needs and the ones common to all the DECI countries, shapes the complete Israeli Customer Segments building block. Starting from this, also the

common Value Proposition described in the previous Chapter is completed, with features specific for Israel.

Fitting the Israeli specific needs with the functionalities that can meet these needs, another specific service model element for Israel is available: Trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities for diagnosis and assessment {*Clinical diagnosis & Frailty*}

A functionality cluster is enriched for the Israeli case as follow: Patient's activities (Monitoring): trend analyses performed on data gathered from various patients' monitoring activities.

These packages goes to complete the general service model, shaping the Israeli specific one.

Patient layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up
Patient's status (Monitoring)	7	1		
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation)			3	
Patient's status (Alert)		1		
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)	4	2		2
Patient's activities (Alert)	2	3	2	2
Patient's activities (Monitoring)	6			1

Overall system layer	Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical team needs	Patient psychological needs	Follow-up
Care providers (Communication)	1			
Care providers (teamwork)		2		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)		1		
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)		2		

- High match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between needs & functionalities (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between needs & functionalities

Country specificities

Figure 11 - Israeli value proposition

As shown in **Figure 11**, Israeli clinicians have not highlighted other needs in addition to those common to all the countries. The unique specificity is related to the diagnosis & assessment, that the clinicians considers particularly relevant for the monitoring of patient’s activities.

At the same time, is important to stress that the functionalities that can cover a greater number of needs - all those considered as relevant by the Swedish clinicians - are the ones that can make alert on patient’s activities.

Table 48 presents the main impacts on the other building blocks.

Table 48 - How the Israeli Service Model affect the BMC building blocks

Upstream building blocks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Israeli clinicians consider crucial the diagnosis and assessment: about that, for an early detection GPs should be involved • Provide alerts based on patient’s activities meet all the 4 clusters of needs: this mean that is important to provide automatic remote feedbacks to the patients. This is possible not only mapping the patient’s activities, but also through an engagement of the patient and keeping the relationship with him or his caregiver • To meet the patient psychological needs, a possible key partnership could be the one with the “Supportive neighborhoods” program, that provide a “basket” that include especially social activities, as well as the safety and security of their homes • In addition to the Health Maintenance OrganisationsOrganizations (HMOs), is crucial to involve the Day care centers, where special programs for the cognitively impaired, including elderly people with Alzheimer’s disease and other types of dementia, has been established
Downstream building blocks	<p>Israeli clinicians have not highlighted other needs in addition to those common to all the countries, and the unique specificity related to the Customer Segments regards diagnosis & assessment, that is considered particularly relevant for the monitoring of patient’s activities</p>
Cost and revenu	<p>Revenue Streams should be based on a B2B model: however, cannot be excluded a B2C model for some services that would be sold directly to the patient (B2C), for example the ones for monitoring the patient’s status or for the cognitive stimulation</p>

2.4 Feasibility study for the business model inside each organizational context

We got the results of 11 of the Strategic Advisory Board (SAB) members and 4 invited expert opinion leaders, making a total of 15 returned questionnaires. See for an overview of SAB members, the project management plan in deliverable 8.1. The four invited experts

existed of: an associate professor in entrepreneurship and innovation (Canadian), a professor of Business Management (Dutch), a serial entrepreneur (Dutch) and a strategic business development officer of a university (Belgian).

A grand total of all the returned questionnaires gives the following rated averages (non-country specific) on a 5-point Likert scale, as shown in table 49.

1	The DECI service model clearly addresses the common value proposition via the patient layer and the overall system layer.	4,13
2	The business models allows to take relevant local/regional health and social system context elements into account (e.g. environment)	4,07
3	The business model delivers the value to the end-users and involved stakeholders.	3,80
4	The business model is NOT disruptive for clinicians and clinical stakeholders (normal patient flow).	3,80
5	The business model is in line with the current trends and developments in care for MCI patients.	4,00
6	The business model is in line with the current trends and developments in care for mild dementia patients.	3,86
7	The business model allows customization to different (end-)users-groups needs and wishes.	4,07
8	The business models takes all the relevant (regional/national) cost and revenue systems into account.	3,33
9	The resources and activities are enabling the business model' value delivery.	3,60
10	There is enough flexibility in the business model to cope with change drivers (technology, markets, (de-)regulation).	3,73
11	The business model offers a real possibility for ubiquitous commercialization in future.	3,47
12	The business model allows growth and scale-up easily.	3,73
13	The displayed pilot scenario design facts are realistic (as described in D1.5).	3,87
14	The business models converge with the pilot scenario design.	3,21

Table 49 Average scores per statement of all respondents (non-country specific)

2.4.1 Statements ranking

A cut-off of average of 3,00 for low-rated statements, and a cut-off of average 4,00 for high rated statements, was chosen. Below 3,60 cut-off we consider as 'alert' item to consider. This gives the following image:

- No items scored low: this means that there are not aspect that could seriously compromise the development of the project;
- Four statements (8, 9, 11 and 14) scored in the alert category: these statements point out aspects that have the potential — if not adequately managed — of impacting the overall feasibility of the BM;
- Four items (1, 2, 5 and 7) scored high: these element represent strengths over which basing the development of DECI pilot in order to increase their likely effectiveness;
- The remaining six items (3, 4, 6, 10, 12 and 13) are on par.

Focusing our attention on the alert category, it appears that:

- *The various BMs risk of not taking into account all the relevant (regional/national) cost and revenue systems present in each piloting countries (Statement 8):* this has been highlighted by SAB experts because is a crucial aspect that compromised several past projects accomplished in similar fields at both national and international levels; in order to cope with this potential issue, during the pilots design we will put a peculiar emphasis over the overall costs and revenues associated to the development of DECI proposal; a peculiar emphasis will be put on the engagement of the representative of the regional socio-care systems in which the pilots will be accomplished—due to their centrality in the definition of the cost and revenue structures; luckily, in most of the pilots we have already established strong connection with these actors.
- *The resources and activities available in the various pilots risk of not enabling the BM's value delivery (Statement 9):* although the various value propositions are recognized as adequately defined by SAB experts, the practical implementation of resources and activities related to these propositions is still not completely clear in this stage of the project; we expect to fulfill SAB concerns after the detailed design of the various pilots, which will deepen exactly these aspects as well as establishing a link to the proposed value propositions.
- *The BM could have issues in offering a real possibility for ubiquitous commercialization of DECI's output in the future (Statement 11):* the commercialization of DECI output in the future it is not a main goal that the consortium developing DECI gave to itself. Of course this aspect could positively affect the sustainability of the solution in the long run. Thus, in the design and development of the pilots we will try to produce solutions that are easily replicable in an affordable fashion into context and domain that are not those in which DECI project has been accomplished.
- *The BMs have potential issues on not converging with the pilot scenario design (Statement 14):* DECI BM has been purposefully designed in order to convergence by its nature with the bottom-up pilot design. The fact that SAB experts underlined a

potential issue from this viewpoint suggest that we have to put more emphasis on the communication of the robustness of the methodological approach that we have followed. In the upcoming dissemination phases we will develop a publication focusing exactly this topic, in order to be more clear and to reduce the potential concerns.

The other statements mentioned in Table 49 received medium-high evaluations by SAB experts, suggesting that the, overall, the project seems highly feasible. As far as the regional context settings is concerned, it was seen as one of the strongest points of the business models within the DECI project. This is in line with the customization flexibility of the models. Since the regional context are taken into account in the BMs, we allow for customization flexibility. The SAB considers this as a strong point. Furthermore, our models follow the key trends of the target population.

For the Israeli pilot, the relevant cost structures and revenue systems are rated as a factor that should be addressed more clearly in order to improve feasibility. For the Italian pilot, the flexibility to adopt and cope with change drivers is the possible weakest feasible link in the business model. Here, the contextual factors are of great value, end hence solutions can be found within the current model.

For the Spanish pilot, the concern lies in the convergence of the pilot with the general model and the connected cost and revenue systems for the Spanish situation of implementing the model. For the Swedish pilot, scale-up perspective and the ubiquitous commercialization perspective is rated as very unfeasible in the current business model. The same goes for the convergence of the pilot and the general DECI business model. Here the contextual factors might be of bigger influence then on beforehand anticipated.

2.4.2 Success and risk factors (country specific)

Success and risk factors elicited by the SAB and invited experts are shown in table 50.

	Identified success factors	Identified risk factors
<i>Israel</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The system, business models and concept are generic and flexible and will allow different care models to be implemented. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organizations avoid connecting to other organizations. This will take time for implementation and adaptation. It will be possible at first stage in smaller scales.
<i>Italy</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Modularity of the business model and adaptability to local situations makes it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Primarily costs of technology (i.e. hardware for patients)

	<p>interesting for applications in other national contexts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fall detection and alarm is a universal risk for geriatric patients, how to process the alarm and the cascading actions is a local implementation, fitting with existing or feasible infrastructures. • Applicability in different geographies and local organization of the community. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited spending possibilities of local/regional healthcare authorities. • Cultural attitudes and a resistance to change by users (technophobia). • Scarce interest of the patient/caregiver. • The possibility for commercialization in future. • Change management issues needed to efficiently implement such technologies. • No proven cost-effectiveness (yet).
<i>Spain</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The actual need for attention to this population. • The Spanish scientific-technical-organizational development and our health system is prepared and is suitable for this model. • Social services and dependency law has resources for MB. • You can apply the whole or part of BM (it's divisible, units can be offered). • It is already implemented (albeit poorly developed) the payment model for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MCI is poorly covered by the current attention in Spain; Dementia care, is attended only with medicines and other support covered by the Law of Dependence. • The Law of Dependence and it's aid is underdeveloped and applied an unequal way in different areas. • Political view which are against spending go to private systems. • National health system in Spain – which is divided and comparted – will possible endanger the implementation of ICT tools.

	<p>private services with Social Security check.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High prevalence of MCI and dementia. • Strong structure of health and social services. • Area of growing interest because of aging population and increasing demand for care. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty of combined treatment perspective health and social services. • Problems of access to new technology in Spain (patients and caregivers).
<i>Sweden</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation between CHI and VGR already developed successful business models. • Modularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changing environment of ICT systems in Sweden. • The intervention is to minor and hence no impact in KPI and real-life.

Table 50 Elicited success and risk factors of the DECI business models

General comments of the experts towards the consortium on the feasibility of the BMs are in line with the success and risk factors mentioned, as it is emphasised with the following quotes:

“In general, the business model presentation doesn't provide information about hurdles to overcome, resistance to be expected. It would be a good suggestion to do so”

“The general format and business model is clear and convincing, although the drawback might be in the strict format which makes it more difficult to appreciate national / regional differences / strengths. A next step could be to put it the other way around: given the fact that the general business model is convincing, what would be the typical national circumstances to take into account, and what we can learn from them?”

“A good improvement could be to align the business model to the expected normative frameworks for reimbursement from institutional payers”.

“In my opinion the personal motivation and the curiosity of the patient play key roles in technology usage. Patient empowerment can be obtained through services and technologies less standardized and more personalized. Indeed, a high level of personalization is required, for example with technologies specifically adapted to the map of patient’s activities”.

“Success is dependent by many factors, but two are critical. First, the service should be designed and delivered accordingly to the expectations of the different actors of the ecosystem. Additionally, once finalized the structure of the Business Model, it should be discussed also with the members of the Local Brain Storming”

“Patient's perspective and/or informal care-giver's perspective, including and specific needs are to be better evaluated and taken into account/integrated in the model. Daily life problems to be addressed with priority, e.g. getting lost. Mild Cognitive Impairment and mild dementia are very different in terms of disabilities.”

“I wish to emphasize the social-health aspect of the project, model in which the therapeutic action takes the value of the process of co-construction and co-production of health.”

“It is an ambitious project and I would like to have clear therapeutic benefits in relation to costs of products. It would also be very interesting to evaluate better what kind of people would be more feasible, for example, what kind of caregivers, which requires use of new technologies, etc.”

It is up to the consortium to re-iterate and implement improvements in the pilot scenarios and the pilot evaluation framework to find supporting data and create outstanding BMs.

3 Organizational and process models including variants of each local needs

3.1 Methodological approach and tools

This paragraph reports the main results of the activities executed within the T3.2 “Design of TO-BE organizational and process model including variants of each local needs”. This task is aimed at modelling and engineering the care processes for patients with Cognitive Impairment in the pilot countries involved in the project via the pervasive use of ICT, taking inputs from the care process analysis performed within the WP1 and the evidence emerged from the technological benchmark analysis (WP2).

The methodological approach applied, based on the *Business Process Reengineering* (BPR) method (Hammer, 1990; Champy, 2002)⁴, includes the following phases:

1. **Design of the care process model**, which firstly defines the *macro-phases of a general care process* applicable in each country (meta-model). This meta-model is defined starting from the literature and empirical analysis performed within the WP1. The impacts of the Business Models, designed within the T3.1 “Design of the business models for the delivery of assistance and independent living services”, will be analysed through these macro-phases.

Moreover, starting from the meta-model and the results of the WP1, a general home care process for patient with cognitive impairment is defined, as the basis for subsequent analysis. Please note that the macro-activity flow can't be radically modified, because of regulatory restrictions, although main changes are visible at the activity level (see TO-BE process models in Chapter 3.4).

2. **Analysis of the AS-IS processes in each pilot site**, which is aimed at modelling the AS-IS processes in each country, marking the process instances that have a different state and execution flow in the general care process model.

This phase is performed always starting from the empirical care process analysis performed within the WP1.

3. **Design of the TO-BE processes in each pilot site**, which underlines the difference between the two versions (AS-IS and TO-BE) of the home care process models in each country. The TO-BE process models of each local site are defined from the digital environments emerged from the top-down approach applied in T3.1.

The TO-BE process models identified will feed the T3.4 “Design of different implementation settings”, that defines the overall application (in terms of ICT solutions and processes) in each country.

In the following figure, there is a graphical synthesis of the methodological approach applied.

⁴ In DECI, the BPR approach is used to analyse current processes and to evaluate potential improvements is the as is-to be approach. Performing a strategic as is-to be analysis means starting from the study of the actual care pathways for people with cognitive impairment, in order to identify specific corrective actions for the future.

Figure 12 Methodological approach for designing home care process models

There are many tools useful to graphically representing business processes. The solution selected to define and analyse care pathways in the four pilot sites, is principally based on the *Business Process Modeling Notation –BPMN-* (White, 2004; Allweyer, 2010; OMG, 2009). Such notation is a method of illustrating processes in the form of a diagram (*Business Process Diagram*) constructed from a set of graphical components that should be easy to read for both the expert users and the expert providers of the services and for both technical and non-technical readers.

Graphical components are categorized into four major groups that are: *flow objects* (e.g. circles, rectangles and diamonds to indicate events and activities) *connecting objects* (e.g. arrows and line to indicate process directions), *swimlanes* (visual mechanism of straight lines to categorize activities in different categories), *artifacts* (e.g. rectangles used to add information in the model).

Moreover, specific notations are used to mark the process instances that have a different state and execution flow of the general care process model and to underline the difference between the two versions (AS-IS and TO-BE) of the home care processes models in each country (Hammer, 1990).

We used a Weber et al. (2009) specific notation to visualizing the actual execution of the activities in the process. Since it is possible to apply the notation in different contexts, whereas the meta-model remains the same, each declination may have a distinct execution flow. Weber et al. (2009) use three different state markers, graphically attached to activities, for indicating the state of activities in a process instance: *activated*, *completed* and *skipped*.

Figure 13 Concepts for visualizing activity states according to Weber *et al.* (2009)

Moreover, we adopted the Slama and Nelius (2011) notation to show differences between two versions of a process (AS-IS and TO-BE models) in each pilot site. They use three different symbols, similarly attached to activities, that are: *new*, *modified* and *disposed* activities. The semantic information of the symbols is emphasized by colouring the activities.

Figure 14 Concepts for visualizing activity states according to Slama and Nelius (2011)

In particular, in this analysis, for the AS-IS layout, we implemented the Weber's notation with these specific meanings:

- Activated activity mark refers to those activities that could be done, their activation depends on the specific situation of the patient path;
- Completed activity mark refers to those activities that always happen;
- Skipped activity mark refers to those intermediate activities that do not happen and are passed over in that country.

In the process maps, we show how the general model specifies itself into the four different pilot sites by colouring in grey the specific activities.

In the TO-BE layout, instead, we implemented the Slama and Nelius's notation with these specific meanings:

- New activity mark refers to those activities that are not in the AS-IS process;

- Modified activity mark refers to those activities that are substantially modified from the AS-IS status. These changes must be huge and be related not only to an information technology switch;
- Disposed activity mark refers to those activities that are eliminated from the AS-IS process without any flow interruption.

For TO-BE process models the differences from the AS-IS process models are clearly highlighted by coloured boxes.

Please, note that the “skipped activity” and the “disposed activity” marks are graphically similar but they have a different meaning, for this reason they are used for the AS-IS and TO-BE process models, respectively.

3.2 Design of the care process model

The purpose of process models is to document and communicate processes and to enhance the reuse of processes. A meta-model can be instantiated several times in order to define various process models (Hammer, 1990). For this reason, the analysis is firstly focusing on designing a meta-model of the care process for people with cognitive impairment, in order to have a common point of reference among analysis.

The analysis is based on results emerged from D1.1 “State-of-the-art of clinical and assistance management models and practices of older adults with cognitive impairment due to MCI or dementia” and on the literature analysis on care models for people with cognitive impairment (Fabbricotti, 2013; NICE; Øvretveit et al., 2010; Goñia, 2012; Alzheimer’s Society and Lilly UK, 2013), reported also in D1.5 “Design of the final pilot based on the pre pilot study”.

The analysis highlighted four common phases to every care process for people with cognitive impairment, showed in Figure 15.

Figure 15 Meta-model of the care process for people with CI

Noticing symptoms and first detection

This first phase includes the access point of the patient with cognitive impairment in the care process and it considers the first identification of the patient with suspected

cognitive impairment. Please, note that this phase includes all activities aimed at the early detection of cognitive impairment (e.g. periodical screening of the older population).

The patient can access the care service by different channels, related to different actors involved in the process:

- *General Practitioners* who are strictly related to the patient, especially older people, for periodic visits. GPs are the principal figures that activate the care process and they often open the channel between patients and socio-health care providers or specialized physicians;
- *External s*, such as Geriatricians or Neurologists that direct the patient to a socio-health care provider. The patient, often, is directed to external specialized physicians by the GP;
- *Socio-health care providers* that include specific ward in Hospitals, Nursing Home or Community, that with their health-care professionals (such as Occupational Therapists – OTs, physiotherapists or specialized physicians) and social workers deliver the whole spectrum of socio-health care services needed by patients affected by cognitive impairment. The patient, often, accesses the socio-health care provider directed by GP or external specialized physicians.

Assessment and diagnosis

This phase considers all clinical activities aimed at the assessment and diagnosis of the cognitive impairment in the patient identified in the previous phase. The output of this phase is all clinical information needed to define the care service. The phase includes:

- A first basic assessment of cognitive impairment that can be owned by the *GP*, the *socio-health care provider* or *External specialized physicians*; and then,
- A comprehensive assessment that is usually owned the *socio-health care provider*, although some of the requested exams are provided by external physicians (e.g. neurological examination)

This phase also considers all periodical follow-ups of the patients that do not need a care service at this moment, but they need to be constantly monitored, to be accessed to the care process as soon as they need.

Treatment and care service definition

In this phase, the patient needs are analysed, both clinical needs, emerged from the clinical assessment delivered in the previous phase, and social needs, usually analysed with the patient and the family with a Social Assistant. When needs are defined and clear, the care service is designed.

The main owner of this phase is always the *socio-health care provider*, but note that this phase needs to be delivered coherently with external stakeholders involved in the care

process (e.g. external Social Assistants, for example, from the Municipalities or other social-health care providers that provide different services to the same patient).

Service delivery and follow-up

The final phase considers the delivery of the care service designed in the previous phase and the continuous monitoring of his social and health status. From this phase, the care process can stop, or it can restart depending on the specific situation.

Even in this case, the main owner of this phase is usually the *socio-health care provider*, but note that this phase need to be delivered coherently with internal and external stakeholders involved in the care process. For example, if the socio-health care provider has to deliver to the patient some cognitive exercises in a specific day, the social care provider (e.g. Municipality) should not accompany the patient to the supermarket.

Please note that the meta-model does not consider administrative activities, such as the services financing by the State or insurances (e.g. Beveridge vs Bismark model⁵).

As shown in the following figure, these macro-phases are detailed in the home care process, which is the basis for designing of the AS-IS and TO-BE process models in each pilot site.

⁵ Wallace, L. S., 2013, “A View of Health Care Around the World”, *Annals of Family Medicine*, 11(1), 84. <http://doi.org/10.1370/afm.1484>.

Figure 16 General model of the home care process for people with cognitive impairment

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

A deep analysis of the general model of the home care process is done phase by phase.

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
<p>Activation of the periodical screening of the older population</p>	<p>A first identification of early sign of cognitive impairment could be done through the activation of a screening of the population. This initiative might consist in a periodical check of the health status of people with different characteristics (i.e. people older than 65 years old or that are going to be 75). Moreover, it is also possible to screen the population by querying the Electronic Health Records looking for risk conditions.</p> <p>Screenings can be conducted by General Practitioners, the socio-health care provider or by other External specialized physicians (such as geriatricians and so on). However, the prevalent decision is to give the Primary care level the responsibility for screening the population, which is very effective, in particular, when a great proportion of the population goes to the General Practitioner even if they do not have a specific symptom related to dementia.</p> <p>The screening can be assessed using a list of questions and/or questionnaires and some validated tests (i.e. GDS, DSM, MMSE, SWEET, BARTHEL). Physical examinations are also possible.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General practitioner (GP), Socio-health care provider and/or External specialized specialists</p>
<p>Visit</p>	<p>Patients typically go to the physician to get health advice or treatments. They present one symptom or more and the physician tries to obtain further information about those symptoms and the patient's general status of health. The meeting between those two actors can take place on a regular basis, like a check-up visit, because patients need it for a particular reason or even after an acute episode, in a long term care facility. In any case, such types of encounters could put the basis for a detection of MCI o Dementia related problems.</p>

	<p>This activity can be delivered by General Practitioners, but also by the socio-health care provider and/or External specialized physicians.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General practitioner (GP), Socio-health care provider and/or External specialized physicians</p>
Detection of the patient with suspected CI	<p>Once patients with certain kind of characteristics have been identified through a periodical screening of the population or during a doctor's visit, their path continues in the care process. Physician of the socio-health care provider, whether GPs or External specialized physicians, should recognize the main symptoms of MCI or Dementia. Difficulties in learning and retaining new information, in handling complex tasks, in reasoning, in managing sense of direction, language and behaviours are all symptoms that help professionals identifying patients who need to be involved in a basic assessment, that is the following activity.</p> <p>Please, note that sometimes GPs identify the patient with suspected MCI or Dementia and, then, they point out the patient to the socio-health care provider or to External specialized physicians to activate the basic assessment.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General practitioner (GP), Socio-health care provider and/or External specialized physicians</p>
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Basic Assessment	<p>In case there are symptoms of Cognitive Impairment, both General Practitioners, the socio-health care provider and External specialized physicians can perform the so-called basic assessment. This initial assessment consists of a basic examination of patients with suspected MCI or Dementia, aimed at understanding more than one perspective on patients' health conditions, including also the social situation. During this phase, physicians perform the anamnesis, thus collecting information about the medical history by asking detailed questions either the patient or a patient's closed ones. Note that even if medical histories may vary in their depth and focus, the overall objective is always</p>

	<p>to put the basis to formulate a future and precise diagnosis of MCI or Dementia as early as possible. Therefore, a fundamental part of the basic assessment activity is the assessment of the physiological and psychological condition of the patient. Moreover, physicians that take the anamnesis, typically perform some basic screening tests, such as Pfeiffer or MMSE. In case the basic screening test performed yields positive results, a comprehensive assessment follows.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General practitioner (GP), Socio-health care provider and/or External specialized physicians</p>
<p>Comprehensive assessment</p>	<p>The comprehensive assessment is the first activity of the assessment and diagnosis phase that starts when basic screening tests yield positive results. The comprehensive assessment protocol for MCI and Dementia is a standardized protocol aimed at reaching a diagnosis (following activity) as accurate as possible. Therefore, in the hands of physicians, the result of this activity provides the basis for the design of an appropriate care plan, including appropriate services and good patient care. In order to do that, physicians belonging to the socio-health system, can interact with patients and administer the most appropriate validated tests. To help clinicians assess the possible presence of MCI or Dementia in people with suspected diseases, without being biased by the influence of variables associated to the age, the following tools are available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MMSE, Mini Mental State Examination - CDR, Clinical Dementia Rating - ADL, Activities of Daily Living - IADL, Instrumental Activities of Daily Living - Brain CT scan - CANE-S, Camberwell Assessment of Need for the Elderly – Short form (this tool is not usually used in the routinely clinical practice) - External exams (neurological examination, neuropsychological assessment, blood tests, liquor tests) <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider</p>

<p>Diagnosis of CI</p>	<p>Once clinicians have concluded both a basic and a comprehensive assessment as exposed above they are able to diagnose MCI or Dementia.</p> <p>More in detail, the diagnosis is the activity of determining the behavioural syndrome (that is MCI or Dementia) and the possible aetiology underlying the emerged behavioural syndrome (that is, Alzheimer disease, Vascular Dementia, etc.). Even if it is not always straightforward to determine the exact aetiology of Dementia (i.e. it happens that symptoms of different subtypes of dementia can overlap), physicians can determine it with a quite-high level of certainty.</p> <p>In case patients are diagnosed with MCI without a service need (see “Needs identification” activity), they will be continuously monitored and called back for further visits and comprehensive assessments (see “Call to the patient for a follow-up” activity). If symptoms do not worsen overtime, this cycle holds.</p> <p>Otherwise, in case patients are diagnosed with MCI with a service need or Dementia, it follows a definition of the home care service (see “Definition of the health care/social care service” activity).</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider</p>
<p>Call to the patient for a follow-up</p>	<p>Once diagnosis has been made, patients with MCI, that for the time being do not need the activation of care services, are followed-up at regular intervals -whose length depends on both the socio-healthcare provider’s characteristics and the patients’ health status-. The aim of this activity is to continuously monitor the variables that influence patients’ clinical conditions. It is fundamental to verify the suitability of treatments, the presence of unexpected clinical events or the presence of new behavioural disturbance in everyday activities. Before calling back the patient for a follow-up, the provider can also activate preventive interventions to control the most relevant risk factors (see “Activation of preventive interventions” activity).</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider</p>

Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Activation of preventive interventions	<p>If the patient is affected by MCI but for the time being do not need the activation of care services, the socio-health care provider can deliver preventative interventions, such as cognitive exercise or physical exercise.</p> <p>In some cases, the socio-health care provider provides only recommendations and guidance depending on the results of the comprehensive assessment, aiming to reduce risk factors (unhealthy lifestyle, depression, etc.) and to improve the functional status of the patient.</p> <p>However, the patient is continuously monitored and the comprehensive assessment is periodically repeated, until the patient needs to activate a care service (see “Call to the patient for a follow-up” activity).</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider</p>
Needs identification	<p>If the patient is affected by MCI or Dementia, the socio-health care provider discusses the diagnosis with the patient and his family. This activity is usually delivered in the presence of a Social Assistant, who can analyse the whole situation of the patient, also from a social perspective.</p> <p>If the patient affected by MCI or Dementia needs a care service, the socio-health care provider goes on with the definition of the service (see “Definition of the care service” activity). Otherwise, the socio-health care provider activates preventive interventions (see “Activation of preventive interventions” activity).</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider</p>
Definition of the health care/social care service	<p>Some providers deliver one type of service without integration with external stakeholders (e.g. Municipalities) or deliver both services but not internally integrated. In this case, the socio-health care provider defines the care plan, from a health perspective or from a social perspective.</p>

	<u>Main owner</u> : socio-health care provider
Definition of the socio-health care service	<p>The socio-health care provider defines the integrated care plan, from a socio-health care perspective, with an internal and external integration.</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider (with some external stakeholders)</p>
Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Delivery of the health/social care service	<p>The provider delivers the care service defined, going to the patient's home and providing the service (e.g. hygienic cleaning, cognitive exercises, accompany the patient to medical visits or to the supermarket, etc.).</p> <p>Some providers deliver one type of service (health care or social care) without integration with external stakeholders (e.g. Municipalities) or deliver both services but not internally integrated.</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider</p>
Delivery of the socio-health care service	<p>The provider delivers the care service defined, going to the patient's home and providing the service (e.g. hygienically cleaning, cognitive exercises, accompany the patient to medical visits or to the supermarket, etc.).</p> <p>Some providers deliver both types of services (health care and social care) internally integrated.</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider</p>
Integrated delivery of the socio-health care service	<p>The provider delivers the care service defined, going to patient's home and providing the service (e.g. hygienic cleaning, cognitive exercises, accompany the patient to medical visits or to the supermarket, etc.).</p>

	<p>Some providers deliver both types of services (health care and social care) internally integrated. <u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider (with some external stakeholders)</p>
<p>Continuous patient follow-up</p>	<p>During the service delivery the patient is continuously monitored by the socio-health care provider.</p> <p>If the service is aligned with patient’s needs, the socio-health care provider goes on with the delivery of the care service. If there are some variations on the patient’s status and on his needs, the service and the related process are consequently adjusted: the process restart from the “Needs identification” activity.</p> <p>Finally, in case of change of external factors (e.g. death of the patient), the service is interrupted and the process is closed.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider</p>

Table 51 Deep analysis of the general model of the home care process

3.3 Design of the AS-IS process models in each pilot site

3.3.1 HUG AS-IS process

Figure 17 HUG AS-IS process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the Spanish pilot, the socio-health care provider of the AS-IS process model is represented by the University Hospital of Getafe, which has a direct communication with the Primary Care Centres (GPs).

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Visit	<p>In Spain, due to close contacts between patients and GPs, visits to this kind of professionals offer important opportunities to detect MCI related problems. Therefore, GPs in Primary Care typically diagnose and monitor people with cognitive impairment during those regular encounters.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General practitioner – GP <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OMI-AP - AP-Madrid - HORUS
Detection of the patient with suspected CI	<p>General practitioners in Primary Care are responsible for the identification of the health status of patients with MCI or Dementia. Once patients have been identified during a GP's visit, their path continues in the care process.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General Practitioner – GP <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OMI-AP - AP-Madrid - HORUS
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Basic Assessment	<p>In case there are symptoms of cognitive impairment that do not seem age-related, the GPs that take the anamnesis, perform a basic assessment. This step typically consists in the administration of some basic screening tests, such as Pfeiffer or MMSE. The region of Madrid is one of the regions in Spain that counts on a screening for Alzheimer for people older than 65, assessed during the MiniMental and conducted by a Primary Care Nurse.</p>

	<p>In case the screening tests yield positive results, the physician will refer the patient to a Specialized Care, according to his/her condition and morbidities: (a) if patients are younger than 65 years old, they are usually referred to the Neurology Service; (b) if patients are older than 65 years old, they are usually referred to the Geriatrics Service; (c) if patients have (or had in past) psychiatric problems, they are referred to the Psychiatric Service.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner – GP - Primary Care Nurse <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OMI-AP - AP-Madrid - HORUS
<p>Comprehensive assessment</p>	<p>The Specialized Care Units typically perform the comprehensive assessment. Both the Geriatrics and the Neurology Service have specific consultations for Dementia. If the patient is new for the Unit, the consultation lasts for one hour, otherwise, for subsequent revisions (see the activity “Call the patient for a follow-up”), the visit is shorter and it takes half an hour.</p> <p>In particular, the geriatricians of the Geriatrics Service perform a Geriatric Multidimensional Assessment, comprising the following elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical anamnesis (medical and family history) - Physical and neurological exam - MMSE (MiniMentalFolstein Spanish adaptation) and MoCA (Montreal Cognitive Assessment) - GDS (Geriatric Deterioration Scale for Dementia) or FAST (Functional Assessment Staging) - ADL (Activities of Daily Living) - IADL (Instrumental Activities of Daily Living) - Blood tests, in order to screen common metabolic disorders, Vitamin B12 deficiency, Vitamin D, hypothyroidism, syphilis, etc.

	<p>Additional examinations might include a Brain CT Scan or a Brain MRI. It is also recommended to perform both a neuropsychological assessment with a cognitive and behavioural anamnesis, that involves caregivers, and a more formal one. Furthermore, in the rare cases of specific etiological differential diagnosis, Brain PET, DaTSCAN, EEG and lumbar puncture are prescribed.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS
<p>Diagnosis of CI</p>	<p>The physicians at the Specialized Care Units are able to diagnose and treat the disease.</p> <p>In case the patient is diagnosed with MCI or Dementia, the specialist starts the treatment, that might cover two different approaches: the pharmacological and the non-pharmacological one.</p> <p>Moreover, the Neurology Service has a neuropsychologist available once a week to assess the most complicated cases.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS
<p>Call to the patient for a follow-up</p>	<p>In case patients are diagnosed with MCI, a guidance is provided. The type of recommendations depends on the results of the Comprehensive Geriatrics Assessment, whose aim is to reduce some risk factors (e.g. unhealthy lifestyle, depression) and to improve the health condition of people (see the activity “Comprehensive Assessment”). For follow-up, patients are referred in the Memory Clinic in a period of about 6 months.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe <u>Information system:</u></p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS
Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Needs identification	<p>Before starting the treatment, patients diagnosed with MCI or Dementia need to show the prescription to someone who will approve or reject it, that is the GP and an independent inspector (i.e. psycho-geriatrician and/or clinical pharmaceutical).</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS
Definition of the health care/social care service	<p>In case patients are diagnosed with MCI or Dementia, a pharmacological treatment is defined (for details about the program, see the activity “Delivery of the health/social care service”).</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - HIRE
Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Delivery of the health/social care service	<p>In case of pharmacological treatment, the GPs perform a continuous follow-up of the health status of patients and of the possible negative effects of the medication. For example, they increase the dose if no adverse effects are detected until the maximum recommended dose is reached.</p> <p>Once the patient is stable, physicians establish routine visits (see the activity “Continuous patient follow-up”) with screening tests to evaluate the performance on a daily</p>

	<p>basis, the progression of the disease and the effectiveness of the medication.</p> <p>In case of non-pharmacological treatment, there is not an established protocol or a precise program for the long-term support of patients. If the patient has a specific problem, it happens that the Specialized Services refer him/her to other specialists, such as physiotherapists, speech therapists, nutritionists, and so on. Note that the Geriatrics Service has a Day Hospital with an occupational therapist. In the DH, patients that have problems in performing their daily activities, are enrolled in personalized exercise programs that aim to promote independent living.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - HIRE
<p>Continuous patient follow-up</p>	<p>Once patients have been diagnosed, the specialist (geriatrician, neurologist or psychiatrist) attend them at regular intervals: 3 months at the beginning of the disease and every 6 – 12 months as the disease progresses. Primary care will also schedule regular visits, but the patient can attend on demand at any time.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe - General practitioner – GP <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - HIRE

Table 52 HUG AS-IS process description

3.3.2 MAC AS-IS process

Figure 18 MAC AS-IS process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the Israeli pilot, the analysis is focused on the Maccabi Healthcare Centre and its MCI patients. In this document, the Socio-health care provider is the Maccabi Healthcare Centre that includes all professionals belonging to this centre (Geriatric multidisciplinary centre, OT centres, Specialists, etc.). Note that the GPs in Maccabi are included in the Centre, but for the practical reason of being aligned to the general model they are graphically represented in a different swim lane.

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
<p>Activation of the periodical screening of the older population</p>	<p>A first identification of early sign of cognitive impairment is done through the activation of a "gentle/by the way" 75th-birthday screening. Maccabi launched this proactive and strategic initiative for screening older population, employing 30 geriatricians and 1400 general practitioners, in particular because many people prefer going to the GP and not to a specialist if they do not have a specific health problem.</p> <p>It is possible that younger people are screened for cognitive, frailty and depression prevention. Moreover, Maccabi screens the population by querying the Electronic Health Records looking for risk conditions, according to 7 criteria (from 4 to 7 the patient is at risk):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age above 75 y.o. - Co-morbidity- 2 or more chronic diseases - More than 2 hospitalizations/emergency room visits in the last year - More than 2 physician home visits (emergency) - Malnutrition - Polypharmacy- above 8 medications - Permanent use of one of the following drugs: insulin, NSAID, diuretics, digoxin, anti-platelet, Coumadin, sulfonylureas or heparin antithrombotic agent <p>Patients who are at risk of cognitive impairment are invited in the clinic by the professionals to start an assessment.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Practitioner - GP

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Visit	<p>One of the pathway that Maccabi uses to identify patients with suspected CI is the physician’s visit. In particular, a typical channel is the visit that makes the geriatric evaluation and a general consultation. The physician can be GP that works in clinic or in the multidisciplinary centre or can be a specialist.</p> <p>Maccabi has recently launched a new program that aims to improve screening, early detection and intervention by GPs.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Detection of the patient with suspected CI	<p>Once patients have been identified through the different types of screenings of the population or during a physician’s visit, their path continues in the care process. In Maccabi, both GPs, physicians of the multidisciplinary centre or External specialized physicians can recognize the main symptoms of cognitive impairment.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Basic Assessment	<p>In Maccabi, screening visits consist of physical examinations. A problem for the assessment is that the general practitioner usually has maximum 10 minutes per visit while the screening takes 45 minutes. Then, Maccabi decided to pay a special fee for the screening to GPs.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Comprehensive assessment	<p>If the screening is positive for MCI, the GP can refer the patient to a specialist for a comprehensive assessment in one of the following fields: geriatrics, neurology and psychiatry.</p> <p>The multidisciplinary teamwork is typically constituted by GPs, nurses, social workers, nutritionists, occupational therapists, dieticians, physiotherapists and psychiatrists that manage elderly and frail patients when needed. Those patients are referred to the CGA units, that are the units created for conducting a <i>Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment</i>.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Diagnosis of CI	<p>The physicians are able to diagnose and treat the disease.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Activation of preventive interventions	<p>If the patient is affected by MCI, the socio-health care provider delivers preventative interventions, workshops for memory and MCI related symptoms treatment, F2F visits homecare visits and training for physical exercise and cognitive exercise.</p> <p>In Maccabi they prove that an early treatment can have benefits on the progression of symptoms.</p>

	<p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Needs identification	<p>If the patient is affected by MCI, the socio-health care provider discusses the diagnosis with the patient and his family. In Israel, the family involvement is very important because the majority of elderly and frail people live at home (almost 95%) and the majority of treatments take place in the community.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists - Social worker <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Definition of the socio-health care service	<p>Maccabi's teams provide, maintain and coordinate most of the social care services (according to organizational guidelines and to the national law) and they also contract some services with outside providers.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists - Social worker <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>
Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Delivery of the socio-health care service	<p>When patients are diagnosed with MCI, drug treatments are recommended to slow down the symptoms and to control behavioural problems. In Maccabi, many patients are treated by multidisciplinary homecare teams, that put their effort to be trained appropriately in order to address the wide range of patients' needs. Treatments for the psychological manifestations of Dementia are usually</p>

	<p>carried out outside Maccabi. In cases the patient remains at home, Maccabi offers a home care program to support the care at home and support the family.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists - Social worker - Home care teams - GP <p><u>Information system: EHR</u></p>
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Table 53 MAC AS-IS process description

3.3.3 FDG AS-IS process

Figure 19 FDG AS-IS process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the pilot in Italy, the socio-health care provider of the AS-IS process model is represented by the Palazzolo Institute, centre of Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi Onlus, that offers care programs and integrated assistance services to older adults.

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Visit	<p>The meeting between patients and physicians can take place on a regular basis, like a check-up visit, or after an acute episode in a long term care facility.</p> <p>Physicians can be General Practitioners, External specialized physicians, or they can belong to the Palazzolo Institute.</p> <p>Note that at this stage, when the patient interacts with his/her General Practitioner or with a specialist, often he/she is not referred to a specialized service for the diagnosis of MCI or Dementia.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Socio-health care provider – Specialists at FDG Palazzolo Institute - External specialized physicians <p><u>Information system:</u> WebHospital (FDG)</p>
Detection of patients with suspected CI	<p>Physicians at the Palazzolo Institute, GPs or External specialized physicians should recognize the main symptoms of cognitive impairment.</p> <p>It could be that the GPs identify the patient with suspected MCI or Dementia and perform the basic assessment, but it is also possible that they point out the patient to the Palazzolo Institute or to External specialized physicians to activate the assessment.</p> <p>Once patients with certain kind of characteristics have been identified during a physician’s visit, their path continues in the care process (see the Activity “Basic Assessment”).</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socio-health care provider – Specialists at FDG Palazzolo Institute - External specialized physicians <p><u>Information system:</u> Web-Hospital (FDG)</p>
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Basic Assessment	<p>In case there are symptoms of cognitive impairment, both General Practitioners, specialists at the Palazzolo Institute and External specialized physicians can perform the basic assessment. Note that usually the GP points out the patient to specialists (at the Palazzolo Institute or externally).</p> <p>This initial assessment consists of a basic examination of patients with suspected MCI or Dementia, aimed at understanding more than one perspective on patients' health conditions, including also the social situation. In case the basic assessment strengthens the initial suspicion of cognitive impairment, a comprehensive assessment follows.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Socio-health care provider – Specialists at FDG Palazzolo Institute - External specialized physicians <p><u>Information system:</u> Web-Hospital (FDG)</p>
Comprehensive assessment	<p>The comprehensive assessment protocol for MCI and Dementia is a standardized protocol aimed at reaching a diagnosis as accurate as possible. At the Palazzolo Institute, for a comprehensive assessment, patients can be referred to a specialized geriatrics unit (e.g. the UVA - Unità Valutazione Alzheimer). GPs, other specialists or geriatricians in the Institute who saw the patient for another issue, can put patients in touch with the specialized unit. At this point, the unit starts the assessment protocol aimed at reaching the diagnosis (following activity).</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo Institute</p> <p><u>Information system:</u> Web-Hospital, BI</p>

<p>Diagnosis of CI</p>	<p>Typically, a specialized geriatrics service (e.g. UVA) is responsible for the diagnosis of patients with MCI or Dementia (see the activity “Comprehensive Assessment”).</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo Institute <u>Information system</u>: Web-Hospital, BI</p>
<p>Call to the patient for a follow-up</p>	<p>Once diagnosis has been made, patients with MCI, that for the time being do not need the activation of care services, are followed-up at regular intervals or on demand, and they are properly trained. Patients are followed-up to monitor cognitive functions and reversible clinical conditions potentially associated with cognitive impairment.</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo Institute <u>Information system</u>: Web-Hospital, BI</p>
<p>Phase</p>	<p>Treatment and care service definition</p>
<p><i>Activity</i></p>	<p><i>Activity description</i></p>
<p>Needs identification</p>	<p>In Italy, it is common that patients’ relatives or caregivers take the responsibility for organizing the care pathway of their care receivers, depending on the progressive reduction of their autonomy. If patients are monitored by the UVA, the care pathway can be managed by PASS (“Punto di Accesso Socio-Sanitario”) and ST (“Servizi Territoriali”) through the activation of home-based and facility-based services, whose activation is discussed together with the family.</p> <p>It is possible that caregivers look for the assistance of formalized services in particular in case of patients’ clinical or functional deterioration, evolution of behavioural and psychological symptoms of dementia, falls, malnutrition, dysphagia, etc. The domestic care system can also break down because of caregivers’ burnout or temporary unavailability.</p> <p><u>Main owner</u>: socio-health care provider – PASS and ST at FDG Palazzolo Institute</p>

	<u>Information system:</u> Web-Hospital, BI (only for PASS, ST has not a Web ERP)
Definition of the socio-health care service	<p>When patients are diagnosed with MCI or Dementia, if possible, it starts a pharmacological treatment with AChEI and a follow-up is scheduled. At this stage, for both patients suffering from MCI or Dementia, the specialist of the UVA interacts with PASS and ST services to activate the required socio-health care services (e.g. home-care services, case-management or psychological counselling to caregivers). From 2015 there are two new home-care services offered to patients with Dementia: ADI Demenza and RSA Aperta.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit, PASS and ST at FDG Palazzolo Institute <u>Information system:</u> Web-Hospital, BI (only for UVA and PASS, ST has not a Web ERP)</p>
Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Integrated delivery of the socio-health care service	<p>The Palazzolo Institute delivers the health care and social care services defined, going also to patient’s home to provide them.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider <u>Information system:</u> Web-Hospital, BI</p>
Continuous patient follow-up	<p>During the service delivery the patient is continuously monitored by the professionals of the Institute. It is fundamental to verify the suitability of treatments, the presence of unexpected clinical events or the presence of new behavioural disturbance in everyday activities.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo <u>Information system:</u> Web-Hospital, BI</p>

Table 54 FDG AS-IS process description

3.3.4 VGR AS-IS process

Figure 20 VGR AS-IS process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the pilot in Sweden, the socio-health care provider of the AS-IS process model is represented by the Skaraborg Care Network (SCN) that includes all Primary Care Centres, 17 communities and the 4 hospitals at the Skaraborg Hospital Group (SHG). Please, note that the primary care physician is included in the Primary Care Centre.

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Visit	<p>In Skaraborg, patients are usually visited in the Primary Care Centres or in the Hospitals.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>
Detection of patients with suspected CI	<p>Once patients with certain kind of characteristics have been identified during a doctor's visit, the physician send a message to a specialized nurse of the Primary Care Centres.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Basic assessment	<p>In Skaraborg, once the specialized nurses responsible for MCI and Dementia (ND) have received a message (from patients, patients' relatives, physicians, nurses, hospitals or</p>

	<p>the community) containing information about suspected patients, they contact patients and relatives within two weeks.</p> <p>At this point, the NDs perform a pre-visit, that would be followed by a more comprehensive assessment held by physicians (see the activity “Comprehensive Assessment”).</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>
<p>Comprehensive assessment</p>	<p>The Primary Care Centres are responsible for the first examination of patients with suspected MCI or Dementia.</p> <p>This initial examination involves different perspectives on the patients’ current condition (including the social situation). In Skaraborg the initial assessment consists of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A structured anamnesis including interviews with nearest and dearest - An assessment of the physiological and psychological condition of the patient - Cognitive tests including MMT and the Clock test - A structured assessment of patient activities of daily life and level of activity <p>In addition, tests to include other conditions are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CT scan - neuropsychological tests - blood tests - liquor tests <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>
<p>Diagnosis of CI</p>	<p>The Primary Care Centres are also responsible for the diagnosis of patients with suspected MCI or Dementia.</p>

	<p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>
Call to the patient for a follow-up	<p>At the Primary Care Centres, both the physician and the specialized nurse continuously monitor patients with MCI: at least yearly visits to the physician are planned, including a pre-visit to the nurse responsible for Dementia. Patients can also contact the specialized nurse at any time they need support. Note that the National Guidelines do not include a clinical pathway for patients with MCI, and interventions are decided on an individual basis.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u> -</p>
Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Needs identification	<p>If patients with MCI or Dementia get worse, the aid assistance coordinator collaborates with families, professionals of the hospital and of the Primary Care Centres.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>
Definition of the socio-health care service	<p>The aid assistance coordinator designs an individual care plan for the patient, and given the care plan, community care resources are made available for him/her, including basic home care.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals - Communities <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>

Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Integrated delivery of the socio-health care service	<p>Cross-professional teams, under the management of the Municipality, provide basic and long-term care of patients affected by dementia. The professional teams are led by the community Dementia nurse, that is a specialized nurse, supported by a general practitioner and the specialized nurse of the Primary Care Centre. In any case, the primary care physician has the overall medical responsibility for the patient.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals - Communities <p><u>Information System:</u> Local Information System</p>
Continuous patient follow-up	<p>During the service delivery the patient is continuously monitored by Primary Care Centres.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u> -</p>

Table 55 VGR AS-IS process description

3.3.5 AS-IS processes: an overall view

As represented in the four processes, all the local sites have the same process at a high level analysis. This demonstrate that the general home care process correctly maps every process configuration.

The main challenge was to combine the actors in the care system, because in each local site there are the same care actors organized in a different way. This is due not also to the characterization of each local care system, but also to the role of each clinical partner in the care network involved in the project.

As shown in the processes layouts, the pilot sites are different from each other: HUG is focused only on the health-care service, MAC offers both health-care and socio-care

services and, finally, VGR and FDG offer a socio-health care service integrated with external Community.

In the next Chapter, we show the TO-BE process models, designed from the AS-IS process models here described and the results of the BMs design (see D3.1).

3.4 Design of the TO-BE process models in each pilot site

3.4.1 HUG TO-BE process

Figure 21 HUG TO-BE process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the Spanish pilot, the socio-health care provider of the TO-BE process model is always represented by the University Hospital of Getafe, which has a direct communication with the Primary Care Centres (GPs).

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Visit	<p>In Spain, due to close contacts between patients and GPs, visits to this kind of professionals offer important opportunities to detect MCI related problems. Therefore, GPs in Primary Care typically diagnose and monitor people with cognitive impairment during those regular encounters.</p> <p>Before a visit, the caregiver could fill in a questionnaire describing the patient's symptoms on the DECI website. After filling in the questionnaire, the caregiver receives a first feedback, for example the website could recommend visiting the GP.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General practitioner – GP <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OMI-AP - AP-Madrid - DECI website
Detection of the patient with suspected CI	<p>General practitioners in Primary Care are responsible for the identification of the health status of patients with MCI or Dementia.</p> <p>The results of the questionnaire filled on the DECI website might indicate some form of cognitive impairment beyond normal ageing</p> <p>Once patients have been identified during a GP's visit with the support of the DECI questionnaire, their path continues in the care process.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> General Practitioner – GP <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OMI-AP - AP-Madrid - DECI platform
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
<p>Basic Assessment</p>	<p>In case there are symptoms of cognitive impairment that do not seem age-related, the GPs that take the anamnesis, perform a basic assessment. This step typically consists in the administration of some basic screening tests, such as Pfeiffer or MMSE.</p> <p>During the basic assessment, the GP discusses patient's symptoms and, in case of suspicion that the patient might have some type of MCI or Dementia, the GP opens the DECI platform and creates a profile for the patient. To this point, the physician appoints a visit with the nurse in Primary Care.</p> <p>The region of Madrid is one of the regions in Spain that counts on a screening for Alzheimer for people older than 65, assessed during the MiniMental and conducted by a Primary Care Nurse, following the protocol suggested by the DECI platform.</p> <p>DECI platform can be used by the caregiver to get more accurate information about the suspected disease and their options for services.</p> <p>In case the screening tests yield positive results, the physician will refer the patient to a Specialized Care with the support of the DECI platform, according to his/her condition and morbidities: (a) if patients are younger than 65 years old, they are usually referred to the Neurology Service; (b) if patients are older than 65 years old, they are usually referred to the Geriatrics Service; (c) if patients have (or had in past) psychiatric problems, they are referred to the Psychiatric Service.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner – GP - Primary Care Nurse <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - OMI-AP - AP-Madrid - DECI platform
<p>Comprehensive assessment</p>	<p>The Specialized Care Units typically perform the comprehensive assessment, starting from the preliminary tests run by the Primary Care, as</p>

	<p>suggested by the DECI platform. Both the Geriatrics and the Neurology Service have specific consultations for Dementia. If the patient is new for the Unit, the consultation lasts for one hour, otherwise, for subsequent revisions (see the activity “Call the patient for a follow-up”), the visit is shorter and it takes half an hour.</p> <p>In particular, the geriatricians of the Geriatrics Service perform a Geriatric Multidimensional Assessment, comprising the following elements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical anamnesis (medical and family history) - Physical and neurological exam - MMSE (MiniMentalFolstein Spanish adaptation) and MoCA (Montreal Cognitive Assessment) - GDS (Geriatric Deterioration Scale for Dementia) or FAST (Functional Assessment Staging) - ADL (Activities of Daily Living) - IADL (Instrumental Activities of Daily Living) - Blood tests, in order to screen common metabolic disorders, Vitamin B12 deficiency, Vitamin D, hypothyroidism, syphilis, etc. <p>Additional examinations might include a Brain CT Scan or a Brain MRI. It is also recommended to perform both a neuropsychological assessment with a cognitive and behavioural anamnesis, that involves caregivers, and a more formal one. Furthermore, in the rare cases of specific etiological differential diagnosis, Brain PET, DaTSCAN, EEG and lumbar puncture are prescribed.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - DECI platform
<p>Diagnosis of CI</p>	<p>The physicians at the Specialized Care Units, starting from the results stored on the DECI platform, are able to diagnose and treat the disease.</p> <p>In case the patient is diagnosed with MCI or Dementia , the specialist starts the treatment, that might cover two</p>

	<p>different approaches: the pharmacological and the non-pharmacological one. Moreover, the Neurology Service has a neuropsychologist available once a week to assess the most complicated cases.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - DECI platform
Call to the patient for a follow-up	<p>In case patients are diagnosed with MCI, a guidance is provided. The type of recommendations depends on the results of the Comprehensive Geriatrics Assessment, whose aim is to reduce some risk factors (e.g. unhealthy lifestyle, depression) and to improve the health condition of people (see the activity “Comprehensive Assessment”). The caregiver can directly contact professional in case of doubt on the disease. For follow-up, patients are referred in the Memory Clinic in a period of 6 months.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe <u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - DECI platform
Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Needs identification	<p>Before starting the treatment, patients diagnosed with MCI or Dementia need to show the prescription to someone who will approve or reject it, that is to GP and an independent inspector (i.e. psycho-geriatrician and/or clinical pharmaceutical) with the support of the DECI platform.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe</p>

	<p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - DECI platform
<p>Definition of the health care/social care service</p>	<p>In case patients are diagnosed with MCI or Dementia, a pharmacological treatment is defined (for details about the program, see the activity “Delivery of the health/social care service) by a care network.</p> <p>The patient’s profile is available on the DECI platform and visible to all professionals of the care system. In this case, if the caregiver contacts a social worker he can see all data and previous tests performed by the patient.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - HIRE - DECI platform
Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
<p>Integrated delivery of the socio-health care service</p>	<p>In case of pharmacological treatment, the GPs perform a continuous follow-up of the health status of patients and of the possible side effects of the medication. For example, they increase the dose if no adverse effects are detected until the maximum recommended dose is reached.</p> <p>Once the patient is stable, physicians establish routine visits (see the activity “Continuous patient follow-up”) with screening tests to evaluate the performance on a daily basis, the progression of the disease and the effectiveness of the medication.</p> <p>In case of non-pharmacological treatment, there is not an established protocol or a precise program for the long-term support of patients. If the patient has a specific problem, it happens that the Specialized Services refer him/her to other specialists, such as physiotherapists,</p>

	<p>speech therapists, nutritionists, and so on. Note that the Geriatrics Service has a Day Hospital with an occupational therapist. In the DH, patients that have problems in performing their daily activities, are enrolled in personalized exercise programs that aim to promote independent living.</p> <p>The DECI platform supports these treatments with different reminders on daily activities or medication activities, directly to the patient or to the caregiver. Moreover, the patient’s activity is monitored with a specific wearable device that send this information on the DECI platform.</p> <p>Every once in a while, to the patient it’s requested to fill in some questionnaires about their cognitive status, where needed with the help of the caregiver.</p> <p>Moreover, the caregiver and the physician receive a notice in the DECI platform summarizing the results of the patient’s activities.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - HIRE - DECI platform - DECI activity monitoring device
<p>Continuous patient follow-up</p>	<p>Once patients have been diagnosed, the specialist (geriatrician, neurologist or psychiatrist) attend them at regular intervals: 3 months at the beginning of the disease and every 6 – 12 months as the disease progresses. Primary care will also schedule regular visits, but the patient can attend on demand at any time.</p> <p>The follow-up visit is supported by the DECI platform, where are stored all patient’s activities and the results of the questionnaires about patient’s cognitive status.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Socio-healthcare provider – Geriatrics or Neurology Service of the University Hospital of Getafe - General practitioner – GP <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clinical Documentation (CD) - HORUS - HIRE - DECI platform
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Table 56 HUG TO-BE process description

3.4.2 MAC TO-BE process

Figure 22 MAC TO-BE process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the Israeli pilot, we focus on the Maccabi Healthcare Services and its MCI patients.

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
<p>Activation of the periodical screening of the older population</p>	<p>A first identification of early sign of cognitive impairment is done through the activation of a "gentle/by the way" 75th-birthday screening. Maccabi launched this proactive and strategic initiative for screening older population, employing 30 geriatricians and 1400 general practitioners, in particular because many people prefer going to the GP and not to a specialist if they do not have a specific health problem.</p> <p>It is possible that younger people are screened for cognitive, frailty and depression prevention. Moreover, Maccabi screens the population by querying the Electronic Health Records looking for risk conditions, according to 7 criteria (from 4 to 7 the patient is at risk):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Age above 75 y.o. - Co-morbidity- 2 or more chronic diseases - More than 2 hospitalizations/emergency room visits in the last year - More than 2 physician home visits (emergency) - Malnutrition - Polypharmacy- above 8 medications - Permanent use of one of the following drugs: insulin, NSAID, diuretics, digoxin, anti-platelet, Coumadin, sulfonylureas or heparin antithrombotic agent <p>Patients who are at risk of cognitive impairment are invited in the clinic by the professionals to start an assessment.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General Practitioners - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR</p>

<p>Visit</p>	<p>One of the pathway that Maccabi uses to identify patients with suspected MCI is the physician’s visit. In particular, a typical channel is the visit that makes the geriatric evaluation and a general consultation. The physician can be GP that works in clinic or in the multidisciplinary centre or can be a specialist.</p> <p>Maccabi has recently launched a new program that aims to improve screening, early detection and intervention by GPs.</p> <p>The GP can explore specific recommendations in the doctor portal of DECI and ask the patient to perform online digital tests to detect MCI. The results of the tests, along with all medical information, will be available to the geriatric clinic staff. If test results require additional examination, the geriatric clinic or an occupational therapist will receive an alert containing the summary from the GP, to invite the patient for further assessment.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
<p>Detection of the patient with suspected CI</p>	<p>Once patients have been identified through the different types of screenings of the population or during a physician’s visit, their path continues in the care process. In Maccabi, both GPs, physicians of the multidisciplinary centre or External specialized physicians can recognize the main symptoms of cognitive impairment.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>

Basic Assessment	<p>In Maccabi, screening visits consist of physical examinations. A problem for the assessment is that the general practitioner usually has maximum 10 minutes per visit while the screening takes 45 minutes. Then, Maccabi decided to pay a special fee for the screening to GPs.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Comprehensive assessment	<p>If the screening is positive for MCI, the GP can refer the patient to a specialist for a comprehensive assessment in one of the following fields: geriatrics, neurology and psychiatry.</p> <p>The multidisciplinary teamwork is typically constituted by GPs, nurses, social workers, nutritionists, occupational therapists, dieticians, physiotherapists and psychiatrists that manage elderly and frail patients when needed. Those patients are referred to the CGA units, that are the units created for conducting a <i>Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment</i>.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
Diagnosis of CI	<p>The physicians are able to diagnose and treat the disease.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>

<p>Activation of preventive interventions</p>	<p>If the patient is affected by MCI, that for the time being do not need the activation of care services, the socio-health care provider delivers preventative interventions, workshops for memory and MCI related symptoms treatment, F2F visits homecare visits and training for physical exercise and cognitive exercise. In Maccabi they prove that an early treatment can have benefits on the progression of symptoms.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
<p>Needs identification</p>	<p>If the patient is affected by MCI, the socio-health care provider discusses the diagnosis with the patient and his family. In Israel, the family involvement is very important because the majority of elderly and frail people live at home (almost 95%) and the majority of treatments take place in the community.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists - Social worker <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
<p>Definition of the socio-health care service</p>	<p>Maccabi's teams provide, maintain and coordinate most of the social care services (according to organizational guidelines and to the national law) and they also contract some services with outside providers.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists - Social worker <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
<p>Phase</p>	<p>Service delivery and follow-up</p>
<p><i>Activity</i></p>	<p><i>Activity description</i></p>

<p>Integrated delivery of the socio-health care service</p>	<p>When patients are diagnosed with MCI, drug treatments are recommended to slow down the symptoms and to control behavioural problems. In Maccabi, many patients are treated by multidisciplinary homecare teams, that put their effort to be trained appropriately in order to address the wide range of patients' needs. Treatments for the psychological manifestations of Dementia are usually carried out outside Maccabi. In cases the patient remains at home, Maccabi offers a home care program to support the care at home and support the family.</p> <p>The DECI platform will support the communication with Communities.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists - Social worker - Home care teams - GP - Communities <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>
<p>Continuous patient follow-up</p>	<p>Treatments defined by the Maccabi's teams can be adjusted overtime. For example, when the patient's cognitive and functional condition declines, patients are contacted by the occupational therapist for further assessment and change of treatment.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geriatric multidisciplinary centre - OT centres - Specialists - GP <p><u>Information system:</u> EHR (DECI platform)</p>

Table 57 MAC TO-BE process description

3.4.3 FDG TO-BE process

Figure 23 FDG TO-BE process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the Italian pilot, the socio-health care provider of the AS-IS process model is represented by the Palazzolo Institute, centre of Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi Onlus, that offers care programs and integrated assistance services to older adults.

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Visit	<p>The meeting between patients and physicians can take place on a regular basis, like a check-up visit, or after an acute episode in a long term care facility.</p> <p>Physicians can be General Practitioners, External specialized physicians, or they can belong to the Palazzolo Institute.</p> <p>Note that at this stage, when the patient interacts with his/her General Practitioner or with a specialist, often he/she is not referred to a specialized service for the diagnosis of MCI or Dementia.</p> <p>The physician visualises the patient’s medical records on the DECI platform connected with the databases of local hospitals and GP.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Socio-health care provider – Specialists at FDG Palazzolo Institute - External specialized physicians <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WebHospital (FDG) - DECI platform
Detection of patients with suspected CI	<p>Physicians at the Palazzolo Institute, GPs or External specialized physicians should recognize the main symptoms of cognitive impairment.</p> <p>It could be that the GPs identify the patient with suspected MCI and perform the basic assessment, but it is also possible that they point out the patient to the Palazzolo Institute or to External specialized physicians to activate the assessment.</p>

	<p>Once patients with certain kind of characteristics have been identified during a physician’s visit, their path continues in the care process (see the Activity “Basic Assessment”).</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Socio-health care provider – Specialists at FDG Palazzolo Institute - External specialized physicians <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WebHospital (FDG) - DECI platform
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Basic Assessment	<p>In case there are symptoms of cognitive impairment, both General Practitioners, specialists at the Palazzolo Institute and External specialized physicians can perform the basic assessment. Note that usually the GP points out the patient to specialists (at the Palazzolo Institute or externally).</p> <p>This initial assessment consists of a basic examination of patients with suspected MCI or Dementia, aimed at understanding more than one perspective on patients’ health conditions, including also the social situation. In case the basic assessment strengthens the initial suspicion of cognitive impairment, a comprehensive assessment follows.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General practitioner - GP - Socio-health care provider – Specialists at FDG Palazzolo Institute - External specialized physicians <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WebHospital (FDG) - DECI platform
Comprehensive assessment	<p>The comprehensive assessment protocol for MCI and Dementia is a standardized protocol aimed at reaching a diagnosis as accurate as possible. At the Palazzolo Institute, for a comprehensive assessment, patients can be referred to</p>

	<p>a specialized geriatrics unit (e.g. the UVA - Unità Valutazione Alzheimer). GPs, other specialists or geriatricians in the Institute who saw the patient for another issue, can put patients in touch with the specialized unit. At this point, the unit starts the assessment protocol aimed at reaching the diagnosis (following activity).</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo Institute</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WebHospital, BI (FDG) - DECI platform
Diagnosis of CI	<p>Typically, a specialized geriatrics service (e.g. UVA) is responsible for the diagnosis of patients with MCI or Dementia (see the activity “Comprehensive Assessment”). All the data collected by the UVA are entered in a tablet and immediately shared (through a cloud service) with the other stakeholders of the care network.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo Institute</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WebHospital, BI (FDG) - DECI platform
Call to the patient for a follow-up	<p>Once diagnosis has been made, patients with MCI, that for the time being do not need the activation of care services, are followed-up at regular intervals or on demand, and they are properly trained. Patients are followed-up to monitor cognitive functions and reversible clinical conditions potentially associated with cognitive impairment.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo Institute</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WebHospital, BI (FDG) - DECI platform
Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>

<p>Needs identification</p>	<p>In Italy, it is common that patients’ relatives or caregivers take the responsibility for organizing the care pathway of their care receivers, depending on the progressive reduction of their autonomy. If patients are monitored by the UVA, the care pathway can be managed by PASS (“Punto di Accesso Socio-Sanitario”) and ST (“Servizi Territoriali”) through the activation of home-based and facility-based services, whose activation is discussed together with the family.</p> <p>It is possible that caregivers look for the assistance of formalized services in particular in case of patients’ clinical or functional deterioration, evolution of behavioural and psychological symptoms of Dementia, falls, malnutrition, dysphagia, etc. The domestic care system can also break down because of caregivers’ burnout or temporary unavailability.</p> <p>A first needs analysis can be performed by the patient/caregiver filling in on-line questionnaire on the DECI platform. Then a visit could confirm the results of the questionnaire.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – PASS and ST at FDG Palazzolo Institute</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web-Hospital, BI (only for PASS, ST has not a Web ERP) - DECI platform
<p>Definition of the socio-health care service</p>	<p>When patients are diagnosed with MCI or Dementia, if possible, it starts a pharmacological treatment with AChEI and a follow-up is scheduled. At this stage, for patients suffering from MCI or Dementia, the specialist of the UVA interacts with PASS and ST services to activate the required socio-health care services (e.g. home-care services, case-management or psychological counselling to caregivers). From 2015 there are two new home-care services offered to patients with dementia: ADI Demenza and RSA Aperta.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit, PASS and ST at FDG Palazzolo Institute</p>

	<p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web-Hospital, BI (only for UVA and PASS, ST has not a Web ERP) - DECI platform
Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
<p>Integrated delivery of the socio-health care service</p>	<p>The Palazzolo Institute delivers the health care and social care services defined, going also to patient's home to provide them.</p> <p>An assistance plan, making use of DECI solutions, is activated. For example, the following plan can be activated:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A wearable sensor could be used to detect abnormalities in the level of activity (e.g. immobility, fall) and send alert messages to family members and/or the ADI service; - The GP and specialists can share the information collected through the DECI platform and plan together a revision of the medication and treatment plan, and schedule visits. If needed, a short hospitalization (day hospital) can also be planned to perform analyses and diagnostic tests. The Alzheimer Evaluation Unit of the Palazzolo institute takes charge of the patient and coordinates the interventions. All the collected data are saved in the cloud server and included in the socio-clinical record of the patient. These data could be shared through GP and specialists to plan the necessary revision of the medication and treatment plan,; - A basic support service can be activated to help the patient in daily living activities; - The patient could monitor their medical parameters independently using a system that collects the data from the different medical devices (sphygmomanometer, glucometer, etc.), sends them to the electronic medical record, and automatically sends alerts to the ADI service and/or to caregivers in case of abnormal values.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - If needed a home rehabilitation program can be activated. The program can alternate sessions in physical presence of the physiotherapist with telerehabilitation sessions, where the therapist can make use of a sensor based system connected to the TV and to a webcam to follow the patient remotely. - The patient can be involved in the activities promoted by external services such as the church or the "Alzheimer Cafè" initiatives. - Some cognitive stimulation and rehabilitation exercises could be done also at home through the online platform. - The platform can also be used by the case manager to motivate the patients to follow their diet and medication plan. This could allow to reduce the frequency of face to face visits at home or in the ambulatory. - The platform also includes a calendar and an agenda of the visits and exams shared among all the actors. This allows the caregivers and families to be easier updated on their parents' health condition. <p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web-Hospital, BI - DECI platform - DECI activity monitoring device
<p>Continuous patient follow-up</p>	<p>During the service delivery the patient is continuously monitored by the professionals of the Institute. It is fundamental to verify the suitability of treatments, the presence of unexpected clinical events or the presence of new behavioural disturbance in everyday activities.</p> <p>The General Practitioner and specialists receive the information collected (through the online platform for patient management) and, if needed, plan together the revision of the medication and treatment plan.</p>

	<p><u>Main owner:</u> socio-health care provider – Specialized geriatric unit at FDG Palazzolo</p> <p><u>Information system:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Web-Hospital, BI - DECI platform
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Table 58 FDG AS-IS process description

3.4.4 VGR TO-BE process

Figure 24 VGR TO-BE process map

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

For the pilot in Sweden, the socio-health care provider of the AS-IS process model is represented by the Skaraborg Care Network (SCN) that includes all Primary Care Centres, 17 communities and the 4 hospitals at the Skaraborg Hospital Group (SHG). Please, note that the primary care physician is included in the Primary Care Centre.

Phase	Noticing symptoms and first detection
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Visit	<p>In Skaraborg, patients are usually visited in the Primary Care Centres or in the Hospitals.</p> <p>Patients could schedule their appointments only by sending a simple text message in the provided app.</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
Activation of periodical screening of the older population	<p>The process could be start, not only through the visit but also by reached out patients using campaigns in various media. Then, thanks to DECI platform, socio-health care providers could receive an automatic alert from the system based on selected information on the patient (e.g. age).</p> <p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DECI platform
Detection of patients with suspected CI	<p>Once patients with certain kind of characteristics have been identified during a doctor’s visit, the physician send a message to a specialized nurse of the Primary Care Centres or share all the information directly by DECI platform.</p>

	<p><u>Main owners:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
Phase	Assessment and diagnosis
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Basic assessment	<p>In Skaraborg, once the specialized nurses responsible for MCI and Dementia (ND) have received a message (from patients, patients' relatives, physicians, nurses, hospitals or the community) containing information about suspected patients, they contact patients and relatives within two weeks.</p> <p>At this point, the NDs perform a pre-visit, that would be followed by a more comprehensive assessment held by physicians (see the activity "Comprehensive Assessment").</p> <p>By DECI platform, the patient can share their concerns and their doubts about their symptoms in real-time. Primary Care Centres could send an online memory tests in form of a game executable also from home.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
Comprehensive assessment	<p>The Primary Care Centres are responsible for the first examination of patients with suspected MCI or Dementia.</p> <p>This initial examination involves different perspectives on the patients' current condition (including the social</p>

	<p>situation), that are available on DECI platform. In Skaraborg the initial assessment consists of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A structured anamnesis including interviews with nearest and dearest - An assessment of the physiological and psychological condition of the patient - Cognitive tests including MMT and the Clock test - A structured assessment of patient activities of daily life and level of activity <p>In addition, tests to include other conditions are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CT scan - neuropsychological tests - blood tests - liquor tests. <p>There could be an additional tests recommended by DECI program.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
<p>Diagnosis of CI</p>	<p>The Primary Care Centres are also responsible for the diagnosis of patients with suspected MCI or Dementia.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
<p>Call to the patient for a follow-up</p>	<p>At the Primary Care Centres, both the physician and the specialized nurse continuously monitor patients with MCI: at least yearly visits to the physician are planned, including a pre-visit to the nurse responsible for Dementia. Patients can also contact the specialized nurse at any time they need support. Note that the National Guidelines do not include a clinical pathway for patients with MCI, and interventions are decided on an individual basis.</p>

	<p>Thanks to DECI App, all the communications could be online, web-based, including also video calls.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
Phase	Treatment and care service definition
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
Needs identification	<p>If patients with MCI or Dementia get worse,, the aid assistance coordinator collaborates with families, professionals of the hospital and of the Primary Care Centres.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
Definition of the socio-health care service	<p>The aid assistance coordinator designs an individual care plan for the patient, and given the care plan, community care resources are made available for him/her, including basic home care.</p> <p>The care plan, including the visit, is documented in the EMR that is available to all the care providers. Also each patient has its own access to EMR usable by computer or by mobile app.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals - Communities <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform

Phase	Service delivery and follow-up
<i>Activity</i>	<i>Activity description</i>
<p>Integrated delivery of the socio-health care service</p>	<p>Cross-professional teams, under the management of the Municipality, provide basic and long-term care of patients affected by Dementia. The professional teams are led by the community Dementia nurse, that is a specialized nurse, supported by a general practitioner and the specialized nurse of the Primary Care Centre. In any case, the primary care physician has the overall medical responsibility for the patient.</p> <p>At Integrated Care Centre, there is a coordinator who handles all the healthcare services delivered by the various care providers for the family.</p> <p>The key elements of the plan are self-monitoring applications and web-based training, such as a language training.</p> <p>All the patient could be also connected to the Patients-Like-Me social network on the web, a forum for patients with MCI where it is possible to share experiences from living with the disease.</p> <p>There is available also a web-based appointments system to fix visits, also “at home visit”, and to monitor the follow-up plan.</p> <p>The patient could use the DECI app to get a physical exercise program or a cognitive game to stimulate the brain from the occupational therapist in the mobile care team. Information from the game is automatically sent to the occupational therapist through the app and the therapist gives to each patient continuous feedback regarding exercises.</p> <p>The GPS-technology unit, which can be worn with regular watch, carries geo-fencing possibilities and functionalities such as marking different locations important for everyday life - a grocery store, pharmacy, etc. This watch can also give notification</p>

	<p>to other caregivers when the patient leaves predetermined geographical zones.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Primary Care Centres - Hospitals - Communities <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local Information system - DECI platform
<p>Continuous patient follow-up</p>	<p>During the service delivery the patient is continuously monitored by Primary Care Centres.</p> <p>Through a web-based appointments system it's possible to fix visits, also "at home visit", and to monitor the follow-up plan.</p> <p>All patients connected to the DECI platform are monitored and all data are available for the nurse.</p> <p>By filling in a questionnaire regarding their health status, all patients are monitored.</p> <p>The communication among patients and all physicians is easy and efficient thanks to a video call and also a fast feedback to an app games.</p> <p><u>Main owner:</u> Primary Care Centres</p> <p><u>Information System:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - DECI platform

Table 59 VGR AS-IS process description

3.4.5 TO-BE processes: an overall view

The main differences from the AS-IS processes concern the fourth macro-phase "Service delivery and follow up". Only VGR will introduce a periodical screening in the first macro-phase "Noticing symptoms and first detection" and only HUG will improve the activity of the "Definition of health care/social care services" in the macro-phase "Treatment and care service definition". This focus on the last part of the flow is also caused by the type of technological solutions that are mainly directed to the home assistance.

The proposed solutions have all a great impact on the patient's social inclusion, because they put the patient at the centre of the care network, allowing a continuous communication between each care actors to each other and to the patient and their family/caregiver. Thanks to these integrated solutions, each patient will be never excluded from the care and the social network.

Please, notice that these TO-BE process models, above described, are the processes desired by each pilot site. To value the feasibility of those hypothesized scenarios, it's important to have a mutual comparison with the institutional members of socio-health care system (e.g. General Practitioners) to jointly evaluate the effective feasible scenarios in the DECI project contest.

In the task T3.4 "Design of different implementation settings", all the effective feasible scenarios of the process models will be identified and thoroughly described.

4 Preliminary Assessment of the Impact of the Business Model on All Involved Environments

With the aim to monitor the performances related to the delivery processes, and to analyze the benefits associated with the development of DECI solution, a dedicated analysis has been performed starting from preliminary elements from WP6 “Evaluation of business, industrial and quality impacts”, where the full set of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) will be described, monitored and implemented.

From the starting point of the Key Functionalities (both Country-specific and common among Countries ones) described in Chapter 2.2 and Chapter 2.3 and of the process phases described in Chapter 3, the first tool developed to assess the impact is the Impact Matrix (IM). This tool allows to consider the links among the following dimensions: (i) Country-specific and common among Countries Key Functionalities; (ii) Phases of the care process; (iii) Categories of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

It is a $s_p \times t \times u$ matrix where (Table 60):

$$imp_{e_p.f.g} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if Functionality } e_p \text{ has an impact on the Phase } f \text{ AND it} \\ & \text{can be assessed through the category } g \text{ of the KPIs} \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$e_p = 1_p, 2_p, \dots, s_p$$

$$f = 1, 2, \dots, t$$

$$g = 1, 2, \dots, u$$

$$p = \begin{cases} \text{Israel} \\ \text{Italy} \\ \text{Spain} \\ \text{Sweden} \end{cases}$$

Table 60 – Impact Matrix

	KPI ₁	KPI ₁	KPI ₁	KPI ₁	KPI ₂	KPI ₂	KPI ₂	KPI ₂	...	KPI _u	KPI _u	KPI _u	KPI _u
	Phase ₁	Phase ₂	...	Phase _t	Phase ₁	Phase ₂	...	Phase _t	...	Phase ₁	Phase ₂	...	Phase _t
Functionality_{1p}	<i>imp_{1p.1.1}</i>	<i>imp_{1p.2.1}</i>	...	<i>imp_{1p.t.1}</i>	<i>imp_{1p.1.2}</i>	<i>imp_{1p.2.2}</i>	...	<i>imp_{1p.t.2}</i>	...	<i>imp_{1p.1.u}</i>	<i>imp_{1p.2.u}</i>	...	<i>imp_{1p.t.u}</i>
Functionality_{2p}	<i>imp_{2p.1.1}</i>	<i>imp_{2p.2.1}</i>	...	<i>imp_{2p.t.1}</i>	<i>imp_{2p.1.2}</i>	<i>imp_{2p.2.2}</i>	...	<i>imp_{2p.t.2}</i>	...	<i>imp_{2p.1.u}</i>	<i>imp_{2p.2.u}</i>	...	<i>imp_{2p.t.u}</i>
...
Functionality_{sp}	<i>imp_{sp.1.1}</i>	<i>imp_{sp.2.1}</i>	...	<i>imp_{sp.t.1}</i>	<i>imp_{sp.1.2}</i>	<i>imp_{sp.2.2}</i>	...	<i>imp_{sp.t.2}</i>	...	<i>imp_{sp.1.u}</i>	<i>imp_{sp.2.u}</i>	...	<i>imp_{sp.t.u}</i>

The focus is on the impact of the common or Country-specific key Functionalities. The total number of these Functionalities per Country is represented by the variable e_p . In each Country, the Boolean variable $imp_{e_p.f.g}$ allows to identify the trios Key Functionality-Phase-Category of KPI that will be further analyzed in WP6. Also these elements can be Country-specific or common among Countries.

The main KPI categories that will be considered for the analysis are the following:

- Patient;
- Staff;

- Organization;
- Cost (economic feasibility).

The 4 process phases considered are the following:

- Noticing symptoms and first detection;
- Assessment and diagnosis;
- Treatment and care service definition;
- Service delivery and follow-up.

Subsequently, the IM is further particularized through the Clusters of Key Functionalities described in Chapter 0 and it drives to the definition of the Cluster Impact Matrix (CIM). CIM is characterized by the x-axis related to the process phases, the y-axis related to the 4 categories of KPI and the cells are filled by the various Clusters of Functionalities. Furthermore, it distinguishes between Country-Specific and Common among Countries Clusters (Table 61).

Table 61 – Cluster Impact Matrix structure

	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up
Patient	Patient layer Cluster 1 Cluster 2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			
	Overall system layer Cluster n+1 Cluster n+2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			
Staff	Patient layer Cluster 1 Cluster 2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			
	Overall system layer Cluster n+1 Cluster n+2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			
Organization	Patient layer Cluster 1 Cluster 2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			
	Overall system layer Cluster n+1 Cluster n+2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			
Cost (Economic feasibility)	Patient layer Cluster 1 Cluster 2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			
	Overall system layer Cluster n+1 Cluster n+2 ... Cluster n Country-Specific Cluster			

CIM provides a general model useful to assess the impact of the digital solutions that will be developed in the 4 pilot sites. In order to synthesize the findings and to facilitate readings comprehension the paragraph Chapter 4 will mainly present the analysis through this level of detail, while the IM and the related spreadsheet with the full list of Functionalities (i.e. functionalities that are not clustered) will be attached.

Finally, the same elements are analyzed in terms of the match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (i.e. numbers of notable

crossings) for each Country. It allows to highlight the pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs that are not covered by any Cluster of Functionalities, Country-specific peculiarities and the trios Cluster of Functionalities-Process Phase-Category of KPIs that are characterized by the highest matching (Table 62).

Table 62 – Country specific CIM Structure

	Patient	Patient	Patient	Patient	Staff	Staff	Staff	Staff	Organization	Organization	Organization	Organization	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	KPI
Patient layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Patient's status (Monitoring)																	
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive)																	
Patient's status (Alert)																	
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)																	
Patient's activities (Alert)																	
Patient's activities (Monitoring)																	
Overall system layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Care providers																	
Care providers (teamwork)																	
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)																	
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)																	

- High match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs

This Chapter shows the results of the preliminary assessment of the DECI Service Model in the 4 pilot settings. Through the adoption of the CIM (Table 63) it was possible to highlight:

- Clusters of Functionalities that are characterized by a relevant potential impact on the various pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs;
- Pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs that are not covered by any Cluster of Functionality;
- Country-Specific Clusters of Functionalities characterized by a relevant potential impact on some pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs.

Regarding the points 1 and 3, the high relevance for the Swedish pilot site of the category of need “Detection” (

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Detection	Patient detection	Reactive detection	4			4	0	0	5	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
		Proactive search I (Database parameters)	4			4	0	0	5	3
		Proactive search II (75th birthday)	4			0	0	0	4	3
Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical	Clinical diagnosis	5		5	5	0	0	5	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Overall medical condition	5		5	5	5	5	4	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Medical instability	0		3	4	0	0	0	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Psychological	Behavior and mood	5		5		5	5	5	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Anosognosia	0		2	2	1	1	0	0
Diagnosis and assessment	Physical	Assess the Risk of malnutrition	5		5	5	5	5	3	5
Diagnosis and assessment	Functional	ADL	5		5	5	5	5	3	5
Diagnosis and assessment		risk for falls	5		5	5	5	5	3	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Diagnosis and assessment		Frailty	5		5	5	5	5	4	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Socio economic	Assess Socio economic state	5		5	5			5	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Caregiver burden	Assess Caregiver burden	5		5	5	5	5	2	4
Patient environmental needs	The person might not have an adequate and appropriate home	Assuring suitable living space	1		1	2	0	0	4	4
Patient environmental needs	The person might have problems keeping their home tidy and organized	Assuring maintenance of living space	3				3	5	2	3
Patient environmental needs	Buy food	Shopping assistant	2		3		3	4	2	4
Patient environmental needs	Eat in a safe way	Malnutrition avoidance	2		4		3	5	2	3
Patient environmental needs	Patients not able to keep track of their expenses	Money budgeting	3		2	1	3	5	3	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient environmental needs	Caring for someone else	Caring for someone else	1		0	0	1	0	4	4
Patient environmental needs	Wandering expose people to dangers	tracking / prevent wandering	0		1	3	0	4	0	0
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information about the disease, symptoms and evolution	4		5	5	1	0	4	4
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information on current condition and treatment	4		5	5	2	2	4	4
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their	The patient can contact a health professional for questioning	4		3	3	0	0	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
	condition and treatment in a language they can understand									
Patient physical needs	People might need support for designing a physical activity plan	Physical activity plan and exercise	4		5	5	2	1	4	4
Patient physical needs	Drugs (chronic disease management)	Education on side-effects on medication treatment by clinical pharmacologist or clinical team coordinated by case manager	4		4	4	0	0	4	4
Patient physical needs	Have a prescription by general practitioner	Medication plan	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Patient physical needs	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions	Medication Reminders	4		4	4	5	5	4	5
Patient physical needs	Eyesight/hearing/Communication		0				3	2	2	2

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient physical needs	People can have high risk of fall	Fall detection	3		3	4	3	5	3	4
Patient physical needs	People need to be able to move	Immobility detection	3		3	3	3	5	3	4
Patient physical needs	Keeping neat and tidy	education, follow-up	2		2	2	3	5	2	2
Patient physical needs	Continence		0		1	1	1	4	0	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Access to non-pharmacological treatment	4		4	5	5	5	4	5
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Alternative treatments	4		4	4	3	3	4	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Brief psychotherapies	4		4	4	0	0	4	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Psychopharmacological treatment	0		0	0	0	0	3	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Remote monitoring of psychological status	4		5	5	2	2	3	3
Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Cognitive stimulation	5		5	5	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Patient psychological needs	Alcohol abuse prevention	Alcohol abuse prevention	3		3	3	3	0	3	3
Patient psychological needs	inadvertent self-harm		1		1	1	0	1	0	0
Patient psychological needs	deliberate self-harm		0				0	1	0	0
Patient psychological needs	Psychotic symptoms	Monitoring hallucinations or delusions	0		3	4	3	4	4	4
Patient Social needs	Patient refuses help and sociality outside home / lives alone in an isolated house / does not have partners	social interaction	0		3	3	3	3	3	3
Patient Social needs	Intimate relationship		0		0	0	0	0	1	1

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient Social needs	The person might not have relatives / friends / etc. With whom realising social activities	Recommendation of social activities	1		2	2	1	2	3	4
Patient Social needs	People with cognitive problems might have problems with other people that might take advantage of their condition (i.e. using their money)	Abuse/Neglect prevention	1		1	2	0	2	2	2
Patient general needs	People might not be aware of available social services	information of the social benefits available in the area	4		4	4	3	4	4	4
Patient general needs	People are not able to contact social services or social workers	Patients can contact the social worker	4		4	4	2	0	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	2	0	4	4
Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Discuss financial and long-term care plans	4		4	4	1	0	4	4
Clinical team needs	Coordinated care	Coordination of care	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Information sharing	Clinical team information sharing	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Improve diagnosis method	Improve diagnosis method	5		5	5	*	*	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Advising on deciding course of action	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Standardized care pathway	5		5	5	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Clinical team needs	Accessibility	Facilitating access to medical services in rural/ isolated areas	3		2	3	0	0	5	5
Clinical team needs	Longitudinal treatment	comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy+ follow-up	5		5	5	3	3	5	5
Social care team needs	Information sharing	Health team information sharing (including social care)	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Social care team needs	Information sharing	To improve social awareness about the disease	4		5	5	3	3	5	5
Social care team needs	Information sharing	To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources	4		5	5	5	5	5	5
Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate access to social services in rural/ isolated areas	3		3	3	0	0	4	4
Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate and to speed up access to social services (Day Centres, Night Centres, etc.)	3		3	3	5	5	3	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5		3	3	5	5
Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Monitoring of cognitive condition	5		5		3	3	5	5
Follow up	overall condition	monitoring overall condition	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Follow up	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions / ensure adherence	measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Follow up	social care	Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Caregivers needs	Physical and psychological monitoring of the caregiver	Interventions with the caregiver	4		4	4	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease	4		5	5	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the secondary effects of medication	4		4	4	3	3	4	4
Caregivers needs	Communication healthcare prof. - NFC	The caregiver can ask questions to the health professional	4		3	3	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about available social services in the area	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	3	3		

Table 68

- Appendix) justifies all the Country-specific results regarding the Process Phase of Noticing symptoms and first detection, while the high relevance of the Drug Management of the Italian pilot site explains the Country-specific Cluster “Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)” for various pairs Process Phase-Category of KPIs. Other two relevant Country-specific Clusters i.e. Patient’s Status (Monitoring) and Patient’s Activities (Monitoring) are also related to the Italian context.

Regarding the point 2, only the pair Noticing symptoms and first detection-Organization has not any Cluster of Functionalities.

Table 63 – Results of the Cluster Impact Matrix

	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up
Patient	Patient layer Patient's activities (Alert) SWEDEN	Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Monitoring) Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring)	Patient layer Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation) Patient's status (Monitoring) Overall system layer Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring) ITALY	Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Communication-cognitive stimulation) Patient's status (Monitoring) ITALY Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring) ITALY Overall system layer Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring) ITALY
Staff	Patient layer Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) SWEDEN Patient's activities (Alert) SWEDEN	Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Monitoring) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring) Overall system layer Care providers (Communication) Care providers (Teamwork) Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)	Patient layer Patient's status (Monitoring) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Overall system layer Care providers (Communication) Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information) Care providers (Teamwork)	Patient layer Patient's status (Monitoring) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring) Overall system layer Care providers (Teamwork)
Organization		Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Monitoring) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring)	Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Overall system layer Care providers (Communication) Care providers (Teamwork) Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring) Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)	Patient layer Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring) Overall system layer Care providers (Teamwork) Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring) ITALY
Cost (Economic feasibility)	Patient layer Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) SWEDEN Patient's activities (Alert) SWEDEN	Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Monitoring) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring)	Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Monitoring) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Overall system layer Care providers (Communication) Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring) ITALY	Patient layer Patient's status (Alert) Patient's status (Storage and sharing information) Patient's activities (Alert) Patient's activities (Monitoring) Overall system layer Care providers (Teamwork) Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring) ITALY

Further details for the four Pilot sites and regarding the number of Clusters of Key Functionalities for each pair Process Phase-Category of KPIs are showed in the following Tables (Table 64 - Table 65 - Table 66 - Table 67) .

Table 64 – Italian CIM

	Patient	Patient	Patient	Patient	Staff	Staff	Staff	Staff	Organization	Organization	Organization	Organization	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	KPI
Patient layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Patient's status (Monitoring)		6	1	1		5	2	2		2				4	1		
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive)			1	2				1							1	1	
Patient's status (Alert)		1		1		1				1	1			1	1	1	
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)						5	3	2		4	3	1		4	2	2	
Patient's activities (Alert)		1		4		2		2		1		2		2		5	
Patient's activities (Monitoring)		3		1		2	1	1		1		1		3		1	
Overall system layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Care providers						1	1			1	1			1	1		
Care providers (teamwork)						1	1	1		1	1	1					
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)			1	1				1			1	1				1	1
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)						1	1			1	1						

- High match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs

Table 65 – Swedish CIM

	Patient	Patient	Patient	Patient	Staff	Staff	Staff	Staff	Organization	Organization	Organization	Organization	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	KPI
Patient layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Patient's status (Monitoring)		5	1			5	2	1		2				4	1		
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive)			1	2				1							1	1	
Patient's status (Alert)		1		1		1				1	1			1	1	1	
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)					1	5	3	2		4	3	1	1	4	2	2	
Patient's activities (Alert)	1	1		4	1	2		2		1		2	1	2		5	
Patient's activities (Monitoring)		3				2	1	1		1		1		3		1	
Overall system layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Care providers						1	1			1	1			1	1		
Care providers (teamwork)						1	1	1		1	1	1					
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)											1						
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)						1	1			1	1						

- High match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs

Table 66 – Spanish CIM

	Patient	Patient	Patient	Patient	Staff	Staff	Staff	Staff	Organization	Organization	Organization	Organization	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	KPI
Patient layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Patient's status (Monitoring)		5	1			5	2	1						4	1		
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive)			1	2				1								1	1
Patient's status (Alert)		1		1		1				1	1			1	1	1	
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)						5	3	2		4	3	1		4	2	2	
Patient's activities (Alert)		1		4		2		2		1		2		2		5	
Patient's activities (Monitoring)		3				2	1	1		1		1		3		1	
Overall system layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Care providers						1	1				1			1	1		
Care providers (teamwork)						1	1	1		1	1	1					
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)											1						
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)						1	1			1	1						

- High match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs

Table 67 – Israeli CIM

	Patient	Patient	Patient	Patient	Staff	Staff	Staff	Staff	Organization	Organization	Organization	Organization	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	Cost (economic feasibility)	KPI
Patient layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Patient's status (Monitoring)		5	1			5	2	1		2				4	1		
Patient's status (Communication-cognitive)			1	2				1								1	1
Patient's status (Alert)		1		1		1				1	1			1	1	1	
Patient's status (Storage and sharing information)						5	3	2		4	3	1		4	2	2	
Patient's activities (Alert)		1		2		2		2		1		2		2		3	
Patient's activities (Monitoring)		3				2	1	1		1		1		3		1	
Overall system layer	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Noticing symptoms and first detection	Assessment and diagnosis	Treatment and care service definition	Service delivery and follow-up	Phase
Care providers						1	1				1			1	1		
Care providers (teamwork)						1	1	1		1	1	1					
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Monitoring)											1						
Care pathway/Treatment plan (Sharing information)						1	1			1	1						

- High match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- Weak match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs (n° of notable crossings)
- No match between Clusters of Key Functionalities, Process Phases and Categories of KPIs

5 Conclusions

This Chapter synthesizes the outputs generated through the previous chapters, provides an overview of the implications of these outcomes and a link with the rest of the tasks characterizing the project.

The deliverable describes four main outputs:

1. It provides a scalable, solid and general framework, which can be exploited also in context different from the ones in which DECI pilots will be accomplished;
2. It identifies and assess the feasibility of key service packages to be delivered in DECI, which are useful for the following phases associated to pilot design;
3. It provides a care processes model and describes as-is and to-be care processes in the 4 pilot settings;
4. It offers insights about the potential impact of the various key service packages identified, in order to estimate the area of benefits that DECI project could impact.

In the rest of the chapter, we will briefly outline these outputs.

5.1 *A Scalable, Solid and General Framework*

The framework (Figure 25) adopted and developed to carry out the research is relevant because:

- It allows to combine and link all the information from the other previous DECI documents putting together various elements (e.g. context-specific aspects, needs, technological functionalities, etc.);
- It adopts a spreadsheet (attached to this document) that allows to collect all the relevant information and the knowledge generated;
- It adopts already established frameworks (e.g. Business Model Canvas, Business Model Environment, etc.);
- It highlights the common traits among the Countries within the DECI project and the differences among them from many viewpoints;
- It allows to distinguish firstly between coherent and not coherent elements, then between high-priority and low-priority ones;
- It provides information about the impact of the various digital solutions;
- It is applicable in other contexts (i.e. Countries) therefore it can potentially overcome the boundaries of the DECI project thanks to its scalability;
- It has the potential to support decision-making processes also after the pilot phases because, once the first most relevant needs are addressed, it will be possible to proceed with the Actions to address the needs with a lower relevance.

Most of the previous points are enabled by the aforementioned spreadsheet that is therefore characterized by high flexibility in terms of time, contents and context considered. It provides information that can be updated over time – once a need is addressed, his related priority can be lowered, and therefore the focus can be on other Actions – in order to be always a support for decision makers about the prioritization

of the development of Functionalities. It easily allows extending the scope of the analysis also to other Countries for which the only required data are related to contextual elements and the relevance of the Actions to address the needs for the various clusters of patients.

Figure 25 - Methodological model

Furthermore, the framework was validated and refined also through the 4 Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) meetings organized in the Countries in which the pilots will take place. Every SAB meeting is characterized by the involvement of the following key figures:

- **Academics:** to assess the methodological robustness and rigor;
- **Practitioners:** that are experts in the treatment of Cognitive Impairment, to assess the validity of the findings;
- **Technology providers:** to assess the feasibility from the point of view of the groups of functionalities selected in each pilot site.

Finally, the framework provides not only a flexible and scalable tool but it also suggests an effective usage of it in order to support the definition and implementation of a comprehensive and multifaceted business model in a complex and continuously evolving context.

5.2 Assessment and Feasibility of Key Service Packages

Trying to describe the BM in all his details and to link all the terms within it before the design and implementation of the pilots is overambitious and can be considered an absurd pretention. Nevertheless, the simplification carried out through the DECI Service Model and its service packages allows to lead and support the decision-making process regarding the design and implementation of the aforementioned pilots. Therefore, a further and detailed description of the BM can be done only after the choices regarding the specific service packages that decision makers want to select and then implement in their Countries.

Additionally, the assessment of the feasibility of these service packages constitutes a further support for decision making processes. As an example, it is an information that could be used during the change management process to demonstrate that the solution is implementable therefore to face possible barriers to the change.

The two levels of detail provided through BM_{Canvases} and DECI Service Model support the pilot design phase because they allow to take into account all the possible alternatives/elements that can affect the implementation of the various pilots and their effectiveness. Furthermore, they ensure the coherence among all the numerous variables and aspects of the BM and sustain decision makers in linking the various building blocks of BMC.

Finally, the different service packages enable a detailed design of the various pilot projects and they enclose the information about their key relevance in order to rationalize the effort made for each pilot project.

5.3 A Care Process Model

The analysis performed within T3.2, aimed to define the TO-BE process and organizational models, have allowed to design a home care general model from a service provider perspective, and then to specialize it in different pilot sites.

As reported in the paragraphs above, the designed TO-BE process models are the processes desired by each pilot site. To value the feasibility of those hypothesized scenarios, it is important to have a mutual comparison with the institutional members of socio-health care system (e.g. General Practitioners) to jointly evaluate the effective feasible scenarios in the DECI project contest. In the task T3.4 “Design of different implementation settings”, all the effective feasible scenarios of the process models will be identified and thoroughly described.

5.4 A Preliminary Analysis of Project Impacts

DECI Service Model and its service packages have the potential to impact various process phases from various perspectives (i.e. patient, staff, organization and costs). The analysis regarding these aspects is valuable for who will develop the pilots because it provides preliminary suggestions about the outcomes that could be

reached through the implementation of all the various service packages and about the aspects that will be monitored and assessed, also through a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The set of Functionalities and Actions to address the needs helps in understanding how the related service packages will affect the various pilot projects and it steers their design and development.

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7 Annex

7.1 Business Model Environment

7.1.1 Business Model Environment for Italy

Macro Area	Key context variable	Italy
Key trends	National Socio-Health care System overview	<p>Socio-health care is provided by the National Socio-Health care System, which is composed by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the National Healthcare System, that provides citizens with health care services; • the Welfare System, that provides citizens with social care services and consists of all organizations, people and actions whose primary intent is to integrate all possible resources to prevent, eliminate, or reduce conditions of hardship, economic or social difficulties, not self-sufficiency and disability.
	General government expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	77,30%
	Private expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	22,70%

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

	Out-of-pocket expenditure as a percentage of private expenditure on health	82,80%
	Per capita total expenditure on health (PPP int. \$)	2.438
Macro-economic forces	Payment mechanisms	<p>Payment rates for hospital and outpatient care are determined by each region, with national rates (determined by the Ministry of Health) as a reference. More specifically, payment for hospital care (ordinary and day hospital treatments) is based on DRG tariffs.</p> <p>Reimbursement for outpatient specialist care, diagnostic services and imaging is based on tariffs defined by unit of service. Specialist/ambulatory care is generally provided by local health authorities or by public and private accredited hospitals under contractual agreement with a local health authority.</p> <p>Primary/ambulatory care is managed by GPs and is paid via a combination of capitation and fee-for-service, sometimes related to performance, and is regulated under national and regional contracts.</p>
	Sources of revenue and financial flow	<p>The healthcare system is funded from general taxation.</p> <p>The main source of finance for the Italian SSN is a mix of taxes applied at both regional and national level. Thus, collection is performed partially at national and partially at regional level (IRPEF), although pooling of funds is managed at national level (IRAP, VAT).</p>
Industry force	Public VS Private	The National Socio-Healthcare System has a universal and solidarity nature (Beveridge model). In this model, health is considered a fundamental right of all citizens, who are entitled to make use of all the services established at national level.

	<p>Centralization VS Decentralization</p>	<p>Italy's health-care system is a regionally organized National Health Service.</p> <p>The National Healthcare System and the Welfare System make use of three different fundamental tools for managing the care system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The National Plan of care services that the Governing Body prepares every three years and that identifies general addresses and criteria. • The Regional Plans establish the integration between health and social care services in line with the Regional Health Plan goals. • The Local Plans define, design and implement interventions that compose the overall offer of socio-health care services provided by public or private subjects. <p>Regions are autonomous in managing and defining their care services: in this sense, different regions have made different choices on how to use their autonomy. The regional differences in policies and financing, a large vertical fragmentation exists in the extent and the quality of such strategies between regions.</p>
	<p>Actors involved</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National level: the national Government, through the Ministry of Health, takes the lead in health-care planning, including the definition of the benefit package (LEAs), and the setting of long-term goals, financing - with the distribution of available funds to the regional health systems - and monitoring of the SSN. • Regional level: the 19 Regions and 2 Autonomous Provinces share planning and financing responsibilities with the central government in the State-Regions Conference, and are exclusively responsible for delivering public health and health-care services through their regional health-care systems. Each region, through its elected Regional Council, carries out legislative activity, for example: general principles and organization of the regional health-care system and criteria for financing public and private health-care providers. • Local level: within each region, responsibility for the organization and delivery of services rests on geographically and population-defined institutions, the Local Healthcare Authority (in Italy called

		ASL), that has the role of manager, and in some cases even of regulator, of health care and social care services (only for the hygiene performance of the patient).
	Health and social care integration	<p>The multiplicity of actors and services involved in the process of patient care and the increasing joint demand of health care and social care services, provided respectively by the Local Health Authorities and the Municipalities with the related care service providers, necessitate a continuous link between the different actors and services. However, in the Italian National Socio-Health Care System, patients and their caregivers often play the role of connector between the health care and social care realities. The main actors involved are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality: has the role of manager of social care services and in some cases of leader authority of the associated management between the municipalities in relation to social care services. • Care service provider: is the actor that usually delivers the socio-health care services managed by the Local Health Authority and/or the social care services managed by the Municipality, when these actors cannot manage the delivery. <p>At the regulatory national level, there is an increasing drive towards integration between Local Health Authority and Municipality, and consequently between health care and social care services. Although inside the Italian National Socio-Health care System there are many initiatives of integration, there is still not an effective and complete socio-health care integration: indeed, the health and social care actors rarely communicate with each other.</p>
	Hospitals (per 100.000 population)	2,1
	Psychiatric beds (per million population)	44,5
Market	Population aged > 60 years (%)	27%

	Life expectancy at age 60 (years)	25
	Estimated prevalence of dementia per 1.000 population	2015: 21,8 2035: 31,4
	Population living in urban areas (%)	69%
	Population IT readiness (%)	89%
	Tendency to Informal Care (%)	68%

7.1.2 Business Model Environment for Sweden

Macro Area	Key context variable	Sweden
Key trends	National Socio-Health care System overview	In Sweden, as in many other countries in the European Union, the health care needs of all legally registered citizens are covered by the state. The Government and the Parliament have the overall political responsibility for healthcare, while 20 counties/regions and 290 municipalities bear the operational responsibility for citizens' care.
	General government expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	81,30%

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

	Private expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	18,70%
	Out-of-pocket expenditure as a percentage of private expenditure on health	88,10%
	Per capita total expenditure on health (PPP int. \$)	3.284
Macro-economic forces	Payment mechanisms	<p>The Swedish health care system is integrated to a high degree. The county councils are responsible for both the financing and organization of health care services. There are few private hospitals, and the number of private primary care providers varies widely between the county councils. In some urban county councils, up to 60% of the primary care providers may be private, whereas in other county councils only a few private providers can be found. The same variation in the public/private mix of providers can be found across the municipalities.</p> <p>It is up to each county council to decide on the mechanisms for paying providers and therefore methods vary across the country. In hospital care, a mix of payment mechanisms is used across the country. Often, fixed prospective per-case payments (based on DRGs), complemented with price or volume ceilings and quality components are used. The use of DRGs and other classification systems for payment varies among regions and county councils.</p> <p>For private practitioners to be reimbursed by the county council they need to have an agreement with the county.</p>

	Sources of revenue and financial flow	The regions and municipalities have a mandate to tax the population through employee and employer salary-based taxes. Both the county councils and the municipalities levy proportional income taxes on the population to cover the services that they provide. The principle of local self-government means that the county councils and regions may design and structure their activities with reference to local conditions. The county councils and the municipalities also generate income through state grants and user charges.
Industry forces	Public VS Private	According to the Health and Medical Services Act, the Swedish system provides coverage for all residents of Sweden, regardless of nationality. In addition, emergency coverage is provided to all patients from the EU and European Economic Area countries, and nine other countries with which Sweden has bilateral agreements. The services available are highly subsidized and some services are provided free of charge.
	Centralization VS Decentralization	The Swedish health care system is organized into three levels: the national, regional and local. The responsibility for health care services is divided between the state, county councils/regions and municipalities. The Health and Medical Services Act specifies that the responsibility for ensuring that everyone living in Sweden has access to good health care lies with the county councils/regions and municipalities. The Act is designed to give county councils and municipalities considerable freedom with regard to the organization of their health services. The state, through the Ministry of Health and Social Affairs (Socialdepartementet), is responsible for overall health care policies.
	Actors involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National level: The Ministry of Health and Social Affairs works to meet the objectives set by the Riksdag in the area of health care, health and social issues/insurance. This includes people's financial security, social services, health care, public health and the rights of children and people with disabilities. There are eight government agencies directly involved in the area of health, medical care and public health: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The National Board of Health and Welfare is a large government agency, engaged in a wide range of activities in the areas of social services, health care services, environmental health, communicable disease prevention and epidemiology. - The HSAN is a government agency that decides on disciplinary measures in the event of complaints

		<p>or possible malpractice.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The primary objective of the SBU is to promote the use of cost-effective health care technologies. - The MPA is the Swedish national authority responsible for the regulation and surveillance of the development, manufacture and sale of drugs and other medicinal products. - The TLV works has the primary task of deciding if a medicine or medicinal product should be subsidized and included in the pharmaceutical benefits scheme. - The Swedish Agency for Health and Care Services Analysis analyse and evaluate implemented measures and the availability of information within the sphere of health and care service policy from the perspective of citizens and patients. - National Institute for Public Health promote health and prevent diseases by providing the government, government agencies, municipalities and county councils with knowledge based on scientific evidence. - Swedish Social Insurance Agency is the authority that administers the various types of insurance and benefits that make up social insurance in Sweden. • Regional level: At the regional level, the structure of care can be divided into primary care, district county council care and regional care. • Municipal level: The responsibilities of a municipality include issues relating to the immediate environment of the citizens, for example social welfare services.
	<p>Health and social care integration</p>	<p>The responsibility for means testing, and the financing and organization of long-term care services for older people and providing support to people with disabilities lies with the municipalities: patients who have been fully medically treated and have been discharged from emergency care or geriatric hospitals also fall within the remit of the municipalities. There are both public and private nursing homes and home care providers.</p> <p>The Social Services Act is a framework law emphasizing the right of individuals to receive municipal services. It specifies that older people have the right to receive public services and help at all stages of life. In addition, older and disabled people are normally entitled to subsidized transport to health care</p>

		<p>facilities. Problems with coordination of care for older people have been on the agenda for many years and several efforts towards solving this issue have been made: the national government introduced a national action plan for the strengthening of primary care, psychiatric care and care for older people.</p> <p>At the local government level, several county councils initiated reform projects in the early 2000s focusing on the development of community services, that is, locally organized and provided services that should respond to the needs for common preventive and curative services for the population. The idea of community services developed in different directions across county councils: in some county councils, the reforms focused on a new role for smaller hospitals. In other county councils, the reforms focused more on the need to develop primary care in order to improve the care for older people and for patients with chronic diseases.</p>
	Hospitals (per 100.000 population)	0,8
	Psychiatric beds (per million population)	45
Market forces	Population aged > 60 years (%)	26%
	Life expectancy at age 60 (years)	24
	Estimated prevalence of dementia per 1.000 population	2015: 18,5 2035: 24,9
	Population living in urban areas (%)	86%
	Population IT readiness (%)	93%

	Tendency to Informal Care (%)	14%
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7.1.3 Business Model Environment for Spain

Macro Area	Key context variable	Spain
Key trends	National Socio-Health care System overview	The Spanish National Health System (SNHS) is universal coverage-wise, almost fully funded from taxes and predominantly within the public sector. After a 25-year transition from a centralized model of legislation, and planning and provision of health services, health competences were totally devolved to the regional level (AC) from the end of 2002; this devolution resulted in 17 regional ministries or departments of health with primary jurisdiction over the organization and delivery of health services within their territory, thus health expenditure is mainly determined by the regional administrations.
	General government expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	71,70%
	Private expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	28,30%
	Out-of-pocket expenditure as a percentage of private expenditure on health	77,10%

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

	Per capita total expenditure on health (PPP int. \$)	2.098
Macro-economic forces	Payment mechanisms	Hospitals are normally funded through a global budget, set against individual spending headings. The trend has evolved to a DRG-like system. Regarding GPs, the most common formula for family doctors includes salary plus a capitation component (amounting to about 15% of the total), which takes into account the nature of the population registered with them, its density and the percentage of the population over 65 years of age.
	Sources of revenue and financial flow	The system is funded through taxes: healthcare provision is free of charge at the point of delivery, with the exception of some pharmaceuticals, which are charged with a percentage co-payment, adjusted on age and dependency. Private Voluntary Insurance (PVI) plays a minor function in the Spanish healthcare system, and it is mostly used for specific specialties such as Dental Surgery, to speed up waiting lists or for complementary care. The Spanish can freely purchase health care services from private health insurers that contract private health providers (e.g. Quirón, Ruber, etc.) or independent specialists.
Industry forces	Public VS Private	The Spanish National Health System provides Spanish citizens with universal coverage. The SNHS is a clear example of a Beveridge model: the Government acts as the main responsible for providing citizens with healthcare.
	Centralization VS Decentralization	The National Ministry of Health, Social Services and Equality (MSSSI) is the Government body responsible for the planning and execution of the national health policy, for planning and providing healthcare and for ensuring the right of citizens to health services. The MSSSI is responsible for actuations such as the legislation on pharmaceuticals or the definition of the portfolio of healthcare services that Regional Health Systems are obliged to provide. Spain comprises 17 highly decentralized regions (Autonomous Communities, ACs), which have the faculty in fields such as finances and healthcare. The Spanish National Government provides each AC with general resources

		according to their population, area and special conditions such as insularity. ACs can freely allocate those funds among their Ministries. This freedom brings out heterogeneity in health expenditure per capita and access to different baskets of services, as each AC can give more or less importance and support to health issues.
	Actors involved	<p>Distribution of competences in the SNS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State health administration (central government): basic legislation and general coordination of the SNS; international health issues; pharmaceutical policy. • 17 regional health administrations (Acs): regional health legislation; health insurance; health services planning; health services management and provision. • Local authorities (provinces and municipalities): sanitation; collaboration in health services provision and direct management of "residual" public health and community services.
	Health and social care integration	Citizens do not have a legally established right to social services. The provision of such services is at the discretion of the Autonomous Administration: access rights are governed by legislation at the level of the autonomous communities.
	Hospitals (per 100.000 population)	1,6
	Psychiatric beds (per million population)	38,7
Market forces	Population aged > 60 years (%)	23%
	Life expectancy at age 60 (years)	25
	Estimated prevalence of dementia per 1.000 population	2015: 18,5 2035: 28,0

	Population living in urban areas (%)	79%
	Population IT readiness (%)	92%
	Tendency to Informal Care (%)	38%

7.1.4 Business Model Environment for Israel

Macro Area	Key context variable	Israel
Key trends	National Socio-Health care System overview	Israel has a National Health Insurance (NHI) system that provides a broad benefits package to the population. There is free choice among four competing, non-profit-making health plans that receive NHI funds from the Government according to a capitation formula, called HMO (Health Maintenance Organizations). The system is financed primarily from public sources via payroll and general tax revenues.
	General government expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	59,80%

	Private expenditure on health as a percentage of total expenditure on health	40,20%
	Out-of-pocket expenditure as a percentage of private expenditure on health	64,50%
	Per capita total expenditure on health (PPP int. \$)	1.384
Macro-economic forces	Payment mechanisms	<p>Approximately 80% of hospital revenue comes from sales of services to health plans. The reimbursement of public hospitals in Israel takes place in the form of fee-for-service payments, per diem fees and case payments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A fee-for-service charge list established by the Government regulates payment for hospital outpatient care in ambulatory clinics; • most inpatient admissions are reimbursed on a per diem basis: the per diem rate is set by the Government; • differential case payments are established for about 30 types of admission: case payments were established in order to shorten waiting times, primarily for more expensive procedures and for moderately priced procedures with short hospital stays
	Sources of revenue and financial flow	<p>The system is financed primarily from public sources via payroll and general tax revenues.</p> <p>The HMOs are health insurance funds recognized by the Israeli National Health Insurance Law, and are obligated to a uniform basic basket of health services. They are allowed to offer supplemental health and care services beyond the basket, for an additional premium. Approximately 75% of the</p>

		population purchases complementary health insurance from one of the four health insurance funds that covers services outside the basic package, such as dental care, ancillary services, and provides choice of private provider and a third of the Israeli population buys commercial health insurance that offers additional benefits such as lump sum payments for certain diseases additional benefits for treatment abroad and cover for lifesaving medication not included in the public basket of services. A further two-thirds of the population also purchases commercial insurance for long-term care the vast majority through group policies purchased by their HMO.
Industry forces	Public VS Private	Israel has a tax-funded national health insurance system that provides its population with universal coverage of healthcare. There is free choice among four competing, non-profit-making health funds (HMOs), which receive NHI funds from the Government according to a capitation formula. The four HMOs are Clalit, Maccabi Healthcare Services, Kupat Holim Meuhedet and Leumit.
	Centralization VS Decentralization	Israel has a centralised governance model, which also applies to healthcare. However, there are Public Health Divisions that operate through regional and local offices. Their aim is to ensure the implementation of those policies and strategies developed at national level. Every HMO is also governed in a similar way. Although national headquarters are responsible for the management and planning, the operation of services is decentralised, to the Regional level and below that to the branch level, which eases access to care in the community.
	Actors involved	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Knesset ultimately determines laws and budgets. • The Ministry of Health has overall responsibility for the health of the population and the effective functioning of the health care system. It plans and determines health priorities, drafts health care laws to be discussed with the Knesset, provides adequate resources for NHI system, monitor and promote population health, ecc. • Health plans are voluntary, non-profit-making organizations, obliged to ensure that their members have access to a benefits package, as specified in the NHI Law. In return, the health plans receive an annual capitation fee per member from the Government. • Hospitals: While the Government owns approximately half of the acute beds, Clalit owns one-third

		of the acute beds and the remaining beds are owned by various non-profit-making and profit-making entities.
Health and social care integration		<p>The vast majority of elderly people live or are cared for at home, with only 4,5% residing in any kind of institutional setting (with less than 3% in a nursing home). This is due to the extensive care provided by families and the development of formal services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Day care centres: in addition to some 900 social clubs that provide a framework for activities and facilitate interpersonal contact and socialization for the elderly population that are in good health, a network of (at least 180) day care centres for the disabled elderly has been developed. Most centres are stand-alone organizations although some are affiliated with other institutions (sheltered housing, old-age homes and so on). Another significant development within the day care centre network has been the establishment of special programmes for the cognitively impaired, including elderly people with Alzheimer’s disease and other types of dementia. • Supportive neighborhoods: One of the most important and innovative developments in community care in recent years has been the supportive neighbourhood programme, designed to emphasize the neighbourhood as a force that provides the elderly with a sense of security and access to services. Elderly people who live in supportive neighborhoods in cities, towns or rural areas enjoy a “basket” of services that includes: a neighbourhood facilitator who ensures their personal safety, as well as the safety and security of their homes, and also provides home repairs; an emergency call button; a physician/ambulance on call 24 hours a day; social activities. • Institutional long-term care: Patients are categorized according to (one of) five levels of dependency with the institutions, and regulated by two ministries: the Ministry of Health and the Ministry of Social Affairs. Those families that are able to purchase care from a licensed long-term institution (whether profit-making or non-profit-making) are expected to do so. However, given the high cost of such care, more than two-thirds of families turn to the Ministry of Health for a subsidy.
Hospitals (per 100.000 population)		0,6

	Psychiatric beds (per million population)	43,8
Market forces	Population aged > 60 years (%)	15%
	Life expectancy at age 60 (years)	25
	Estimated prevalence of dementia per 1.000 population	2015: 10,4 2035: 15,1
	Population living in urban areas (%)	92%
	Population IT readiness (%)	/
	Tendency to Informal Care (%)	/

D3.1 - Business models, process with details on procedure for carrying out the various activities and identification of area for the introduction of IT solutions

7.2 Actions to address the needs and perceived relevance

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Detection	Patient detection	Reactive detection	4			4	0	0	5	4
		Proactive search I (Database parameters)	4			4	0	0	5	3
		Proactive search II (75 th birthday)	4			0	0	0	4	3
Diagnosis and assessment	Clinical	Clinical diagnosis	5		5	5	0	0	5	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Overall medical condition	5		5	5	5	5	4	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Medical instability	0		3	4	0	0	0	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Psychological	Behavior and mood	5		5		5	5	5	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Anosognosia	0		2	2	1	1	0	0
Diagnosis and assessment	Physical	Assess the Risk of malnutrition	5		5	5	5	5	3	5
Diagnosis and assessment	Functional	ADL	5		5	5	5	5	3	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Diagnosis and assessment		risk for falls	5		5	5	5	5	3	5
Diagnosis and assessment		Frailty	5		5	5	5	5	4	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Socio economic	Assess Socio economic state	5		5	5			5	4
Diagnosis and assessment	Caregiver burden	Assess Caregiver burden	5		5	5	5	5	2	4
Patient environmental needs	The person might not have an adequate and appropriate home	Assuring suitable living space	1		1	2	0	0	4	4
Patient environmental needs	The person might have problems keeping their home tidy and organized	Assuring maintenance of living space	3				3	5	2	3
Patient environmental needs	Buy food	Shopping assistant	2		3		3	4	2	4
Patient environmental needs	Eat in a safe way	Malnutrition avoidance	2		4		3	5	2	3

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient environmental needs	Patients not able to keep track of their expenses	Money budgeting	3		2	1	3	5	3	4
Patient environmental needs	Caring for someone else	Caring for someone else	1		0	0	1	0	4	4
Patient environmental needs	Wandering expose people to dangers	tracking / prevent wandering	0		1	3	0	4	0	0
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information about the disease, symptoms and evolution	4		5	5	1	0	4	4
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	Information on current condition and treatment	4		5	5	2	2	4	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient physical needs	People need to receive and understand information about their condition and treatment in a language they can understand	The patient can contact a health professional for questioning	4		3	3	0	0	5	5
Patient physical needs	People might need support for designing a physical activity plan	Physical activity plan and exercise	4		5	5	2	1	4	4
Patient physical needs	Drugs (chronic disease management)	Education on side-effects on medication treatment by clinical pharmacologist or clinical team coordinated by case manager	4		4	4	0	0	4	4
Patient physical needs	Have a prescription by general practitioner	Medication plan	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Patient physical needs	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions	Medication Reminders	4		4	4	5	5	4	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient physical needs	Eyesight/ hearing/ Communication		0				3	2	2	2
Patient physical needs	People can have high risk of fall	Fall detection	3		3	4	3	5	3	4
Patient physical needs	People need to be able to move	Immobility detection	3		3	3	3	5	3	4
Patient physical needs	Keeping neat and tidy	education, follow-up	2		2	2	3	5	2	2
Patient physical needs	Continence		0		1	1	1	4	0	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Access to non-pharmacological treatment	4		4	5	5	5	4	5
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Alternative treatments	4		4	4	3	3	4	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Brief psychotherapies	4		4	4	0	0	4	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Psychopharmacological treatment	0		0	0	0	0	3	3
Patient psychological needs	Psychological distress and behaviour: anxiety Sleeplessness, agitation, aggression etc.	Remote monitoring of psychological status	4		5	5	2	2	3	3
Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Cognitive stimulation	5		5	5	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient psychological needs	People might need help in daily activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Patient psychological needs	Alcohol abuse prevention	Alcohol abuse prevention	3		3	3	3	0	3	3
Patient psychological needs	inadvertent self-harm		1		1	1	0	1	0	0
Patient psychological needs	deliberate self-harm		0				0	1	0	0
Patient psychological needs	Psychotic symptoms	Monitoring hallucinations or delusions	0		3	4	3	4	4	4
Patient Social needs	Patient refuses help and sociality outside home / lives alone in an isolated house / does not have partners	social interaction	0		3	3	3	3	3	3
Patient Social needs	Intimate relationship		0		0	0	0	0	1	1

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient Social needs	The person might not have relatives / friends / etc. With whom realising social activities	Recommendation of social activities	1		2	2	1	2	3	4
Patient Social needs	People with cognitive problems might have problems with other people that might take advantage of their condition (i.e. using their money)	Abuse/Neglect prevention	1		1	2	0	2	2	2
Patient general needs	People might not be aware of available social services	information of the social benefits available in the area	4		4	4	3	4	4	4
Patient general needs	People are not able to contact social services or social workers	Patients can contact the social worker	4		4	4	2	0	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	2	0	4	4
Patient general needs	The person might have not knowledge about the legal aspects of the disease	Discuss financial and long-term care plans	4		4	4	1	0	4	4
Clinical team needs	Coordinate d care	Coordination of care	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Information sharing	Clinical team information sharing	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Improve diagnosis method	Improve diagnosis method	5		5	5	*	*	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Advising on deciding course of action	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Better access to and relevance of non-pharmacological therapies	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Clinical team needs	Standard of care	Standardized care pathway	5		5	5	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Clinical team needs	Accessibility	Facilitating access to medical services in rural/ isolated areas	3		2	3	0	0	5	5
Clinical team needs	Longitudinal treatment	comprehensive treatment of multiple training sessions and group therapy+ follow-up	5		5	5	3	3	5	5
Social care team needs	Information sharing	Health team information sharing (including social care)	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Social care team needs	Information sharing	To improve social awareness about the disease	4		5	5	3	3	5	5
Social care team needs	Information sharing	To inform general population, health professionals and relatives about the available social resources	4		5	5	5	5	5	5
Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate access to social services in rural/ isolated areas	3		3	3	0	0	4	4
Social care team needs	Accessibility	To facilitate and to speed up access to social services (Day Centres, Night Centres, etc.)	3		3	3	5	5	3	4

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Online Cognitive Training	5		5		3	3	5	5
Follow up	People could need help in daily life activities that imply memory functions	Monitoring of cognitive condition	5		5		3	3	5	5
Follow up	overall condition	monitoring overall condition	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Follow up	Remember timing and drugs according to prescriptions / ensure adherence	measurement of adherence and compliance of patients to treatment	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Follow up	social care	Assess timely changes evolving needs for social care support	5		5	5	5	5	5	5
Caregivers needs	Physical and psychological monitoring of the caregiver	Interventions with the caregiver	4		4	4	5	5	5	5

Need category	Need	Action to address the need	Israel		Spain		Italy		Sweden	
			M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D	M CI	M D
Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the evolution of symptoms and the disease	4		5	5	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Medical information for NFC	Information about the secondary effects of medication	4		4	4	3	3	4	4
Caregivers needs	Communication healthcare prof. - NFC	The caregiver can ask questions to the health professional	4		3	3	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about available social services in the area	4		4	4	5	5	4	4
Caregivers needs	Social care information for NFC	Information about legal aspects of the disease (living will, etc.)	4		4	4	3	3		

Table 68 – Needs, actions to address the needs and perceived relevance in the 4 Countries (adapted from D1.3)